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1. Introduction

Improving energy efficiency has become one of the most important pillars of the sustainable energy policy. The transition towards a sustainable socio-economic system is a must, and the alignment with the environmental boundary conditions (climate change) has given the world huge awareness on the need of undertaking this transition, by deploying all the necessary means to achieve the objectives of such energy policy.

The private sector, including energy service companies (ESCOs), is meant to play one of the main roles in developing the necessary know-how in order to provide services and solutions to the energy market, which should help to achieve significant energy cost reductions. In that path, ESCOs can handle projects, manage financial resources, and take decisions under engineering and scientific criteria by providing energy performance contracting (EPC), energy supplying contracting (ESC) or any other energy service. ESCOs share the unique characteristic to assume energy performance from the installation that is under the contract restrictions, assuming all the risks involved and linking their compensation to the performance of their implemented projects, thus incentivising competitiveness in this area and delivering energy savings oriented solutions [1].

The aim of this report is to provide an approach to different business models (BM) related with operation and energy services for the three case study thermal solutions, in order to ensure the correct performance and durability of the systems by handling all the necessary technical and financial information provided by the CHESSE SETUP system.

Through a close analysis of the current ESCO market situation, this Deliverable is meant to propose and develop an ESCO model for holistic energy efficiency retrofitting projects, focusing on the system developed by CHESSE SETUP project which consists on the optimal combination of solar thermal (ST) energy production, heat storage and heat pump use. This model, with its variances/differences regarding the implementation on the three demonstration pilot sites, should be able to provide a profitable, feasible and scalable business model (BM) to operate and maintain CHESSE SETUP solution, and to maximize its efficiency.

The model proposed is presented with the different terms and alternatives, as well as the benefits earned both for the client and for the ESCOs, and should be adjusted according to the three pilot's experiences to guarantee its replicability on similar conditions.

2. Objectives

The main objectives to be fulfilled by this report are the following:

- To calculate total cost of operation and evaluate a business model solution to apply for the three case studies of the project.
- To define real models on economic viability of different business strategies, also developing a measure and verification plan on energy savings and an energy/maintenance service to guarantee the maximum operation time of the solution.
- To ensure energy savings through expertise and know-how driven by ESCOs and the rest of the partners, taking into account not only economic and financial aspects but also technical and operational issues.
- To expand BMs evaluation to a standard solution that could be implemented in similar conditions.
- To develop a replication plan for scaling project results, providing an exploitation plan for all partners involved in the project and other companies, public entities or any other agent involved in the energy efficiency area.
- To achieve a wide implementation of CHESSETUP solution, by supporting local networks and value chains between public and private sector.

Veolia Serveis Catalunya, S.A.U. will lead Task 6.1, consisting in the analysis of different BMs for the three case studies thermal solutions, including:

- The calculation of total operational cost, providing know-how about the total operational cost of the systems including preventive, normative and corrective maintenance, installations operation, material replacement, installation, billing and indirect costs.
- A Measure and Verification Plan based on energy savings establishing the energy consumption baseline of the buildings and also including a measurement campaign.
- The analysis of BM strategies, from the economic viability and different energy services point of view (Energy Supply Contracting, Energy Performance Contracting, etc.).

3. Acronyms

ASHP – Air Sourced Heat Pump

BM – Business model

BMS – Building Management System

CAPEX – Capital Expenses

CF – Capacity Factor

CHP – Combined Heat and Power

DEM – Distributed Energy Management

DER – Distributed Energy Resources (DG, DS, DR, etc.)

DG – Distributed generation

DH – District Heating

DHC – District Heating and Cooling

DHW – Domestic Hot Water

DR – Demand response

DS – Distributed storage

DSF – Demand Side Flexibility

DSM – Demand Side Management

DSO – Distribution System Operator

EE – Energy Efficiency

EEB – Earth Energy Bank

EER – Energy Efficiency Ratio

EED – Energy Efficiency Directive

EF – Energy Flexibility

ESCO – Energy Service Company

ESC – Energy Supply Contracting

EPC – Energy Performance Contracting

EV – Electric Vehicle

GHG – Greenhouse Gases

GSHP – Ground Sourced Heat Pump

HP – Heat Pump

HVAC – Heating, Ventilating and Air Conditioning

ICE – Internal Combustion Engine

ICT – Information and Communication Technologies

IEA – International Energy Agency

IREC – Catalonia Institute for Energy Research

IRENA – International Renewable Energy Agency

MEB – Material Execution Budget

MPP – Maximum Power Point

M&V – Measurement and Verification

O&M – Operation and Maintenance

OPEX – Operation Expenses

P₁ – Energy Management

P₂ – Maintenance

P₃ – Full Warranty

P₄ – Improvement works and renewal of installations

PES – Primary Energy Savings

PHS – Pumped Hydropower Storage

PPA – Power Purchase Agreements

PV – Photovoltaic

PV-T – Photovoltaic and Thermal

RES – Renewable Energy Sources

SC – Space cooling

SCOP_{net} – Net Active Seasonal Average Efficiency for electrically driven heat pumps

SEC – Smart Energy Community

SEM – Smart Energy Management

SDG – Sustainable Development Goal

SH – Space heating

SHS – Sensible Heat Storage

SM – Smart Meter

SO – System Operator

SPER_{net} – Seasonal Primary Power-active Ratio for heat-driven heat pumps

SPF – Seasonal Performance Factor

ST – Solar Thermal

STES – Seasonal Thermal Energy Storage

TES – Thermal Energy Storage

TSO – Transmission System Operator

UTES – Underground Thermal Energy Storage

VAS – Value-Added Services

VRES – Variable Renewable Energy Sources (wind and PV)

4. Terms and definitions

Since there are many differences in the interpretation of what is entailed by ESCOs and the related action field in which they participate, some definitions must be delivered in order to establish the meaning of the language that is going to be used in this Deliverable. Based mainly on Directive 2006/32/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2006 on energy end-use efficiency and energy services and repealing Council Directive 93/76/EEC (no longer in force), and on Directive 2012/27/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on energy efficiency, amending Directives 2009/125/EC and 2010/30/EU and repealing Directives 2004/8/EC and 2006/32/EC, the main terms and definitions to be considered are the ones that follow:

- **Energy:** all forms of energy products, combustible fuels, heat, renewable energy, electricity, or any other form of energy, as defined in Article 2(d) of Regulation (EC) No 1099/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 October 2008 on energy statistics;
- **Primary energy consumption:** consumption of primary energy (energy in the form that is first accounted for in a statistical energy balance, before any form of transformation/conversion to secondary or tertiary forms of energy);
- **Final energy consumption:** all energy supplied to industry, transport, households, services and agriculture. It excludes deliveries to the energy conversion sector and the energy industries themselves;
- **Energy efficiency:** means the ratio of output of performance, service, goods or energy, to input of energy;
- **Energy savings:** an amount of saved energy determined by measuring and/or estimating consumption before and after implementation of an energy efficiency improvement measure, whilst ensuring normalisation for external conditions that affect energy consumption;
- **Energy efficiency improvement:** an increase in energy efficiency as a result of technological, behavioural and/or economic changes;
- **Energy service:** the physical benefit, utility or good derived from a combination of energy with energy-efficient technology or with action, which may include the operations, maintenance and control necessary to deliver the service, which is delivered on the basis of a contract and in normal circumstances has proven to result in verifiable and measurable or estimable energy efficiency improvement or primary energy savings.
- **Energy service provider:** a natural or legal person who delivers energy services or other energy efficiency improvement measures in a final customer's facility or premises;
- **Energy performance contracting (EPC):** a contractual arrangement between the beneficiary and the provider of an energy efficiency improvement measure, verified and monitored during the whole term of the contract, where investments (work, supply or service) in that measure are paid for in relation to

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a contractually agreed level of energy efficiency improvement or other agreed energy performance criterion, such as financial savings;

- **Energy supply contracting (ESC):** a contractual arrangement between the beneficiary and the provider of an energy efficiency improvement measure, where the focus is the reduction of supply costs rather than demand-side efficiency gains, with energy efficiency measures being typically limited to the energy supply and transformation side. The subject of this contract type is the supply of energy, usually in the form of heat.

Focusing on energy services terms, a wide range of activities can be offered under that concept. Following previous definition, energy services include a varied spectrum of activities delivered on the basis of a contract, which should lead to verifiable and measurable/estimable energy efficiency improvement and, subsequently, leading to primary energy savings and/or energy cost reduction. As stated on Annex XIII of Directive 2012/27/EU, the minimum items to be included in energy performance contracts with the public sector or in the associated tender specifications should mainly include:

- Clear and transparent list of the efficiency measures to be implemented or the efficiency results to be obtained.
- Guaranteed savings to be achieved by implementing the measures of the contract.
- Duration and milestones of the contract, terms and period of notice.
- Clear and transparent list of the obligations of each contracting party.
- Reference date(s) to establish achieved savings.
- Clear and transparent list of steps to be performed to implement a measure or package of measures and, where relevant, associated costs.
- Obligation to fully implement the measures in the contract and documentation of all changes made during the project.
- Regulations specifying the inclusion of equivalent requirements in any subcontracting with third parties.
- Clear and transparent display of financial implications of the project and distribution of the share of both parties in the monetary savings achieved (i.e. remuneration of the service provider).
- Clear and transparent provisions on measurement and verification of the guaranteed savings achieved, quality checks and guarantees.
- Provisions clarifying the procedure to deal with changing framework conditions that affect the content and the outcome of the contract (i.e. changing energy prices, use intensity of an installation).
- Detailed information on the obligations of each of the contracting party and of the penalties for their breach.

ESCOs hold a key role in the field of energy services providers, since they can provide a wide range of activities such as energy audit, energy supplying through installation

operation & maintenance, monitoring – measurement – verification strategies, long-term project financing, etc.

5. Business model: Definition and Analysis

Since there are different action strategies for companies in energy efficiency value chain to develop and implement a business plan, there is also many ways to determine the scope of a business model. That being said, a first approach to get in touch with the different existing methodologies to develop and implement a business plan is to define what a BM is and to take a look at the existing background regarding this subject. In order to do so, a first overview of European Union energy services markets must be considered. Once there's a first picture of the main sector data and what has happened over the last years regarding the energy services market, it is necessary to understand and define the main concepts of a BM: what's its aim, where does it come from and what is its place inside any firm. Since there are many ways to elaborate BMs, we might want to take a close look at different methodologies to create and assess BMs, so this section will be added too. Finally, since this report aims for the look of an applicable and feasible BM for the CHESS – SETUP Project, we would present an approach to its applicability to thermal energy storage, in order to deliver the lector many BMs related to the technical solution considered in the Project. After that, and regarding all the information available, an ESCO BM for the Project will be presented in order to take profit of the technical solution that will be implemented.

5.1. Overview of European Union energy services market

Boza-Kiss et al. (2017) performed a deep review on ESCO companies in the EU: *“Over the last decades, the ESCO market has been growing up in the European Union. Even with the crisis of 2008, that caused several affectations on the economical domain, the ESCO markets were able to overcome the challenges and keep improving the business opportunities”* [1].

The national ESCO market over the EU is composed by both local companies and, in many cases, international and/or multinational actors. The total EU Market was estimated at €2.4 billion ESCO revenue in 2015, with a forecasted growth to €2.8 billion in 2024 at a 1.7 % compound annual growth rate [1]. According to the JRC report, the EU ESCO market growth is expected to be driven by *“demand for capital to overcome the challenges of deferred maintenance, mounting regulatory and policy pressures, and growing interest in more comprehensive energy management strategies”*.

As stated in The Economist Energy and Technology Special Report from 2015 [2], *“ESCOs are already a \$6.5 billion-a-year industry in America and a \$12 billion one in China. Both are dwarfed by Europe, with €41 billion (\$56 billion) last year. Navigant Research, the consultancy, expects this to double by 2023. (...) The growth of a bond market to pay for energy-efficiency projects was an encouraging sign in 2014, when \$30 billion-40 billion were issued; this year's total is likely to be \$100 billion”* [1]. Although

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many previsions were made over the last years, the following figure shows the ESCO revenue by region on 2017, clearly improving the forecasting ESCOs revenue in the EU:

Figure 1 ESCO revenue by region, 2017 (Source: [3])

As stated by Boza-Kiss et al. (2017), "the value of the global ESCO market grew by 8% to \$28.6 billion in 2017; China's ESCO market continues to be the highest among the world, growing 11% to nearly \$17 billion in 2017. The EU ESCO market represents approximately 3% of the global total, increasing 2015 forecasts of many scientific and economic reports" [1]. The incoming figure represents the ESCO revenues by contract type among the main ESCO market participants over the world:

Figure 2 ESCO revenue by contract type in % proportion, 2019 (Source: [4])

5.1.1. Status of energy services markets

As stated again by Boza-Kiss et al. (2017), "The general energy service markets and energy supply contracts (ESC) have not been growing at the significant speed scoped over the last years. It remains stable though, since 18 of the 28 Member States reported no significant changes over their ESCO market distribution and economic impact, and only 7 ESCO markets out of those 28 reported a growth on the period 2014 – 2016. As stated in November 2019 IEA report on Energy Efficiency, in 2018 there was just a 1.2 %

improvement in primary energy intensity – an important indicator of how much energy is used by the global economy. This was significantly slower than the 1.7 % improvement in 2017, and marked the third year in a row the rate has declined. This should be a call for bold action by policy makers and investors, since not only the private sector has to take part of the energy service markets but also an optimal framework must be developed to ensure that the EU and the rest of the world keep walking through the path of sustainability and energy efficiency. Although the revenue of the ESCO market is increasing, it must be followed by an efficiency regulatory plan over the next years in order to fulfil Energy Union's goals on the next decades" [1].

That being said, and following the authors' approach, "an important feature about the EU ESCO market to be mentioned is that it is dominated by the small and medium sized enterprise (SME) sector. For example, the vast majority of Spain's ESCOs fall under the SME profile (93%) while only 7% of them are considered large enterprises. The same happens in Italy, where 95% of the firms dedicated to the energy service markets are SMEs and only 5% of them are considered large ones such as multinational groups" [1].

5.1.2. Status of EPC markets

Boza-Kiss et al. (2017) followed their review by adding that "companies that offer EPCs or its subtypes represent a subset of ESCO market. Since we cannot separate ESCO market from EPCs business work (it would be weird to consider the EPC market as a stand-alone industry since EPCs are, in a lot of cases, one of the main features and incomes of an ESCO), we can differentiate the EPC market from energy services markets by pointing out the fact that EPC providers represent a specific type of ESCO performance. On the other hand, not all ESCO companies can participate in the EPC market since they might not be experienced enough to provide a savings guarantee and to live from it (depending on the size of the client/contract). Since there are many guidelines and over the last decade there has been a huge increase of the legal improvement, promotion and clarification of the EPC concept, EPC markets have been largely growing across Europe. Given those improved conditions that have been affecting most of the EU countries, it is expected that the EPC markets will keep growing, although the high level of uncertainty that is associated to the energy sector" [1].

5.2. Primary concepts of business and financial models

The story beneath the usage of "business models" is farther than we can imagine. As stated by Magretta (2002) [5], "Business model was one of the great buzzwords of the Internet boom, routinely invoked (...). A good business model remains essential to every successful organization, whether it's a new venue or an established player. But before managers can apply the concept, they need a simple working definition that clears up the fuzziness associated with the term".

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Many questions must be asked, therefore answered: who is the customer? What does the customer value within the work done? How to make money out of a business? What is the underlying economic logic that explains how can we deliver value to customers with an appropriate product cost? To answer those questions, another Magretta (2002) [5] statement is considered: *“Business modelling is, in this sense, the managerial equivalent of the scientific method – you start with a hypothesis, which you then test in action and revise when necessary”*. When it comes to define a business model, Ovans (2015) [6] states that *“[Michael] Lewis, for example, offers up the simple of definitions – “All it really meant was how you planned to make money” – to make a simple point about the dot.com bubble (...)”*. Coming back to Magretta (2002) [5], we can think about business model as a two part combination: *“Part one includes all the activities associated with making something: designing it, purchasing raw materials, manufacturing, and so on. Part two includes all the activities associated with selling something: finding and reaching customers, transacting a sale, distributing the product, or delivering the service. A new business model may turn on designing a new product for an unmet need or on a process innovation. That is it may be new in either end”*.

Finally, Osterwalder, Pigneur & Tucci (2005) [7] stated that *“Based on WordNet 2.0, we interpret the word model as “a simplified description and representation of a complex entity or process” (...). A business model is a conceptual tool containing a set of objects, concepts and their relationship with the objective to express the business logic of a specific firm. Therefore, we must consider which concepts and relationships allow a simplified description and representation of what value is provided to customers, how this is done and with which financial consequences”*.

Osterwalder, Pigneur & Tucci (2005) [7] state that there is a lot of confusion and vague explanation on what BMs are, involving different approaches depending on the authors writing about BMs. Depending on their modelling rigour, ranging, items involved or overall business concept, it has been proved that there is no simple approach or understanding of what a BM is, therefore it requires a deep analysis and research of the concept itself.

To keep the argumentation by Osterwalder *et al.*, a three level hierarchy is considered when it comes to BMs understanding:

Figure 3 Business Model Concept Hierarchy (Source: [7])

Level 1 corresponds to the highest hierarchy among the concept: it consists of the definitions of what a BM is and it corresponds to an abstract vision, describing what a business does for a living. Additionally, level 2 consists on several generic BM types: the BM taxonomy of which BM resemble to each other and common characteristics between them. Finally, level 3 represent real world BMs, and also the conceptualization, representation and description of real world BMs that have been already deployed.

Over the years, BMs have been changing and evolving, and Osterwalder *et al.* depicted it through a five-phased evolution graphic:

Figure 4 Evolution of the Business Model Concept (Source: [7])

It is also important to note that terms like *strategy* and *business models* usually merge with each other, but again Magretta (2002) [5] states that "(...) a *business model* isn't the same thing as a *strategy*, even though many people use the terms interchangeably today. *Business models* describe, as a system, how the pieces of a business fit together.

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But they don't factor in one critical dimension of performance: competition. Sooner or later – and it is usually sooner – every enterprise runs into competitors. Dealing with that reality is strategy's job".

That being said, the main difference between a BM and a business strategy is that first one deals with the definition, classification and modelling of the business (how to fit the pieces together) and the second one explains how you will do better than your rivals. Strategy usually contemplates the execution and implementation while BM is more about how a business works as a system.

In that path, next step should be how to execute and implement BMs. The management and operation of a BM includes the translation of the plan to a concrete series of elements and interconnections, such as a business structure, its associated processes, the main infrastructure, etc.

Figure 5 Implementing Business Model Concept (Source: [7])

Last, but not least, is to define how the business plan fits in the firm: BM's place in the firm can be described as *"the blueprint of how a company does business. It is the translation of strategic issues, such as strategic positioning and strategic goals into a conceptual model that explicitly states how the business functions"*. [7] So the BM can be seen as a whole, a building plan that designs and carries out the business structure and systems, taking into account the main strategies and defining either the operational and physical form of it.

The relation of all the blocks can be drawn as a *business triangle*, in which the business represents the core and the main link between strategy, organization and systems and it is subject to external inputs such as social and/or technological advances, legal framework, competitiveness, etc.

Figure 6 The Business Model's place in the firm (Source: [7])

5.3. Review of existing methodologies to create and assess business models. Extrapolation to ESCO level and definition of partnerships/recruitment models

The previous Deliverable's section has pointed out the main concepts related to BMs and their location on the firm's strategy, organization and systems involved. The next section will focus on the analysis of different methodologies to create and assess BMs, identifying the key factors and developing a suitable business plan according to the firm's needs and, in this case, what could be more feasible and profitable regarding CHES – SETUP thermal energy solution, combining solar thermal energy production, heat storage and heat pump usage.

5.3.1. Canvas ontology

For so, the business model can be seen as a block composition; the definition provided by Osterwalder *et al.* is that a business model *"is a conceptual tool that contains a set of elements and their relationships and allows expressing the business logic of a specific firm. It is a description of the value a company offers to one or several segments of customers and of the architecture of the firm and its network of partners for creating, marketing, and delivering this value and relationship capital, to generate profitable and sustainable revenue streams"*.

Based on large information research, a nine block configuration is defined to help researchers, private and public agents and any other person or entity interested in the matter in the elaboration and implementation of a business model:

Pillar	Business Model Building Block	Description
Customer Interface	Value Proposition	Gives an overall view of a company's bundle of products and services
	Target Customer	Describes the segments of customers a company wants to offer value to.
	Distribution Channel	Describes the various means of the company to get in touch with its customers.
Infrastructure Management	Relationship	Explains the kind of links a company establishes between itself and its different customer segments.
	Value Configuration	Describes the arrangement of activities and resources.
	Core Competency	Outlines the competencies necessary to execute the Infrastructure company's business model.
Financial Aspects	Partner Network	Portrays the network of cooperative agreements with other companies necessary to efficiently offer and commercialize value.
	Cost Structure	Sums up the monetary consequences of the means employed in the business model.
	Revenue Model	Describes the way a company makes money through a variety of revenue flows.

Table 1 Nine Business Model Building Blocks (Source: [7])

Figure 7 Business Model ontology Canvas (Source: [8])

As seen from previous Figure 7, this business model ontology is known as Canvas, a tool for describing, analysing and designing business models developed by Alexander Osterwalder and Yves Pigneur. Based on many experiences from people all over the world, the *Business model generation* book points out how should it be used in order to “translate their business plans into the business processes that they (will) need to operate their business and that they are focused properly on being customer-centred in a way that makes the business as highly profitable as can be” (Bob Dunn, U.S.) [9].

The nine blocks cover the four main areas of a business: customers, offer, infrastructure and financial viability. A basic resume of each block's function and linkage is the one that follows:

- **Product innovation:** this first pillar of the analysis consists on covering all the product-related aspects. It can be translated to what the firm wants to offer to specific target customer segments via a value proposition, and what

capabilities the firm has to be able to assure in order to deliver this value. ICT have had a huge impact on product innovation, so it has to be integrated alongside with the value proposition to guarantee interoperability inside the firm.

- Value proposition: the statements of the benefits that are delivered by the firm to its external constituencies [8]. It is described by Osterwalder *et al.* as the definition of how valuable items such as the products and services (as well as any complementary value-added services) are packaged and offered to fulfil customer needs. It contains a description, a reasoning (use, risk reduction effort reduction, etc.), a life cycle analysis, a value level and a price level.
- **Customer interface/relationship**: the second pillar refers to the way the firm goes to the market. Again ICT has had a remarkable influence on the way a firm organizes and raises customer relationship. For so, this block covers all customer-related aspects, comprising the choice of a target customer, the channels which would be used to reach those customers and what kind of relationship would be established between the firm and the customer, meaning how and to whom the value proposition is delivered.
 - Target customer: an effective segmentation defines the type of customers the firm wants to address. If a firm is able to deploy an effective segmentation, it will be able to allocate investment resources to target customers that will be most attracted by its value proposition [8]. Defining the firm's market scope defines where to put the efforts and, for so, where does the firm not compete. Since companies can market either other companies (business-to-business, B2B) or individuals (business-to-consumer, B2C), a correct notion of the firm's target should help it define through which channels it could reach all of its targets.
 - Distribution Channel: as a major definition, distribution channels can be seen as the connection between a firm's value propositions and the customers the firm has targeted as potentially interested on the firm's business. It then describes how a firm can get in touch with its customers, and its major purpose is to establish the correct amount of product and/or service available at the right place, at the right time and to the right people [8]. A channel can be seen as an action pattern that allows a firm to deliver a value proposition to its target customers, giving an aggregated view of how to reach them, but it can be decomposed into channel links; since selling through channels simultaneously may cause some conflicts when addressed to the same set of customers, a channel link has its own reasoning, value level and price level so it can be part of the value proposition, enabling a wider set of interactions between the offering and the customer and, most of all, a different approach depending on the target.
 - Relationship: the customer relationship component is meant to determine the existent relationship between the firm and a target customer segment. This relationship is based on mechanisms,

describing the function to be accomplished between these two parties and it can be understood as the many kinds of interaction between them; a profitable relationship leads to a fruitful business so the search for new customers, the enhancement of profitability of existing ones and the extension of the existing relationships between firm and customer is the key to keep updated of the customer's needs and interests. In the end, the firm must aim for a good relationship in order to attract and seduce the targeted customer segments and maximize customer equity, optimizing its strategy in adding and keeping customers and selling them renewed and fresh value propositions.

- **Infrastructure Management:** third pillar of the framework is based on the value system configuration that is meant to deliver the value proposition correctly. It must describe how the firm creates value and maintains customer relationships, and what abilities are necessary to provide its value proposition [8] [10]. This can be understood as the specification of the business model's capabilities and resources, defining who's in charge of every activity execution and how these activities are related to each other.
 - Value configuration: it comprises all the necessary activities and existing links between them to create a valuable proposition for the customer. In order to do so, a good approach is to base those activities in the value chain framework; the value chain includes performance of low-cost and differentiated products delivery, including inbound and outbound logistics, operations, marketing and sales, and service; the value shop includes the research on what the client wants, including activities such as problem finding and solving, choice, control and evaluation and execution; the value network can be seen as the way the firm links customers who are interdependent, in which case the firm acts like an intermediary, in which case the main goal is to focus on network promotion and contract management rather than logistic and operation activities. As the reader may note, those three value configuration types are different, so each firm has to find its place inside the value chain framework.
 - Core competency: it outlines the necessary competencies to execute the companies' business models. Resources are highly needed when it comes to value creation: a common classification is to distinguish between tangible resources (plants, equipment, cash reserves, etc.), intangible resources (patents, copyrights, reputation, brands, trade secrets, etc.) and human resources (manpower needed to use either tangible or intangible resources) [8] [10].
 - Partner Network: last but not least, the firm must distribute the resources among the different partners and the elements needed for the activity configuration. Partnerships are co-operative agreements between two or more parties who voluntarily carry out an activity together on negotiated terms and conditions [8]. As business experience has proved over the years, partnerships and alliances have become an essential business strategy to be implemented by nowadays

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companies; from traditional joint ventures to the association between partners to optimize a company's logistic and operations. For example, outsourcing agreements can benefit a firm by achieving another partner's specialized knowledge or production structure that, otherwise, could not be achieved. Another aspect to be considered about partnerships is today's uncertain competitive environment; the cooperation between competitors can lead to a low cost launching product, since the firm has more information about market environment and behaviour. Thirdly, another motivation for partnering is the acquisition of specific resources that couldn't be developed in the first place.

- **Financial aspects:** the last pillar of the business model framework is transversal, since it is affected by the rest of the pillars seen previously. It represents how the firm takes profit of the different activities and strategies implemented; to survive among its competitors, the firm's profit model is composed by its revenue model and by its cost structure.
 - Revenue model: translates the value proposition to money earned, therefore, it can be seen the generation of incoming revenue streams [10]. A firm's revenue model can be made of different revenue streams, depending not only on different pricing models but also according to the target customer or the distribution channel.
 - Cost structure: represents the cost associated to the creation, marketing and delivery of the value proposition. The main goal is to take into account every cost related to resources, assets, activities and partner network relationships or any other activity that might represent a cost to the firm. Since the firm must focus on its core competencies and main activities, delegating non-core competencies on partner networks can provide important cost savings (the same could happen by improving the value proposition or redistributing the customer interface; that depends on how the firm distributes its costs and efforts).
 - Profit model: the difference between revenue and costs. It can be seen as an expression of the final output of the business model ontology, as it represents how the firm would profit from all its business structure. Whereas Product Innovation and Customer Relationship shall maximize revenue, an effective Infrastructure management shall minimize costs and, therefore, optimize the profit model [10].

Figure 8 Business Model Canvas tool, so groups of people can jointly start sketching and discussing business model elements with Post-It® notes or board makers (Source: [9])

5.3.2. e³ – value ontology

Following on the previous business model methodology, the e³ – value ontology is also meant to represent a networked business model, including its actors, links and the way the economic value is translated from one to another. The basic cornerstone of it is “*the notion of economic value, and how actors create, exchange and consume objects of economic value*” [11]. The e³ – value is composed by three main viewpoints, one of each representing related statements on an e-Business model:

- **Global actor viewpoint:** its intention is to explain the main value model to all stakeholders. It should show the following concepts:
 - Actors involved in the creation of the business idea (firms and customers);
 - Objects of economic value that might be created, exchanged and consumed by the actors;
 - Economic reciprocity, understood as the exchange of value incomes (value expected from the firm regarding the object of value delivered to the end-customers);
 - Combination, as a result of simultaneous value propositions offered or requested;
 - Phenomena, viewed from the customers’ perspective, that cause exchanges of objects between actors involved.
- **Detailed actor viewpoint:** composed by the representation of “constellations”, seen as a decomposition of part of the global actor viewpoint to simplify it and represent the existing partnerships. It can be seen as the isolation of part of the value model, restricting its actors involved who can decide over a specific part

of the business without the specific need of consulting or participating with other actors. It should contain:

- Partnerships between actors, which show the interaction between actors' objects of value (offered and requested);
 - Constellations of actors, to seek for a detailed viewpoint of the actors involved but avoiding too much complexity;
 - Expressions, as an explanation of the factors involved only in the detailed actor viewpoint rather than in a global viewpoint.
- **Value activity viewpoint:** detailed information about how actors take profit from their business or how to increase the value proposition for themselves. Its main goal is to differentiate between the actors involved and what they do, in order to establish the correct tasks to each actor. Hence, this assignment is a key factor into the firm's decision making, therefore the strategy that must be followed to fulfil the business objectives. It shows:
 - The value-creating or adding activities and the main related tasks assigned to each actor (who's in charge of each task).

Figure 9 e3 – value Business Model ontology (Source: [11])

5.3.3. SWOT ontology

A main definition of SWOT ontology can be found in the article *SWOT Analysis* by the authors Tanya Sammut-Bonnici and David Galea [12]. Citing his words: "A *SWOT analysis evaluates the internal strengths and weaknesses, and the external opportunities and threats in an organization's environment. The internal analysis is used to identify resources, capabilities, core competencies, and competitive advantages inherent to the organization. The external analysis identifies market opportunities and threats by looking at competitors' resources, the industry environment, and the general environment. The objective of a SWOT analysis is to use the knowledge an organization has about its internal and external environments and to formulate its strategy accordingly.*

Figure 10 SWOT ontology (Source: [11])

The components of an internal analysis of strengths and weaknesses are the firm's resources into the functional categories of financial, managerial, infrastructural, suppliers, manufacturing, distribution, marketing, and innovation resources:

- **Financial resources** are defined as the extent to which an organization has access to capital. Organizations with high brand equity and a high reputation are likely to have access to less expensive sources of finance.
- **Managerial resources** create the competencies of an organization in relation to the planning, control, and the leading of functions.
- **Infrastructural resources** are the backbone of the company allowing operations to run efficiently while providing information to improve the current processes.
- **Suppliers** and the nature of their products and services will have a bearing on the competitive advantage of an organization. Different methods and techniques are used to rate and evaluate suppliers. An effective assessment is based on the key deliverables of the product range, quality, availability, lead times, and service responsiveness.
- **Manufacturing resources** such as plant, machinery, automation, and technical support are essential to develop quality products. Flexibility in manufacturing is another factor to consider as it enables innovation and product development. Modular manufacturing and outsourcing of production are other factors that would cater for innovation and change in the product line.
- **Distribution channels** can be analysed to seek the strengths and weaknesses of logistics, partners, and distribution chain management. Other areas of assessment are the motivation of channel members, product, pricing, and motivation issues in the marketing channels.
- **Marketing functions** are reviewed in terms of their effectiveness concerning industry knowledge through research, product development, product life cycle

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management, pricing policies, distribution channel design, advertising, public relations, sales, and product promotion.

- **Brand equity** is the goodwill derived from the reputation of the organization and its brands. The strengths and weaknesses are extracted for different brand names, the market's perceptions of quality and reliability, and the organization's reputation with stakeholders such as suppliers, financiers, prospective employees, channel members, and customers. The objective of the analysis is to create brands that are differentiated from the competition, thereby reducing the number of substitutes in the marketplace.
- **Innovation resources** are part of the culture of an organization that encourages a climate for new ideas and technological capabilities, and has the capacity to innovate. Measureable innovation resources take the form of copyrights, patents, trademarks, and commercially sensitive business blueprints" [12].

SWOT analysis template Internal Strengths (S) and Weaknesses (W) (micro analysis)			
Internal environment	Strengths	Weaknesses	Strategic action
1. Financial	_____	_____	_____
2. Managerial	_____	_____	_____
3. Infrastructural	_____	_____	_____
4. Suppliers	_____	_____	_____
5. Manufacturing	_____	_____	_____
6. Distribution channels	_____	_____	_____
7. Marketing	_____	_____	_____
8. Brand equity	_____	_____	_____
9. Innovation resources	_____	_____	_____

Figure 11 SWOT template for the analysis of strengths and weaknesses (Source: [11])

5.4. Applying business methodologies to energy services market: Definition of main partnerships and revenue streams

5.4.1. Partnerships in energy services market

Companies forge partnerships for many reasons, and partnerships are becoming a cornerstone of many BMs. As seen previously, in order to reduce risks, to acquire resources or to simplify their BMs, companies create alliances to improve their strategies and become the most competitive they can [9]. We can distinguish between four different types of partnerships:

- Strategic alliances between non – competitors;
- Coopetition: strategic partnerships between competitors;
- Joint ventures to develop new businesses;
- Buyer – supplier relationships to assure reliable supplies.

Although this is a common partnership classification on how companies can match objectives and strategies together through different partnerships and/or associations, it is convenient to set the different partnerships present on energy services market. This section's aim is to list those BM partnerships so that we can clearly identify actors involved so that, depending on the project needs and the partners' expertise area, the most suitable partnership option can be deployed [9].

- **Private partnership**

A private partnership can be seen as the association between two or more private entities or citizens in order to accomplish the objectives of a BM. In that path, and always looking forward to its relationship with energy services markets, a private partnership can be understood as the co-ownership or participation in a major firm or citizenship cooperative which shares and invests in renewable and energy efficiency projects, either by dividing the major firm into different categories that might associate with each other to fulfil an EPC or ESC contract or, as it happens with energy cooperatives for private citizens, to simulate the ESCO model by purchasing a share and then becoming owners of the installations and thus share in the profits.

To be more specific about the main relationships that can be found in private partnerships, we can define the following categories:

- **ESCOs working for private ownerships:** operational scheme based on EPC/ESC contracts driven by an ESCO offering an energy service to a private client. Most agreements between customers and ESCOs are underpinned by EPCs, in which the ESCO is committed to install the necessary equipment, deploy the surveillance and provide an efficient performance established in the terms of a contract, stating the minimum guaranteed quality of energy generation or consumption. By providing a guaranteed level of energy savings, ESCOs can find a reliable source of revenue while the customer also takes profit of the improved energy management service provided.

Figure 12 Forfeiting scheme of SUNSHINE project (Source: [13])

The previous figure shows different flows between all participant agents of the forfeiting scheme; ESCO takes charge of the energy efficiency/renewable energy project, using the income of the energy savings or cost shaving to amortize the investment. ESCO doesn't receive any payments unless the project offers the guaranteed energy savings, through a previous definition of terms and conditions stated in the contract. Further information will be given about this kind of contracts but they must be taken into account since they have become one of the different ESCO BM over the last years.

- **Smart Energy Communities (SEC):** a common approach to SEC is the definition given by García Casals *et al.*: "the SEC integrates, aggregates and coordinates distributed energy services users and providers at neighbourhood level, facilitating the full and direct involvement of citizens in the configuration and operation of the energy system, and enabling the flow of smartness in such a way that the full potential from DER can be reaped for the shared benefit of the community and the rest of the energy system" [14]. In the same path, REScoop (Renewable Energy Sources cooperative) project has been working on BM's where citizens jointly own and participate in projects for SE, referred to as local energy communities or community energy projects.

As stated in their many dissemination material papers and reports, REScoop consortium offered a great vision and strategy to improve energy transition through the integration of the citizens, in order to control their production, transportation, distribution and supply. SECs usually follow 7 pillars that have been duly outlined by the International Cooperative Alliance:

- 1) Voluntary and open membership;
- 2) Democratic member control;
- 3) Economic participation through direct ownership;

- 4) Autonomy and independence;
- 5) Education, training and information;
- 6) Cooperating among cooperatives;
- 7) Concern for community.

Any citizen willing to participate in a REScoop can do it; since the moment someone purchases a cooperative share, therefore becoming a member or co-owner of local RES projects and EE initiatives, he/she becomes a member who can take profit from the programmes, installations deployed and all of the main pillars benefits stated before. The main objective of these cooperatives is to encourage members' participation, involving them in what and where the cooperative should be investing members' economic contribution and defining their energy tariffs according to power generation and distributed resources.

There are many reasons why local authorities may decide not to participate in some projects, then relying on a private partnership to promote some specific community need. Therefore, public entities can rely on REScoops, SECs and any other citizen lead projects for services that might require capital intensive investments like sustainability, energy efficiency and other energy related initiatives, rather than relying on commercial focused companies. It is quite satisfying for citizens and end users to know that REScoops use local energy sources by involving local citizens, thus keeping the money within the local community that would otherwise be lost [15]. This empowers citizens by boosting local economy, stimulating employment and interaction between stakeholders and using revenues (as a result from renewable energy projects deployment) to finance energy efficiency measures at a local scope, even applying not only to private needs but to invest it on building public equipment for the local community. For so, local authorities might sometimes consider this option rather than contracting an energy services firm, since the BM is quite different; although those firms can provide huge knowledge and expertise in energy issues, they usually won't get so directly in touch with citizens, plus some firms tend to limit their work to what's stated in the project rather than listening to what the community really needs. Numbers can state the profitability of the project but it is also important to create trustworthy bonds; for so, citizens' participation alongside with private firms could represent a successful business strategy to lead the way through energy transition [15, 16].

- **Public partnership**

When local authorities want to be in charge of some action by autonomously deploying all their infrastructure and resources, they can engage a public consortium agreement to act as a public partnership (involving different departments and/or local entities) working together for a specific task or public need. As local authorities are directly linked to citizens' concerns and worries, they've always serving initiatives and programmes to satisfy and/or take care of specific citizens' needs. Despite liberalisation and unbundling efforts in the 1990s and 2000s, there still are many municipal companies and consortiums withstanding and still acting as important players in today's energy market [15]. An example of municipalities who own sustainable energy projects by themselves is BCNecologia (*Agència d'Ecologia Urbana*

de Barcelona), a public consortium dedicated to rethink in key of sustainability [17]. This public partnership develops strategic projects aimed at reorienting cities to a more sustainable model transferable to urban systems from anywhere in the world. Their scope includes proposals and solutions in terms of energy, waste, water, mobility, urban planning, biodiversity and social cohesion.

During the 1990s, nearly every European national electricity and natural gas markets were still a monopoly, so EU and its Member States decided to liberalise those markets and open them to competition over the next years. Many measures were introduced to these markets; the main ones being listed as the following:

- Introduce independent regulators to monitor the sector;
- Clearly distinguish competitive parts (mostly retailers) and non-competitive parts (TSO, DSO);
- Obligate non-competitive parts to allow third parties to have access to the infrastructure (under technical and safety validate criterion);
- Free up the supply side of the market
- Give the customers free choice on their energy supplying company, removing any restrictions on customers from changing their supplier;

After that, main activities under energy sector such as energy production, transmission, distribution and supply were widely recognised as something that urged public exploitation under a strong framework; that's why governments at all level took up the glove and started investing in public partnerships to take care of citizens' needs.

- **Public – private partnerships**

In general terms, a public – private partnership (PPP) is a government service or private business that is funded and operated through a partnership between a State's government and one or more private-sector companies. This BM considers the participation of public entities through policies, regulations or economic instruments to encourage private sector's participation and collaborate in energy efficiency projects. PPPs usually involve a contract between the public entity and a private party, in which the private party provides a public service or project; the private company assumes financial, technical and operational risks associated o the service or project delivered [18].

In addition to public contracts and concessions, these kinds of partnerships are best suited for large scale operations in which the payment of public service cannot be ensured by the users/citizens. This structure promotes rapid implementation of projects, allowing state or local authorities to involve public enterprises in both the financing and management of a public service and take profit of their expertise in some specific knowledge area. As previously seen, some of the main characteristics of PPPs for EE financing projects include:

- Contractual relationship or agreement between a public entity and a private firm;

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- Allocation of risk between public and private partners in order to mitigate risks and encourage private knowledge in financing mobilise;
- Increased mobilisation of EE project financing;
- New business opportunities for private sector companies.

Type of PPP	Brief Description	PPP Features			
		Agreement between public and private entities	Allocation of risk between partners	Mobilization of private sector financing	Payment to private sector for providing services
Dedicated credit lines	Mechanism under which governments or donors provide low-interest loans to LFI to encourage them to offer sub-loans to implementers of EE projects	Loan agreement between partners	Project financing risk shared between partners	Private partner generally provides co-financing	LFI earns fee by on-lending funds at higher interest
Risk-sharing facilities	Mechanism where governments or multilateral banks offer guarantee product to absorb some EE project risks and encourage involvement of LFI in EE financing by reducing their risk	Guarantee Facility Agreement (GFA)	Public partner absorbs some financial risk	Risk reduction mobilises additional private-sector financing	LFI earns interest on additional loans mobilized
Energy saving performance contracts (ESPCs)	ESCO enters into term agreement with public agency to provide services, with payments contingent on demonstrated performance	Energy Services Agreement (ESA)	Performance risk generally borne by ESCO	ESCOs mobilize private-sector financing	Performance-based payment to ESCO

Figure 13 PPP mechanisms in the policy pathway (Source: [18])

5.4.2. Revenue streams

Nowadays business structure is mostly dominated by utilities and, as liberalized markets progress all over the world, by third-party energy retailers. DERs are changing the paradigm of traditional utility BMs; current business challenges focus on a long-term viability of the project, rising energy sales and taking profit from the exploitation of client's facilities [14].

To ensure the deployment of new BMs, we should first state a distinction between the main services than can be offered by utilities or third-party providers (as distribution grid services, electricity supply services, ancillary and/or emergency services, value-added services), as well as their associated regulations and costs. Valuable-added services (VAS) regarding the energy services market can be seen as energy services beyond supply and safety grid control, also including private or community level service: Renewable Energy Sources (RES), Distributed Generation (DG), Demand Response (DR), Energy Efficiency (EE), Energy Management Systems (EMS), micro grids, Electrical Vehicle (EV) charging, etc. VAS are often considered as optional or complementary services but today's end-users and customers can have (and are meant to have) an active participation into energy systems' behaviour [14]. Both utilities and third-party providers can deliver energy VAS as long as it fits with their profit model, with some examples as the following:

- VAS provided by utilities:
 - Enhanced analysis of meter data to customers/third-parties;
 - DER scheduling and dispatch through the utility's role as TSO/DSO.
- VAS offered by third-party providers:
 - Finance, sale, installation and/or operation of DG or DS;
 - Managing customers' participation in wholesale market DR programs;

Although there are much more services to be offered, basic ones can consist on implementing EE programs mandated by policy, as it happens in most of the Member States directly applying or transposing Energy Efficiency Directive (EED) [1].

Going back to energy VAS, unlocking the full transition potential to an energy service market truly based on applying innovative services, the citizens must be put in the centre of BMs' interest since their involvement in all VAS and basic services is the key factor to break through new economic solutions and paradigms [14]. The principles of the sharing economy, where the income from economic activities is shared between stakeholders and resources are optimized and used to increase social benefits, have recently led to studies that forecast huge value increase of the energy sector. Society is meant to benefit from a cleaner generation mix, improving social equity by creating value for low-income segments of population, since low-income households could participate from the value created by grid edge technologies [14]. As long as emerging social concepts like sharing economy can couple with the rise of DG and any other innovative technologies, the future of energy sector is guaranteed [14].

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The next question to be solved is: while having a clear idea of a BM, which are the main revenue streams associated to the ESCO market? In fact, there is a wide variety of revenue streams associated to energy service market, and their combination, if planned and executed properly, can lead to a huge success for any ESCO market participant. Some of the main revenue streams are the ones that follow:

- **Energy Management (EM):** understood as the different levels of EM services such as buildings, public and private services, single consumers and communities. If we emphasize on community level, the creation and exploitation of local micro grid transactions (DG, DS, DR, etc.) provides the tools for a shared economy where the benefits from community's behind-the-meter EM can be shared by all citizens involved, improving their governance and self-controlling of the installation.
- **EE through capacity markets:** since the improvement of grid's EE allows saving both energy and peak load, it can be traded through the capacity markets with other DER like DG and DR, so not only the grids takes profit from system reliability and stability but also encourages every agent's participation, so everyone complying with the participation terms will also take profit from this activity. EE is currently being deployed by utilities following regulatory framework and goals; EE measures include many benefits like the reduction of local pollution (improving air quality), reduction of GHG emissions, avoiding the need to build new power plants or the cost of producing additional energy to take care of the capacity and/or reserve and ancillary services markets, etc.
- **DR strategies:** the incoming figure of the aggregator can offer flexibility services through different markets available (mentioned reserves and other ancillary services, frequency regulation, etc.) or to offer their services to electricity retailers, improving energy selling by introducing DR strategies that could benefit either the firm and the end-users (cost reduction for all of them).
- **DG with integrated service:** it is commonly known that energy generation sector is growing its path to a more distributed paradigm every day, leading to on-site distributed generation and close energy supply not only for small users but also for public buildings, industry installations, energy communities, etc. Direct DG service, together with RES integration services and EF mechanisms constitute a revenue stream if associated with regulation and grid services.
- **Energy services provider:** as the main power of an ESCO, its task is evolving from trading energy to trading the final services pursued with energy use. As seen previously, an energy service provider/supplier is a natural or legal person who delivers energy services or other energy efficiency improvement measures in a final customer's facility or premises. The market is made up of various energy service suppliers, ranging from energy specialist, auditors, consultants, engineering and architectural firms, etc. The landscape of energy service providers is shown below:

Figure 14 Energy service providers/suppliers market according to their specialization (Source: [1])

- **Clean energy model transition:** as main actors in the energy services market, ESCOs should lead the transition towards a cleaner, more efficient and decarbonized business and economic model. A huge revenue profit model can be deployed if it's followed by a convenient legal framework and policies regarding the EU strategies. Firms can contribute to articulate BMs according to EM, EE, DR, DS, DG and any other actions that contribute to reduce energy consumption, improve energy use and prioritize RES. In that path, involving not only big customers but also small ones (small communities) is essential to avoid frustration over the citizenship, providing a compelling evidence and visibility that big changes are being made not only by energy sector actors, but also by the aggregation of small contributions (essential to track and monitor the transition progress).
- **Mobility services:** over the last years, not only building and industrial sectors have taken profit from the technological innovations in EE; improving urban conditions by reducing traffic congestion and space requirement for public and private vehicles has led to a huge transition on the transport sector. New policies tend to change the actual inefficient and individually-owned vehicles to a system-integrated and efficiently-operated EVs grid, deploying a public transport network based on an effective infrastructure. Although by now it is not one of the powerful ESCO targets, companies could specialize their core competitiveness in the future as long as they focus into smart mobility services BMs.

Figure 15 ESCO revenue by sector (public or private), 2019 (Source: [4])

5.5. Business models archetypes applicable to thermal energy storage

Electricity and thermal storage technologies have been present in EU for the last decades, especially on the Northern countries such as Sweden, Norway, Finland, Denmark, or the ones near them such as Germany. The implementation of energy storage seems inevitable if we think of a more sustainable future; it is a key element in balancing supply and demand and the use of BM innovation in this area results in higher firm performance, if there is coherence between its design themes and deployment [19]. For so, it is not surprising that energy storage deployments have increased so much over the last years, taking a look at the most installed energy storage technologies such as pumped hydro energy storage and molten salt thermal storage [20]. Energy storage technologies have evolved to a relatively modular system in order to adapt to every case scenario; despite such diversity, we can englobe the BMs into main categories that will be analysed and discussed on the next sections. The first one correspond to the main electricity and thermal storage BM archetypes (since they can be matched together although the different storage technology, which would lead to an even bigger analysis that is not this report's objective) and other BMs that deploy energy technologies in conjunction with solar PV panels, which matches with the CHESS – SETUP thermal energy solution.

5.5.1. Energy storage for end-user customers

This BM structure is conceived for installed storage assets at customer sites, regarding the deployment of the technology on the end-user facilities. This model is referred to

energy storage systems installed at customer facilities to manage peak demand charges and set the parameters to match the energy storage with lower energy prices or maximum generation (depending on the demand response strategy, under time-of-use or real-time pricings or under load shifting, load shedding and other direct load control and management systems) [21].

The main objective of deploying residential energy storage systems, according to Scott P. Burger and Max Luke (2016) has been to "increase the profitability of solar PV systems through increasing "self-consumption" (i.e. minimizing the export of energy produced onsite). (...) As technology costs have fallen, providing backup power to residential customers and critical commercial and industrial loads has also emerged as a driver" [20]. These BMs are usually performed by EPC contracts (shared or guaranteed savings arrangements) or through the sale and financing of the storage assets.

Figure 16 Generic energy storage for end-user Business Model structure (Source: [20])

5.5.2. Energy storage and PV energy generation optimization for end-user customers

This BM structure is focused on taking into account a PV generation and energy storage partnership (as several major PV producers and electricity/thermal storage business have joined forces over the last years). Since CHESSETUP thermal energy solution is not meant to connect distributed PV and storage assets with bulk power system markets or operators, this model is applicable in terms of maximizing end-users' financial returns without integrating with the market or TSO/DSO operators, therefore its main interest is to create an efficient, profitable and scalable solution to maximize the use of energy storage and reduce end-users' energy demand as much as possible. The main scheme of this BM could be the one that follows:

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Figure 17 Generic energy storage and PV production for end-user Business Model structure (Source: [20])

As it is well known, integrating any form of RES generation with any form of storage provides a decrease on conventional grid systems' dependency, therefore it contributes to deploying economic attractive solutions and enhance system-wide economic implications of integrating PV and storage systems in terms of network services. As stated on Burger and Luke's deep analysis on BMs for DER, *"Of particular interest is the ability for these systems to enable the system host to significantly reduce or eliminate their total consumption of energy from the bulk power system, thereby reducing network congestion and deferring investments in network reinforcements (but also commonly resulting in a shift of sunk network costs from the system hosts to other network users)"*.

It is not casual that, over the last years, different partnerships have been performed between solar PV companies and energy storage companies; many solar thermal or PV plants have matched their plant design and operation with different ESS so that overall system performance can increase the partnership's revenue streams by diversifying the services provided and cover the needs of either TSOs/DSOs (for example, explicit/incentive-based DR programs such as Direct Load Control (DLC), Interruptible/curtailable service market, emergency DR programs, demand bidding, capacity market or ancillary service market) or end users.

As stated again on Burger and Luke's deep analysis on BMs for DER, *"A number of business models have emerged attempting to bring "firm" solar PV resources to market by pairing solar PV and storage technologies. The aggregations of PV and storage (and, in some cases, other technologies, such as demand response and distributed generators) are often termed "virtual power plants," or "VPPs." Revenue streams are structured around the sales and financing of the assets and fees for brokering market interactions on behalf of the system hosts. In certain cases, businesses will own the projects and earn revenues on the sales of energy (most often under long term power purchase agreements), operating reserve, and capacity services (i.e. commodity sales revenues)"*.

Figure 18 Generic energy storage and PV production for end-user and system co-optimization Business Model structure (Source: [20])

Anyways, and as noted previously, solar-plus-storage systems as CHSS SETUP are meant to be deployed at customer site in order to increase energy self-consumption and pairing on-site RES generation curve with client’s demand curve, trying to match them as much as possible in order to reduce energy consumption and lower energy costs as much as possible, as well as increasing self-sufficiency and decreasing grid dependency. While offering solar PV/thermal generation with energy storage solutions, those business tend to sell products directly to commercial, industrial or residential customers and structure revenue streams around the sales and financing of all equipment and services involved.

Solar-plus-storage for end-user and system co-optimization business models		
<u>Solar-plus-storage for end-user and system co-optimization</u> Typical customers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Residential, C/I/M, Industrial <-> Regulated utility, ISO/TSO/RTO Typical Services: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy, firm capacity, operating reserves 	Solar-plus-storage developers	Sunverge (United States)
		Solar Grid Storage/ SunEdison (United States)
	Virtual power plant developers	Lichtblick (Europe)
		DONG Powerhub (Europe)

Figure 19 Energy storage and PV production for end-user and system co-optimization Business Model examples (Source: [20])

6. Proposed ESCO business model for CHESS – SETUP Project

VEOLIA proposes an Energy Savings and Maintenance Contracting model, which was introduced by the *Instituto para la Diversificación y el Ahorro de la Energía (IDAE)* where the ESCO takes the responsibility to supply the services engaged (such as heating and/or cooling, electricity, etc.) [22]. This model is composed by the following terms:

- P1: Energy Management
- P2: Maintenance
- P3: Full Warranty
- P4: Improvement works and renewal of installations

All of them are described in the following chapters.

6.1. P1 – Energy Management

This term refers to all energy management needed for the correct operation of the installation contract, such as the energy management supply (fuel and electricity), the quality, quantity, using control and the supply guarantees.

The ESCO is responsible to provide the client a set of agreed services (such as heating, lighting, etc.), even taking responsibility of the installation's energy purchase in order to ensure the client an immediate save compared with the actual energetic cost. In this way, the more efficient and economical the ESCO's services are, the higher the benefits will be. This is an incentive to work in the most efficient way.

These types of contracts are used to be long term ones, and then ESCO is the one providing both maintenance and exploitation of the installation during the entire contract. These kinds of contracts are very common when the client wants to outsource the installations and also to finance the investment needed.

There are different models when contracting energy services depending on the measures taken. The most common are:

6.1.1. Energy Performance Contracting

In an Energy Performance Contracting (EPC) the services provided by the ESCO must be linked to an energy efficiency improvement or measurable energy saving.

According to the Directive 2012/27/EU of the European Parliament, based on efficiency of the final energy use and services, the EPC is defined as *“a contractual arrangement between the beneficiary and the provider of an energy efficiency improvement measure, which must be verified and monitored during the whole term of the contract, where investments (work, supply or service) in that measure are paid for in relation to a contractually agreed level of energy efficiency improvement or other agreed energy performance criterion, such as financial savings”*.

As a resume, an EPC is an agreement between a client and an ESCO, who guarantees the investment return taking into account some guaranteed savings as a result of an energy efficiency improvement application. As stated by the IEA, *“the EPC commits the ESCO to installing the necessary equipment, provides a performance guarantee and establishes the terms of any upfront or ongoing payments, which are intended to be less than the financial savings realised by the project”* [4].

The performance and energy saving improvement measures can include modifications on the installations that require an investment.

In the EPC there are basically two types of contracts:

- **Guaranteed Savings Contract:** The ESCO guarantees at least the minimum savings that will be obtained with the implementation of the project and receives an amount of money for the incurred costs and the project profitability. The investments are generally assumed by the client, while the ESCO takes on the technical risk.
- **Shared Savings Contract:** The savings obtained with the implementation of an energy efficiency project are shared between the client and the ESCO. In that case, ESCO assumes both technical and credit risk (of the client), which can be of value to the client as it avoids the need for upfront capital costs, with ongoing payments to the ESCO based on the savings obtained.

For each kind of contract described above there could be 3 different cases comparing the energy real consumption cost vs the estimated one:

CASE 1: Real Cost = Estimated Cost
CASE 2: Real Cost > Estimated Cost
CASE 3: Real Cost < Estimated Cost

Figure 20 Savings distribution in a Guaranteed Service Contract

In CASE 2, the extra consumption cost is assumed by the ESCO, who pays to the client the correspondent amount of money due to the objective has not been reached.

In CASE 3, the profits are divided between the client and the ESCO depending on the percentage accorded in the contract.

Figure 21 Savings distribution in a Shared Savings Contract with investment

In CASE 2 the ESCO gains less benefit as the energy consumption has been higher than initially expected.

6.1.2. Energy Supply Contracting

In the Energy Supply Contracting (ESC) the energy service is based on the efficiency of the energy supplied for: heating, cooling, steam or compressed air, and it is contracted and measured according to a fixed price for the MWh supplied. This BM usually includes the purchase of the fuel/electricity and is the ESCO who establishes its price €/kWh to the client.

Figure 22 Energy Supply Contracting

6.1.3. "Forfeit" Contracting

In the "Forfeit" contracts there is an agreed amount of energy (Guaranteed Consumption - GC) and the price per year is fixed with some parameters such as day-degrees, usage time, etc. This price is reviewed annually according to the variation of these parameters (Revised Guaranteed Consumption – RGC) with a formula established at the beginning of the contract.

In this contracting plan there can be different scenarios:

- Real Consumption > Revised Guaranteed Consumption: the ESCO is the one who pays the extra cost.
- Real Consumption < Revised Guaranteed Consumption: the savings are shared between the client and the ESCO in a stated percentage.
- Revised Guaranteed Consumption < Guaranteed Consumption: the ESCO returns the difference to the client.

Figure 23 Forfeit Contracting Scenarios

6.2. P2 – Maintenance

This term refers to the different types of maintenance that must be applied in order to keep the good working and preservation conditions of the installation and equipment, as well as ensure their continuous operation, effectiveness and efficiency.

The objectives are to comply with current rules and regulations, keep the perfect working and preservation of the installation, guarantee the permanent performance availability and also achieve a high feasibility and security degree.

In order to calculate the P2 cost, the elements to take into account are basically the personnel costs (operational staff, specialists, etc.), materials, transportation and vehicles, communication and management systems, the subcontracting and the CMMS and energy supervision, among others. Taking all these into account, an annual price is fixed and then the ESCO is the responsible to take care of the client's installations maintenance.

6.3. P₃ – Full Warranty

The full warranty service includes the reparation of all the failures that may appear in the equipment listed on the contract, including the labour costs and the materials needed to repair them as well as all the substitutions of the equipment at the end of its useful life.

The client pays a fixed amount every year which is calculated by the services company considering the possible costs of the expected reparations, the technical risks and the substitution costs. The client has the guarantee that all the reparations and substitutions will be covered during the period of the contract. The ESCO must ensure the correct performance and maintenance of the installation in order to avoid possible failures and having to replace non-considered material or equipment.

Figure 24 P₃ schematic evolution of a new installation

6.4. P₄ – Improvement works and renewal of installations

This term refers to the realization and finance of the installation's renewable and improvement works.

There are usually two types of financing possibilities: the client's self-financing and the third-party financing. In the first one, the client assumes the investment costs whereas in the second one there is a contractual arrangement involving a third party that provides the capital for that measure and charges the beneficiary an equivalent fee. This fee is related to the energy savings achieved as a result of the energy efficiency improvement measure. That third party may or may not be an ESCO.

The main reasons for a P₄ are to invest in new equipment for a performance improvement, introduce renewable energies to the system, adapt old installations to the current regulations and also achieve a security improvement.

Figure 25 Third-party financing by an ESCO.

Figure 26 Third-party financing by a bank

7. ESCO business model benefits

The most attractive point of this model is the externalization of the energy services. From an energy saving engagement, the ESCO “takes control” of the client’s installation and ensures an improvement on the energy consumption after its exploitation and some investments, which costs will be amortized at the end of the contract. After that, when the contract runs out, the client has a more efficient installation with a lower energy consumption.

Figure 27 Plan phases

The key point during the ESCO’s exploitation of the installation remains in the control and motorization increase in order to reduce the operational costs.

The externalization of the energetic services offers:

- Energy savings and emissions reduction (CO₂).
- Energetic and exploitation guaranteed costs.
- Transfer of the technical operational risk.
- Normative and legal compliance of all the activities.
- Optimize its assets, with a comprehensive maintenance plan.
- Develop a corporate image, engaged with the energy efficiency.
- Permits the financing of the installations.

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Apart from that, one of the main goals of this type of contract is that it offers different types of contracting depending on the client's needs as represented in the figure below:

Figure 28 Terms contracting

This combination of terms allows the ESCO to generate its business plan depending on the different needs that the client may have and determinate how to make its offer more attractive and profitable.

8. Barriers and success factors

As stated by Boza-Kiss et al. (2017), "Despite considerable efforts to promote the energy services market development, persistent obstacles inhibit many cost-effective energy efficiency projects and prevent the full development of the energy services industry. (...) Some of the barriers are interrelated and act together to inhibit the deployment of energy efficiency investments, while many of the barriers are hereditary to the general nature of energy efficiency. These are divided into: information & awareness, institutional & legislative, financial, market & external, technical & administrative and behavioural. With more projects taken off the ground, it is expected that several entry-level barriers will be overcome in certain countries. In addition to these general barriers, specific sectors and countries have unique constraints that must be addressed if the energy services market is to reach its full potential" [1].

Figure 29 Mapping of ESCO-related barriers (Source: [1])

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Following the main political concerns, and as stated in Deliverable 2.3 about the main legislation/applicable framework regarding the CHESSE SETUP system deployment at the demonstration pilot sites, each demonstration pilot site (divided in two countries, Spain and United Kingdom) has its own regulations that have to be taken into account when designing, deploying and commissioning an energy project like CHESSE SETUP. Both countries have very limited thermal energy storage regulations, which means that a lot of work must be done to match existing technology that could be provided/sold in the market with a strong and concise framework.

In this spirit, and taking into account all of the pilot islands' energy demand and supply, existing RES, and regulatory framework conditions (including RES generation, thermal energy storage, building regulations, distributed generation (DG) issues or self-consumption and energy injection to the grid, among others), the CHESSE SETUP project faced many constraints and barriers that still remain among EU Member States [1]. Following that path, we should define a methodology to characterise and define suitable scenarios and overcome those barriers by complying with all existing laws, but being conscious that every country transposes Europe's Directives with slight differences. Introducing a methodology that includes a PEST assessment (political, economic, social and technological factor), those areas have to be taken into account when running the project:

- **Political conditions:** the enormous potential and benefits of energy communities and self-sufficient citizens is leading to a significant update and improvement of energy policy and regulation, but it has not always been this way and this law reinforcement on energy efficiency has different grades of penetration in every European country. For instance, actual regulatory barriers in some countries such as obligation (or, in the other hand, the inability) to inject electricity to the grid, requirements linked to the size and building of an installation, etc., imply serious challenges to overcome while deploying CHESSE SETUP or any other EU energy projects. Those barriers must be lifted since prosumers/energy communities should be able to freely enjoy the fruits of their own production and, therefore, to become full owners of their energy dispatching and sharing. Again as stated by Boza-Kiss *et al.* (2017), "*Under certain circumstances, the accounting treatment of EPC affects the ability of the public sector to account EPC projects as off-balance sheet investments*" [1].
- **Technological factors:** RES generation and SHSS combined represent a high potential and emerging mixture of technologies. For so, their union can lead to a great number of technology solutions and further deployments, creating above mentioned synergies between technologies with a high maturity level and innovative ones. But sometimes the lack of common technical standards, in order to achieve increased interoperability between energy management solutions while considering both integration with technical equipment and leveraging ICT systems (due to the heterogeneous market and varied

suppliers/manufacturers), represents an important barrier while deploying CHESSETUP or any other EU energy projects.

- **Social issues:** one of the main clues of the EU projects is to successfully recruit and engage users to take an active role in energy management and self-sufficiency. For so, it is essential to create a cooperative movement not only based on economical revenues or outcomes but also implying social concerns. Doing things in cooperative/collaborative way adds benefits not only to each individual but also to a community level. Some other projects have already faced recruitment issues and information asymmetry among users and local authorities: it is not new to find that one party has more information than another, leading to a misunderstanding of the project goals and expectations. The lack of knowledge around RES and DR should be one of the main social issues to fix, enabling end users to know exactly what are they doing, why and the benefits of their actions for the whole community. Boza-Kiss *et al.* (2017) stated that *"Users, clients and investors are faced with the complexity of certain markets and contracts. For example, energy performance contracting is a relatively risky business for energy suppliers and service and requires clear framework conditions and well-defined user behaviour in order to provide sufficient confidence that the investment will be recouped. While this is generally the case with commercial and public service customers, residential end-users represent a higher risk associated with an unpredictable element of user behaviour"* [1].
- **Economic and financial factors:** last but not least, the economy has a significant role in every project or initiative, special if it implies innovative solutions. Sometimes incentives for market players are not aligned to ensure the most efficient, flexible and economic solution. Financial incentives are not big enough for customers to take part actively in the grid balancing and self-sufficiency, so this needs to be taken into account. As the CHESSETUP project is aligned with EU policies, aiming to deploy an innovative solution and exploring new forms of flexibility and other benefits to many actors in the energy system, it seeks for cost reflectivity but also to raise awareness on many climatic and environmental issues, but these benefits are not monetized. The existing energy market players are already positioned and do have a lot of influence through policy and regulatory processes, which makes introducing new business models and exploitation plans more challenging for the CHESSETUP project and any other EU energy projects. Boza-Kiss *et al.* (2017) stated that *"Energy prices have a significant impact on what is cost-effective. Low energy prices mean that short-term returns on investment, in particular for extensive investments and associated services, are difficult to demonstrate. In addition, energy price volatility may have a major impact on the deployment of energy efficiency measures. (...) In addition, small scale projects are not compatible with energy performance contracting as they generally imply high transaction costs. (...) split incentives can severely limit market penetration of*

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ESCOs and EPC-related projects in the rental and multi-family sectors. Misaligned financial incentives exist in both residential and non-residential (e.g. offices) sectors” [1]. Last but not least, Boza-Kiss et al. (2017) also stated that “Energy-efficiency projects compete for scarce capital with more traditional investments such as small power plants, other type of building improvement, or industrial expansion. Investors might not have sufficient capital and would be forced to draw on their lines of credit in order to invest in energy efficiency measures. Moreover, companies generally add energy costs under overhead costs, and energy consumption is considered as secondary issue with regards to investment decisions. The multiple benefits of energy efficiency improvements in terms of e.g. increased asset value, increase comfort or productivity, health improvements are also rarely known and taken into account when making the investment decision” [1].

Moving on, one of the main issues to be tackled when deploying an EPC is the risk analysis: as every project in other fields, investing in a certain activity involves assuming some risks that inherently come with the task performed. When talking about industrial contexts (but that could also apply to commercial and residential areas), the risk analysis consists of four different processes:

1. Identifying underlying sources of risk;
2. Determining the pathways and triggers by which such risks can materialize;
3. Estimate the potential consequences of these risks under various scenarios;
4. Provide the means and tools to mitigate these consequences.

Depending on the risk evaluation period, the main engineering risks of energy performance contracts that ESCOs could perform regarding TES systems can be distributed the following way:

Short-term risks:

- Market risks, seen as uncertainties of the market, client demand and industry competitiveness. This includes:
 - There already is a firm in the market providing an equivalent performance TES system that directly competes with CHESSETUP project solution (either at a more competitive price with the same/similar features);
 - The know-how on TES systems is widely spread on the market, meaning it is easy to counterfeit the solution/service offered;
 - The CHESSETUP project replication/scalability potential is limited, meaning the solution/service provided is either inefficient, unfeasible, too expensive, etc.
 - There are no competitive manufacturers in terms of equipment providing, meaning there is no potential to exploit CHESSETUP results.

Mid-term risks:

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- Technology risk, meaning the risks inherently associated to the technology configuration, operation principles and performance. This includes:
 - Difficulties on ensuring whether the energy-saving technology is able to achieve its expected energy and economic savings;
 - The CHES SETUP project replication/escalation results in a performance lower than market expectations (meaning there already is a solution in the market that could provide a better performance than ours);
- Management risk, meaning that it unpredictable factors can affect the management and operation of the technology since VLC provides know-how on O&M works, forecasting and management methodologies but, in the end, the client is the one who's going to take the final decisions on its energy behaviour. This includes:
 - Missing/wrong information provided by the client regarding its actual facilities energy consumption/production and dispatching;
 - Lack of management ability and experience from the client on energy assets;
 - Wrong strategies/decision-making factors considered by the client's ownership;
 - Contract risks, meaning that either the client refuses to perform the responsibilities stipulated in the contract, or that the contract was incomplete in terms of ESCOs assurances;
 - Quality risks, such as delays in the material/equipment supply, wrong purchasing plan, malfunctioning equipment due to manufacturers' damaged outcomes/quality impairment.

Long-term risks:

- Political and legal risk, in terms of inconsistent legal framework for energy services contracts, lack of precise and specific ESCO regulation in terms of contracting, lack of long-term vision and perspective of policymakers, variable and uncertain law deployments, etc.
- Financial risk, including the inherent risk associated to a project's investment such as changes in inflation or interest rates during contract period due to force majeure (natural disasters, wars, economic crisis, etc.), lack of boosting fund conditions, inadequate business plan on its application to the client's needs, etc.

The ESCO should plan on solving all those issues through an efficient, effective and robust methodology consisting on developing a risk analysis and management. There are many ways of engaging and keeping a risk management plan in ESCOs but it should imply the following terms:

- 1. Establish strategic objectives and perform baseline assessments:** this includes creating the baseline organizational responsibility in the company to

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assess risk issues regarding TES projects. In that phase, the ESCO should clearly define its company goals, perspectives and achievements to develop a baseline potential for TES projects.

2. **Identify sources of risk:** as stated previously, the ESCO already figured out which are the main risks in developing TES systems since experience comes out from CHESSE SETUP Project. Taking into account major activities, timing and resources involved, the ESCO must associate each of the short-term, mid-term and long-term risks with an action plan phase, regarding all key actors and processes involved, identifying areas of potential concern or failure and qualitatively prioritizing these in terms of their consequences for the project, starting from minor inconvenience to fatal ones.
3. **Risk assessment:** using the convenient project management tools, the ESCO must determine what triggers and pathways associated with the many risks identified (including key events and scenarios generated) might elicit these. A basic approach to every risk analysis is to create different scenarios whether those potential concern or failure areas fall under the risk considered, evaluating its impact on the project (either in terms of time or costs).
4. **Risk mitigation and hedging:** once risk factors that can harm the TES project (and therefore the firm's goals and objectives regarding this business line) have been considered, the ESCO should perform the preventive and corrective actions in order to avoid or minimise the risks to an acceptable level; this might involve hedging of cash flows, assurances and any other forms of coverage under the worse scenarios considered.
5. **Project initiation and ongoing control:** lastly, the ESCO should be committed to determine the conditions under which the TES project can be developed, commissioned and delivered to the client through a management plan where the benefits from it clearly outweigh residual risks, establishing contractual and management systems to remain within these bounds of acceptable risk. When talking about larger projects, this will also entail contingent responses to financial surprises as well as insurance provisions for serious disruptions to project operations.

9. Measure and Verification Plan

In order to calculate energy savings of the different thermal solutions, a Measure and Verification Plan must be developed, establishing the baseline energy consumption of the buildings involved as demonstration pilot sites depending on the environmental conditions and internal use of each building. Therefore, this section is completely based on the International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol (IPMVP), developed by the Efficiency Valuation Organization (EVO) which is a non-profit private association [23] [24].

9.1. Purpose and objectives of the IPMVP protocol

EVO publishes the IPMVP in order to increase investment over energy efficiency and water projects, demand response and management and overall renewable energy projects around the world, promoting investments in efficiency under the following activities:

- The IPMVP protocol documents ordinary terms and methods for evaluating the outcome of energy projects for consumers, vendors, and financiers. Some of these terms and methods can be used in project contracting, although the IPMVP protocol does not specifically offer contracting language.
- The IPMVP protocol provides methods, with different levels of cost and accuracy, to determine savings¹ for both a global consumption centre and individual energy conservation measures (ECMs);
- The IPMVP protocol specifies the content of a Measurement and Verification Plan (M&V Plan). This M&V plan adheres to widely accepted fundamental principles of M&V, and will certainly produce a verifiable savings report. An M&V plan must be developed for each specific project by a qualified professional.
- The IPMVP protocol is applicable to a wide variety of consumer centres, including newly constructed buildings, existing buildings, and industrial processes.
- The IPMVP protocol is also related to other M&V guidelines such as:
 - ASHRAE, Guideline 14-2002 Measurement of Energy and Demand Savings: this document from the American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers, Inc. shares complementary details to the IPMVP protocol, giving technical details but with different terminology;
 - Greenhouse Gas Protocol for Project Accounting (2005), which was developed jointly between the World Resources Institute and the World Business Council for Sustainable Development. The IPVMP's Technical Committee was represented in the assessment committee of this document, which defines different ways to track GHG emissions reduction, among others.

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- The IPMVP protocol's application is different and unique for every project, and many users may use similar methods in the elaboration and application of their own M&V Plans. Anyways, the IPMVP protocol can be used by:
 - Contractors with EPC contracts and its building's users;
 - Contractors with EPC contracts and the clients of its industrial processes;
 - Energy users applying their own improvements that do want to track and justify their savings;
 - Managers of energy consumption centres, justifying appropriately the deviations/fluctuations on energy budget;
 - New building developers/designers;
 - New building developers/designers seeking for recognition over their project's sustainability commitment;
 - Existing building managers seeking for recognition over the environmental quality on their building's operation;
 - Designers and decision-makers of demand response and management in the public service;
 - Designers of water efficiency projects;
 - Designers of transaction programs for the GHG reduction.

The main purpose of the M&V in the context of EPC contracts in buildings is to present the economic performance of an improvement project on them. The M&V Plan becomes part of the contractual terms of the EPC contract, defining the measures and calculations to be performed in order to determine the payments between the ESCO and the client, or to demonstrate the achievement of a guaranteed level of efficiency. The M&V costs could be imitated considering each part's responsibilities in the EPC contract. If any parameters could be estimated with enough reliability for all parts involved in the contract, option A could be the cheapest option (further sections will explain the contents of each M&V option). In the other hand, if the contractor is committed to decrease consumed energy of a specific equipment, option B will be used if the contractor contemplates the equipment's metering, while the most suitable option would be option C whenever the metering system considered is performed globally, considering the metering of the whole consumption unit.

When the EPC contract is focused on the behaviour of the whole consumption unit, or whenever the evaluation of different ECMs' effect is difficult, option C should be picked. It should be bearded in mind that the M&V Plan includes all static reference factors, assigning the commitment on its monitoring during the reporting period. For new buildings, option D must be considered. Whenever there is a centralized metering system of multiple buildings and there has not been installed a particular metering system for each of them yet, it is also recommended to go for option D, so that the modifications are not delayed as the project waits for the mew sub-metering system to be deployed in order to collect the reference information for the M&V Plan.

The measurement can be done under the EPC's length or during a testing period just before the deployment of the improvement measures. The longer the reporting period is or the longer the limit measure is, the bigger attention must be focused on the chance of a change on the baseline state after the modifications. This chance requires an intensive register of the static factors of the M&V Plan, and a careful monitoring of the conditions after the ECM installations have been done.

Last but not least, the skills and technical basics of the M&V could be used in energy efficiency projects under the following overall objectives:

- I. **Increasing energy savings:** accurately determining energy savings offers the client, building owners and energy managers a useful amount of information so that they can evaluate their ECMs. That information helps them performing all necessary adjustments in the design of those ECMs or in their own facilities exploitation to improve savings, achieving an increased stability through time and minor changes/deviations on their energy savings.
- II. **Document financial transactions:** in some projects the energy savings through energy efficiency measures is the basis for the payments based on the performance and/or guarantee as stated in the EPC. The M&V Plan, when well defined and applied, can be the base for documenting all energy efficiency transparently and objectively.
- III. **Increasing energy efficiency projects' financing:** a well done M&V Plan increases transparency and credibility of the reporting when evaluation the results of energy related investments, increasing estimations' credibility that have been performed for future scenarios. This credibility increases investors' trust in energy efficiency projects, increasing funding opportunities and options.
- IV. **Enhancing the design, operation and maintenance of a consumption unit:** the preparation of a good M&V Plan encourages an exhaustive design process at the draft stage of the project, including all costs of M&V in the budget, and helps managers in finding out and solving problems related to operation and maintenance of their facilities. That way, the management of the clients' facilities can be improved, as well as enhancing future project designs.
- V. **Management of the energy budget line:** even if the energy savings concept is not raised, the M&V techniques allow managers to evaluate and control their energy usage so that they can justify any deviations over expected budget, as those M&V techniques and methods are used to adjust the operational conditions of the consumption units to establish correct budgets and minimize its deviations.
- VI. **Increase the value of GHG reduction credits:** the justification of GHG reductions implies an added value to energy efficiency projects. A M&V Plan to determine savings enhances the reporting on GHG reduction compared to other reports not including these kind of Plans.
- VII. **Support on evaluation of local/regional energy programmes:** programmes performed by public institutions or TSOs/DSOs might use M&V techniques to

evaluate savings on a specific consumption point. When using statistic methods and other simplifications, the savings determined by the M&V Plan can help in savings' forecasting even in some points that are not part of the controlled sample, so that an overall program's efficiency evaluation can be performed.

- VIII. **Increasing awareness on energy efficiency and renewable energy:** whenever the credibility of an energy management project is proven, the M&V increases public acceptance, which leads to a funding increase in energy efficiency programmes or in GHG emission credits that they would surely provide. While increasing energy savings, a well-designed M&V can contribute in the global benefit awareness of the EMCs as a community health improvement, reducing environmental degradation and creating new jobs.

9.2. Principles of Measure and Verification

The fundamentals or principles of a good M&V are the following:

- **Complete:** energy savings register has to consider all implications of a project, so M&V process must use techniques to quantify the significant effects of it while being able to approximate or estimate the rest.
- **Conservative:** when evaluating uncertain data, the procedures of M&V must be designed to evaluate savings in a conservative way.
- **Consistent:** the reporting on an energy project's effectiveness has to be coherent with different types of energy efficiency projects, different energy professionals, different time periods, etc.
- **Precise:** M&V reporting must be as precise/accurate as the budget allows to. The cost of M&V Plan is usually way lower than the economic savings. The M&V expenses must be coherent with the financing implications of registering an excess or lack of the reporting quality.
- **Relevant:** all M&V activities and information must measure all implied parameters' behaviour (less critic/foreseeable ones can be estimated).
- **Transparent:** all M&V activities must be presented and reported consistently and in a clear way. The document that must be delivered to the client has a common but flexible framework, so that basic procedures and the four options (A, B, C or D) considered do finally meet in a transparent and coherent report justifying all elements and contents of the M&V Plan.

9.3. Framework, design and options of the IPMVP Protocol

Energy, water or demand savings cannot be measured directly as savings represent the absence of energy or water demand or consumption. Therefore, savings are determined by comparing the demand or consumption measured before and after the application of a programme, performing logical adjustments due to changes in the installation working conditions.

Figure 30 Example of energy history from a consumption unit (Source: [24])

As also stated in the IPMVP of 2012, “Operational Verification should be performed as part of any project M&V program. It serves as a low-cost initial step for realizing savings potential and should precede savings verification activities. A range of operational verification methods can be applied. (...) Operational verification activities are accomplished through comprehensive commissioning of affected systems supplemented by more data-driven activities (e.g. data trending and review). The M&V Plan should note the operational verification approach in addition to the savings verification method. Operational verification should be completed prior to implementing M&V savings verification activities. This ensures the savings from ECMs, energy-efficient controls and operation improvements are fully realized” [24].

As an example of how savings are determined, Figure 30 shows an energy history consumption from an industrial boiler before and after introducing an ECM so that the expelled gases are recovered. The moment the ECM is applied, the plant's production is increased. In order to efficiently document the impact of an ECM, the effect on energy must be isolated from the effect on production's increase. The "baseline energy reference" was studied in order to determine the relationship between energy consumed and energy produced. After applying an ECM, that relationship served to estimate how much energy would have been consumed monthly if that ECM was not applied ("adjusted energy to baseline reference"). The "savings" or "avoided consumption" is the difference between "adjusted energy to baseline reference" and the energy that is truly consumed during the "reporting period". Without adjusting the production changes, the difference between the "baseline energy reference" and the "energy from reporting period" would have been way lower, thus underestimating the real effects of energy recovering at the boiler. It is therefore necessary to differentiate between energy effects of a savings programme from other simultaneous effects that impact other consuming systems [24]. The comparison between before and after should rely on a consistent basis following the equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Savings} = & (\text{Consumption or demand from baseline period} \\ & - \text{Consumption or demand from Reporting-Period}) \\ & \pm \text{Adjustments} \end{aligned}$$

The word "adjustments" refers or is commonly used to reintroduce the consumption or demand of the baseline period and the reporting period under common circumstances or conditions between both periods. That word "adjustments" distinguishes between reporting real savings or a simple cost comparison or consumption before and after the application of an ECM. Simple comparisons of service costs without any adjustment only inform about changes on the consumption, but do not offer any information about the effectiveness of the project. In order to correctly report savings, adjustments must take into account the differences between the "baseline period" and the "reporting period".

Additionally, savings verification and reporting must take into account:

- **Measurement boundary:** savings may be determined for an entire facility or for a part of it, depending upon the purposes of the reporting.
- **Measurement period selection:** the period of time to be used as "baseline period" or as "reporting period" should be carefully selected.
- **Basis for adjustments:** those should be done according to identifiable physical facts about the energy governing characteristics with the measurement boundary. For so, adjustments can be:
 - *"Routine Adjustments – for any energy-governing factors, expected to change routinely during the reporting period, such as weather or production volume. A variety of techniques can be used to define the adjustment methodology. Techniques may be as simple as a constant value (no adjustment) or as complex as a several multiple parameter non-*

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linear equations each correlating energy with one or more independent variables. Valid mathematical techniques must be used to derive the adjustment method for each M&V Plan.

- *Non-Routine Adjustments – for those energy-governing factors which are not usually expected to change, such as: the facility size, the design and operation of installed equipment, the number of weekly production shifts, or the type of occupants. These static factors must be monitored for change throughout the reporting period.*

As also stated in the IPMVP of 2012, the M&V Design and Reporting process should involve the following steps:

1. *"Consider the needs of the user of the planned M&V report(s). If the user is focused on overall cost control, Whole-Facility methods may be most suited. If user focus is on particular ECMs, Retrofit Isolation techniques may be most suited.*
2. *While developing the ECM(s), select the IPMVP Option that best suits the ECM(s), the needs for accuracy and the budget for M&V. Decide whether adjustment of all energy quantities will be made to the reporting period conditions or to some other set of conditions. Decide the duration of the baseline period and the reporting period (These fundamental decisions may be written into the terms of an energy-performance contract.).*
3. *Gather relevant energy and operating data from the baseline period and record them in a way that can be accessed in the future.*
4. *Prepare an M&V Plan containing the results of steps 1 through 3 above. It should define the subsequent steps 5 through 9.*
5. *As part of the final ECM design and installation, also design, install, calibrate and commission any special measurement equipment that is needed under the M&V Plan.*
6. *After the ECM is installed, ensure it has the potential to perform and achieve savings by conducting operational verification. This may include inspecting the installed equipment and revising operating procedures as needed to conform to the design intent of the ECM. This requirement may be fulfilled by a formal "commissioning" process as part of the project*
7. *Gather energy and operating data from the reporting period, as defined in the M&V Plan.*
8. *Compute savings in energy and monetary units in accordance with the M&V Plan.*
9. *Report savings in accordance with the M&V Plan. "*

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Moving on, the energy quantities that may be considered for the savings' equation can be measured through different techniques:

- "Utility or fuel supplier invoices, or reading utility meters and making the same adjustments to the readings that the utility makes.
- Special meters isolating an ECM or portion of a facility from the rest of the facility. Measurements may be periodic for short intervals, or continuous throughout the baseline or reporting periods.
- Separate measurements of parameters used in computing energy use. For example, equipment operating parameters of electrical load and operating hours can be measured separately and multiplied together to compute the equipment's energy use.
- Measurement of proven proxies for energy use. For example, if the energy use of a motor has been correlated to the output signal from the variable speed drive controlling the motor, the output signal could be a proven proxy for motor energy.
- Computer simulation that is calibrated to some actual performance data for the system or facility being modelled. One example of computer simulation is DOE-2 analysis for buildings (Option D only)" [24].

IPMVP provides four Options for determining savings (A, B, C and D). The choice among the Options involves many considerations including the location of the measurement boundary. If it is decided to determine savings at the facility level, Option C or D may be favoured. However, if only the performance of the ECM itself is of concern, a retrofit-isolation technique may be more suitable (Option A, B or D).

IPMVP Option	How Savings Are Calculated	Typical Applications
<p>A. Retrofit Isolation: Key Parameter Measurement</p> <p>Savings are determined by field measurement of the key performance parameter(s) which define the <i>energy</i> use of the <i>ECM's</i> affected system(s) and/or the success of the project.</p> <p>Measurement frequency ranges from short-term to continuous, depending on the expected variations in the measured parameter, and the length of the <i>reporting period</i>.</p> <p>Parameters not selected for field measurement are <i>estimated</i>. <i>Estimates</i> can be based on historical data, manufacturer's specifications, or engineering judgment. Documentation of the source or justification of the <i>estimated</i> parameter is required. The plausible <i>savings</i> error arising from <i>estimation</i> rather than measurement is evaluated.</p>	<p>Engineering calculation of <i>baseline</i> and <i>reporting period</i> energy from:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ short-term or continuous measurements of key operating parameter(s); and ○ <i>estimated</i> values. <p><i>Routine</i> and <i>non-routine</i> adjustments as required.</p>	<p>A lighting retrofit where power draw is the key performance parameter that is measured periodically. Estimate operating hours of the lights based on <i>facility</i> schedules and occupant behavior.</p>

IPMVP Option	How Savings Are Calculated	Typical Applications
<p>B. Retrofit Isolation: All Parameter Measurement</p> <p><i>Savings</i> are determined by field measurement of the <i>energy</i> use of the <i>ECM</i>-affected system.</p> <p>Measurement frequency ranges from short-term to continuous, depending on the expected variations in the <i>savings</i> and the length of the <i>reporting period</i>.</p>	<p>Short-term or continuous measurements of <i>baseline</i> and <i>reporting-period energy</i>, and/or engineering computations using measurements of proxies of <i>energy</i> use.</p> <p>Routine and non-routine adjustments as required.</p>	<p>Application of a variable-speed drive and controls to a motor to adjust pump flow. Measure electric power with a kW meter installed on the electrical supply to the motor, which reads the power every minute. In the <i>baseline period</i> this meter is in place for a week to verify <i>constant</i> loading. The meter is in place throughout the <i>reporting period</i> to track variations in power use.</p>
<p>C. Whole Facility</p> <p><i>Savings</i> are determined by measuring energy use at the whole <i>facility</i> or sub-<i>facility</i> level.</p> <p>Continuous measurements of the entire <i>facility's energy</i> use are taken throughout the <i>reporting period</i>.</p>	<p>Analysis of whole <i>facility baseline</i> and <i>reporting period</i> (utility) meter data.</p> <p><i>Routine adjustments</i> as required, using techniques such as simple comparison or regression analysis.</p> <p><i>Non-routine adjustments</i> as required.</p>	<p>Multifaceted energy management program affecting many systems in a <i>facility</i>. Measure energy use with the gas and electric utility meters for a twelve month <i>baseline period</i> and throughout the <i>reporting period</i>.</p>
<p>D. Calibrated Simulation</p> <p><i>Savings</i> are determined through simulation of the <i>energy</i> use of the whole <i>facility</i>, or of a sub-<i>facility</i>.</p> <p>Simulation routines are demonstrated to adequately model actual <i>energy</i> performance measured in the <i>facility</i>.</p> <p>This Option usually requires considerable skill in calibrated simulation.</p>	<p>Energy use simulation, calibrated with hourly or monthly utility billing data. (Energy end use metering may be used to help refine input data.)</p>	<p>Multifaceted energy management program affecting many systems in a <i>facility</i> but where no meter existed in the <i>baseline period</i>.</p> <p>Energy use measurements, after installation of gas and electric meters, are used to calibrate a simulation.</p> <p><i>Baseline energy</i> use, determined using the calibrated simulation, is compared to a simulation of <i>reporting period energy</i> use.</p>

Figure 31 Overview of IPMVP Options (Source: [24])

The selection of an IMPVP Option is a decision that is made by the designer of the M&V program for each project, based on the full set of project conditions, analysis, budgets and professional judgment. The next page's figure illustrates the common logic that is used in order to perform the most suitable Option selection.

Figure 32 Simplified selection process of IPMVP Options (Source: [24])

Furthermore, the Savings Verification process outlines different basis for adjustment or what type of savings are being considered for the project. In that case, and as

stated in the IPMVP of 2012, two different types of savings can be determined throughout the project:

- 1. Reporting-Period Basis or Avoided Energy Use:** when savings are reported under the conditions of the reporting period, avoided energy use quantifies those savings in the reporting period to what energy use would have been without applying the ECMs. These kind of savings can be restated as:

Avoided Energy Use (or Savings)

$$\begin{aligned} &= (\text{Baseline Energy} \\ &\pm \text{Routine Adjustments to Reporting-Period conditions} \\ &\pm \text{Non-Routine Adjustments to Reporting-Period conditions}) \\ &- \text{Reporting-Period Energy} \end{aligned}$$

“Avoided Energy Use” style of savings is dependent upon the reporting period’s operating conditions. Even though savings can be adjusted through conditions such as weather, they depend upon the actual weather so they cannot be directly compared with savings predicted under baseline conditions.

- 2. Fixed Conditions Basis or Normalized savings:** when savings are reported under conditions other than those of the reporting period, adjustment to a fixed set of conditions reports a style that could be called “normalized savings”, since energy from the reporting period and possibly of the baseline period are adjusted from their actual conditions to the common fixed set of conditions selected. These kind of savings can be restated as:

Normalized Savings

$$\begin{aligned} &= (\text{Baseline Energy} \\ &\pm \text{Routine Adjustments to fixed conditions} \\ &\pm \text{Non-Routine Adjustments to fixed conditions}) \\ &- (\text{Reporting-Period Energy} \\ &\pm \text{Routine Adjustments to fixed conditions} \\ &\pm \text{Non-Routine Adjustments to fixed conditions}) \end{aligned}$$

“Normalized savings” style of savings is unaffected by reporting-period conditions, since the fixed set of conditions are established once and cannot be changed. The main difference between “Avoided Energy Use” style of savings is that it can be directly compared with savings predicted under the same set of fixed conditions and can only be reported after a full cycle of reporting-period energy use, so that the mathematical correlation between reporting-period energy and operating conditions can be derived.

9.4. M&V Plan for CHESSE SETUP project

The first steps for the performance analysis consist in the collection of the necessary data to completely characterize the energy performance of the demonstration pilot site's facilities:

- Define the type of measurement and data requirements;
- Collect all relevant energy consumption and baseline period's operating equipment data and record them so that it can be accessible to the Consortium;
- Identify significant energy uses (separating by primary energy consumption and/or end final energy consumption).

In order to do so, the following sections will deepen on each step to fulfil the M&V Plan of the CHESSE SETUP project.

9.4.1. Definition of the measurement boundary

As stated in the beginning, savings may be determined for an entire facility or a portion of it depending upon the purposes of the reporting:

- If it is meant to help in the management of just an equipment affected by the expected savings of the project, the measurement boundary should focus on that equipment, therefore all significant energy requirements can be determined within the equipment boundary. This approach is used in the Retrofit Isolation Options (A&B).
- If it is mean to help in the management of the whole facility energy performance, the measurement boundary should focus on the energy supply of the overall facility, therefore it can assess performance and savings of the whole facilities involved. Therefore, the measurement boundary should in this case encompasses the whole facility and is performed in terms of Option C.
- If baseline or reporting period data are unreliable or unavailable, energy data from a calibrated simulation program can take the place of missing data, for either part or all of the facility. Therefore, the measurement boundary should be drawn accordingly and is performed under the calibrated simulation of Option D.

As the COVID-19 pandemic did not allow a complete data collection of a full cycle of reporting-period energy use, therefore whole-facility energy measurements have been metered but could not provide data of the full operating cycle from maximum energy use to minimum. For so, the CHESSE SETUP system deployment matches with the fundamentals of Option D, Calibrated Simulation, as it involves the use of computer simulation software to predict demonstration pilot sites facilities' energy for one or both terms of savings equation (see Page 62).

9.4.2. Definition of the measurement period selection

Once defined the CHESSE SETUP's measurement boundary, a first analysis must be carried out in order to establish the current performance of the system, thus defining, in the first place, the baseline period (which represents all operating modes of the facility). It should span a full operating cycle, representing all operating conditions of a daily basis energy system performance: in order to perform a deep business model appliance through a business plan analysis, a baseline period of one year has been selected as a whole year of baseline data is typically needed to define a full operating cycle. In that case, and as an example, if data is missing during the selected period of one month, comparable data from the same month in a different year should be used to ensure the baseline record does not under represent operating conditions of the missing month.

The length of the reporting period should at least encompass one normal operating cycle of the equipment/system/facility, so that savings effectiveness can be characterized and evaluated in all normal operating modes. The length of the reporting period should be linked to ECMs duration in terms of equipment's lifespan, degradation or performance and regardless the length of the reporting period, the metering equipment might be left in place so that further information and feedback of operating data is provided to the facility manager. The CHESSE SETUP's reporting period was expected to be of one year at least, but due to the COVID-19 Pandemic, the best scenario was able to collect data from 6 months. Therefore, information of energy demand regarding both baseline and reporting periods (especially for reporting period, as baseline period information is already provided via utility or fuel supply invoices, special meters isolating an ECM, separate measurements of parameters used in computing energy use or measurement of proven proxies for energy use or computer simulation that is calibrated to some actual performance data for the system or facility) has been done with whole-building-simulation programs, as stated in Deliverables 3.2, 3.7 and 5.1 among others.

9.4.3. Basis for adjustments

As seen on previous sections, the adjustments terms shown in savings equation (see Page 62) should be done under the correct understating of the CHESSE SETUP's system performance. The simulations performed by BCN and other partners include routine adjustments (for energy-governing factors that might change such as weather conditions, RES generation, etc.) and can be defined either in Deliverable 3.2 but also in Deliverable 4.1 (Monitoring system design) and Deliverable 4.2 (Management system design), which include external variables considered, data processing and storage, monitoring system's architecture for control and data acquisition and other external information (weather forecasting or electricity energy price) that will help in adjusting both energy and cost savings.

Non-routine adjustments such as energy-governing factors that are not expected to change are also considered for the savings adjustments, such as facility size (or space being heated or air conditioned), building envelope characteristics, amount, type or use of the facilities and users' equipment, indoor environmental standards or conditions, occupancy profile and/or schedule, etc. Therefore, the savings equation can be traduced as:

$$\text{Savings} = (\text{Baseline Energy} - \text{Reporting-Period Energy}) \\ \pm \text{Routine Adjustments} \pm \text{Non-Routine Adjustments}$$

9.4.4. Implementation of M&V Plan

When deploying Option D on the CHESSE SETUP system's deployment at each demonstration pilot site, a model must be developed considering all data collected through the baseline and reporting periods. The energy baseline from each demonstration pilot site's facilities, seen as previous energy infrastructure before the CHESSE SETUP system's deployment, must include, at least:

- Current installation elements/equipment;
- Current energy demand and consumption profile as a baseline/reference, with a proper breakdown according to either primary and final energy consumption;
- Current energy costs, referenced either to primary thermal energy consumption [$\text{€}/\text{kWh}_{\text{PCI}}$] and electricity consumption [$\text{€}/\text{kWh}_e$];
- Current O&M costs;
- Current economic indicators (IPC, VAT, etc.).
- Any other independent and fixed variables for the facilities performance simulations (seen previously as non-routine adjustments parameters).

As also stated in the IPMVP of 2012, regarding Option D's types of simulation programs: *"Whole-building-simulation programs usually use hourly calculation techniques. However, simplified HVAC system models may also be used if the building's heat losses, heat gains, internal loads, and HVAC systems are simple. Other types of special-purpose programs may be used to simulate energy use and operation of devices or industrial processes.*

Any software used must be well documented and well understood by the user. Due to the wide variety of available methods, it is prudent to receive acceptance by the owner or project authority of the proposed modelling program before commencing analysis".

Regarding Option D's calibration, *"Savings determined with Option D are based on one or more complex estimates of energy use. The accuracy of the savings depends on how well the simulation models actual equipment performance, and how well calibrated it is to metered energy performance.*

Calibration is achieved by verifying that the simulation model reasonably predicts the energy patterns of the facility by comparing model results to a set of calibration data.

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These calibration data include measured energy data, independent variables and static factor.

Calibration of building simulations is usually done with 12 monthly utility bills. These bills should be from a period of stable operation. In a new building, it may take a number of months before full occupancy and before the staff learns the best ways to operate the facility. The calibration data should be documented in the M&V Plan along with a description of its sources” [24].

Regarding Option D savings’ calculations, “Savings can be determined using calibrated simulation results representing the baseline energy and/or the reporting-period energy. For projects with a physical baseline, the two calibrated models include one with the ECMs and one without them. For projects with a hypothetical baseline, calibrated models may include the hypothetical baseline and the as-built (reporting period) conditions, but measured data will only be available for calibration under as-built conditions. In either case, both models and measured energy data must be under the same set of operating conditions” [24].

For the CHESSETYP project, the detail of the monitoring results can be found on Deliverable 5.4 report, stating that for each demonstration pilot site a report will be done sensitizing the data obtained from the monitoring results and the comparison with theoretical data coming from simulations performed on other Deliverables. As there are two different forms to estimate savings with Option D, the CHESSETUP project opted for the one given below:

*Savings =
Baseline energy from the calibrated model [hypothetical or without ECMS] –
Reporting-period energy from the calibrated model [with ECMS]*

As a resume, and in order to define a complete M&V Plan for the CHESSETUP project, the following steps must be fulfilled (that information might be split into different Deliverables over the project) as stated in the IPMVP of 2012:

- 1. "ECM Intent:** *a concise and detailed explanation of the ECM (seen as the technical CHESSETUP system deployment), its intended result and operational verification procedures to ensure and verify the effective and efficient deployment of the system.*
- 2. Selected IPMVP option and measurement boundary:** *specify the IPMVP option to determine savings and identify the measurement boundary of the savings determination.*
- 3. Baseline – Period, Energy and Conditions:** *a concise and detailed explanation of the facilities’ baseline conditions and energy data within the measurement boundary. This usually includes:*
 - 3.1. Identification of the baseline period*
 - 3.2. All baseline energy consumption and demand data*
 - 3.3. All independent variable data coinciding with energy data*
 - 3.4. All static factors coinciding with the energy data such as occupancy profile, density and periods; operating conditions for each baseline operating period and*

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season other than the independent variables; description of any baseline conditions that fall short of required conditions; size, type and insulation of any relevant building envelope elements; equipment inventory; equipment operating practices; significant equipment problems or outages during the baseline period, etc.)

4. **Reporting period:** identify the reporting period.
5. **Basis for adjustment:** declare the set of conditions to which all energy measurements will be adjusted.
6. **Analysis procedure:** specify the exact data analysis procedures, algorithms and assumptions to be used in each savings report.
7. **Energy prices:** specify all energy prices that will be used to value the savings and whether and how savings will be adjusted if prices changes in the future.
8. **Meter specifications:** specify the metering points and periods.
9. **Monitoring responsibilities:** assign responsibilities for the reporting and recording of all relevant energy data, independent variables and static factors within the measurement boundary during the reporting period.
10. **Expected accuracy:** evaluate the expected accuracy associated with the measurement, data capture, sampling and data analysis.
11. **Budget:** define the budget and resources required for the savings determination, both initial setup costs and ongoing costs throughout the reporting period.
12. **Report format:** specify how the results will be reported and documented.
13. **Quality assurance:** specify quality-assurance procedures that will be used for savings report and any interim steps in preparing the reports" [24].

Last but not least, those simulations have been performed under simulated and estimated data coming from different partners and other Deliverables of the CHESSE SETUP's project; therefore, VLC exposes that those business plan simulations may not correspond with the real system performance under a complete full operating cycle (at least one year), as the reporting period has not lasted a complete year.

10. ESCO business model applied for the case studies

Once we have defined the main contents of the proposed ESCO business model, we must choose the alternative that results in the most suitable, feasible and profitable exploitation scenario regarding each demo pilot site. In order to do so, the following information is required:

- Current and future installation elements/equipment;
- Current energy demand and consumption profile as a baseline/reference;
- Current energy costs, referenced either to primary thermal energy consumption [$\text{€}/\text{kWh}_{\text{PCI}}$] and electricity consumption [$\text{€}/\text{kWh}_e$];
- Estimated energy savings generated with the new equipment/solution:
 - Primary thermal energy consumption savings [kWh_{PCI}], as energy saved substituting fuel consumption by seasonal thermal energy storage and installing hybrid panels (heat production);
 - Primary electrical energy consumption savings [kWh_e], as energy saved by installing hybrid panels (electricity production);
- Estimated economical savings generated with the new equipment/solution:
 - Primary thermal energy economical savings [€_t], by multiplying primary thermal energy consumption savings [kWh_{PCI}] and current energy thermal energy costs [$\text{€}/\text{kWh}_t$];
 - Primary electrical energy economical savings [€_e], by multiplying primary electrical energy consumption savings [kWh_e] and current electricity energy costs [$\text{€}/\text{kWh}_e$];
- Periodical updated savings provided by the monitoring & control system deployed on each demo pilot site, to see if the deployed technology's performance corresponds with what was theoretically expected;
- Total investment costs;
- Total O&M costs;
- Current economic indicators (CPI, VAT, etc.).

Taking into consideration all previous information, it's feasible to generate a business plan simulation according to each of the demo pilot sites experience and feedback received from them during the construction, commissioning and exploitation phases of the project. The aim of the business plan simulation is to evaluate if the project's initially feasible and economical/financial viable; if it is, we'll be able to generate a standard exploitation, replication and scalable plan and do a market research so the project's solution is ready to be launched in the market.

As already seen in Deliverables 2.1 and 2.2, which mainly focused on a deep analysis on TES storage materials, systems and construction techniques, the CHESSE SETUP system proposal is mainly based on sensible heat storage (SHS): sensible heat can be seen as potential heating or cooling energy with regard to ambient temperature, stored in a solid, liquid or dual environment that consists in a combination of liquid and solid environments. Taking into account different temperature requirements for

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the heating systems from each building, as well as the thermal storage capacity of the storage technology applied, storage duration, location, thermal power source and efficiency, the business plan simulation will provide different values depending on the scenarios' parameters considered. As the CHESSE SETUP system mainly considers two storage systems (one seasonal thermal energy storage (STES) and buffer/daily energy storage), it's important to point out that depending on which SHS system we are considering, different operation modes, capacities and costs will be involved. The main variables defining CHESSE SETUP's SHS system are:

- Storage temperature [K];
- Average storage material density [kg/m^3];
- Average heat conductivity [$\text{W}/\text{m}\cdot\text{K}$];
- Average heat capacity [$\text{kJ}/\text{kg}\cdot\text{K}$];
- Volume-specific heat capacity [kWh/m^3];
- Efficiency [%];
- Media cost [$\text{€}/\text{kWh}$].

Veolia Serveis Catalunya, S.A.U., with all partners involved in this task, will analyse, evaluate and develop different business plans for the CHESSE SETUP system configuration adapted to each demonstration scenario, according to experiences and feedback coming for each of the three pilot sites during the construction, commissioning and exploitation phases of the project. This task seeks for a feasibility analysis of the TES system deployed to be adjusted in different values/forms and costs depending on each building's energy savings results coming from real-time monitored data.

The main new features involving the ESCO business model applied are mainly maintenance (P₂) and full warranty (P₃) services. As previously seen in Deliverable 2.2 on construction techniques, the annual service quote depends on the work being performed under each of those contracts circumstances. When referring to maintenance services (P₂), we can distinguish between different types of maintenance:

- **Preventive Maintenance** comprises all the systematic actuations needed to maintain the Chess-Setup system, the installation and the equipment optimal working conditions in order to prolong their lifespan and maintain their performance similar to the project performance.

As all the elements to maintain are clear and the preventive maintenance actuations are characterised by their periodicity, it is possible to systematise the process in order to identify previously the needs in term of hours, personnel and materials and programme all the preventive actuations to do.

The maintenance company should elaborate a Preventive Maintenance Planning that encompasses all the installations and equipment and with the following characteristics:

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- An annual preventive maintenance operations planning will be done for all the equipment required.
- The specific tasks to carry out for each installation should be detailed, with the expected execution time, the type of personnel assigned and the frequency.
- Preventive maintenance routines will be implemented and all the operations done will be registered, with the real time spent, the number and type of detected incidences and the solution taken in each case.
- The Preventive Maintenance Plan should be elaborated with a chart of actions that will include the necessary cycles to guarantee the functionality and preservation of the installations, civil works and others. These cycles will have the convenient recurrence, according to the installation possible needs, with minimum cost criteria. The maintenance sheets should have:
 - Name of the system
 - Specific element of the system
 - Description of the actions to be carried out and materials needed
 - Frequency of the action

The preventive maintenance chart will also distribute the planned actions during the 52 weeks of the year. To make a correct plan of the preventive maintenance operations is recommended that the control of the cycles and the realisation of the activities are made with informatics support, such as a Computerized Maintenance Management System (CMMS).

- **Legislative Maintenance** will not technically differ from Preventive Maintenance and will be carried out following predetermined cycles with a planning fixed by the different official organisms. The difference is that in the Preventive Maintenance the operations are fixed according to the professional experience and the suppliers recommendations whereas the Legislative Maintenance should be rigorously applied according to current legislations.

There are two types of technical reviews in the legislative maintenance:

- The obligatory inspections carried out by administration collaborating companies.
- The obligatory reviews carried out by the maintenance company.

The elements that require legislative maintenance usually are:

- Low voltage installation
- Chillers and heat pumps
- Protection and detection systems and fire alarms
- Boilers, boiler burners and fireplaces
- Pressure equipment
- Gas distribution systems and networks
- Other fuels distribution systems and networks, liquids or gases
- Grounding networks
- Water networks, DHW, DCW, heating and cooling
- Water distribution systems affected by Legionella Legislation
- Others that can be affected by current legislation

The maintenance company must have all the information and official books updated with the last legislative review so that can be checked by the Official Organisms, insurance companies, etc. The responsible of maintenance of the installation will keep all of this information.

- **Control Maintenance** includes all those operations of checking, verification, operation and adjustment, necessities for the installations to offer at all times the service provision without interruptions or incidents. This includes the commissioning and stops of the installations, according to the previous established criteria, the surveillance and the routes of inspection and function check.

As an essential part of the building control tasks, the maintenance company should execute all the actions needed in order to reduce the energy consumption (water, gas and electricity) according to a rational use, comfort and minimum cost.

The control routes are considered in this type of maintenance. The daily installation route is focused in ensure the continuity and good performance of the equipment and installations considered as critical.

The proposed route should be defined according to the operating conditions:

- The route will be based on the control points monitoring (installations and equipment) according to their proximity.
- Annotation of the total and partial water, gas and electricity meter readings. Computerized control of the data and analyse of deviations.
- Annotation of the working parameters of the equipment (system balancing, emergency batteries, transformers, chiller, etc.)

With the data obtained during the route the following actions will be done:

- Computerized analyse of the installation consumption tendencies. From the energy consumption of the different subsystem registered the evolution of the consumption will be analysed in accordance with

the climatology (temperature and humidity), seasonality (summer, winter), activity in the centre, etc.

Take actions to reduce the energy consumption to a minimum in water, gas and electricity installations, following rational use, comfort and minimum cost criteria and optimal tariffs selection. Once there will be enough knowledge of the installations, certain elements with a high consumption could be, in a controlled way, stopped in order to offer additional energy savings without affecting the system activity.

- **Corrective Maintenance** is all of the non-systematic technical works which objective is to solve the malfunctions and deficiencies that might occur in the system or equipment.

Depending on the gravity there will be a different degree of response in order that the solution arrives more or less rapidly. The breakdowns are usually classified as follow:

- Urgent resolution:
 - Those breakdowns that may represent a danger to public or serious installation damage require an immediate response. Also the ones that force to stop the activity or suppose a serious inconvenient for its development.
 - In order to cover this type of breakdowns at any time a good solution is to dispose of a 24h assistance service.
- Non-urgent resolution
 - All the breakdowns not identified as urgent. They can be solved during a programmed maintenance visit.

A detailed maintenance plan adapted to CHESS SETUP reference system can be found in Appendix I, the same way it can be found inside D2.2 Report on construction techniques, section 6.3 Chess-Setup maintenance plans.

When referring to full warranty service (P3), as this task is very complex and involves all kind of variables, each ESCO has its own calculation/prevision tools in order to adjust as much as possible the total cost of repairing all equipment failures that may occur during the contract's duration. As P3 services includes repairing tasks as well as all equipment substitution at the end of its lifespan, ESCOs must ensure the correct performance and maintenance of the installation in order to avoid possible failures and having to replace non-considered material or equipment. Therefore, a fixed amount is arranged between ESCO and client taking into account expected repairing costs, considering ESCOs assume all technical risks and substitution works and costs as long as the contract is in force.

10.1. Lavola's headquarters – Manlleu (Spain)

As a brief reminder, the Ecobuilding (Lavola's headquarters) pilot site has been finally designed not to integrate any TES; its technical solution is based on integrating PV panels in combination with an air-source heat pump (ASHP). Given the reduced size of the TES that could be installed in previous CHESSETUP system configuration's analysis, the final configuration is taking advantage of the thermal inertia of the building's slab upper layer of mortar where the radiant heating floor is already installed as a small form of thermal storage system. Therefore, as stated in Deliverable 3.7, the thermal energy stored in the slab is up to a 70% higher than what could be accomplished with the hot water TES that was initially planned.

10.1.1. Total cost of operation

The first thing in order to define the total cost of operation of the technological configuration deployment is the investment costs of all equipment involved. The main budget items which can be resumed as follows:

Budget line	Cost
Photovoltaic installation	32,665.58 €
Galvanized layer sheet	9,756.92 €
Perimeter railing system and concrete slab for the air-sourced heat pump	4,140.43 €
Air-Sourced Heat Pump	29,350.46 €
Monitoring and control system	32,579.74 €
Electric wiring	3,182.90 €
Metallic structure legalisation project	1,750.00 €
TOTAL MATERIAL EXECUTION BUDGET (MEB)	113,426.03 €
General costs (13% MEB)	14,745.38 €
Industrial profit (6% MEB)	6,805.56 €
TOTAL IMPLEMENTATION BUDGET (IB)	134,976.98 €
VALUE-ADDED TAX (21% IB)	28,345.16 €
TOTAL CHESSETUP IMPLEMENTATION BUDGET (VAT INCLUDED)	163,322.14 €

Table 2 Main budget items CHESSETUP's system deployment at Lavola's headquarters (Source: LVL)

For the business plan simulation, this report will be working (as it's usual) with the material execution budget as it only involves the requested material to be installed and the pilot site that can be attributed to the CHESSETUP system deployment. In that case, a total MEB of **113,426.03 €** is considered for Ecobuilding's pilot site.

The following steps include the calculation of both maintenance (P2) and full warranty (P3) costs, including all services detailed in sections 6.2 and 6.3 of the current report, as well as what has been detailed previously in section 10.

In order to calculate the P2 cost, the main variables affecting its calculation are:

- Personnel costs, including operational staff, operator/workman, etc.;
- Tools, clothing and other material costs including uniforms, protective and safety equipment, etc.;
- Vehicle and transportation costs;
- Communication and management systems (PDA, monitoring devices, etc.);
- Subcontracting costs for specific works;
- Additional specific contracting works not included before (such as legionella prevention tasks, sanitation, etc.).

Taking into account all personnel hours and concepts seen before, the total annual cost of maintaining the CHESSE SETUP system at Lavola's headquarters is approximately **1,813.00€/year (does not change with the contract's duration)**.

In order to calculate the P3 cost, the main variables affecting its calculation are:

- Personnel manpower cost;
- Reference year for amortisation;
- Algorithms of failure calculation of equipment involved;
- Range of equipment involved;
- Amount of equipment involved;
- Lifespan of equipment involved.

Taking into account all equipment and concepts seen before, the total annual cost of a full warranty service for the CHESSE SETUP system at Lavola's headquarters ranges between **701.00€/year and 991.00 €/year (5-year to 10-year EPC)**.

10.1.2. Energy savings

Once seen the total improvement works/installation renewal costs (P4), as well as maintenance (P2) and full warranty (P3) costs, it's time to check the main results of the CHESSE SETUP system's energy retrofit. This time it will not be correct to strictly define it as an energy management (P1) service and associated cost, as this term refers to all energy management needed for the correct operation of the installation contract, such as the energy management supply (fuel and electricity), the quality, quantity, control operation and supply guarantees. Whenever this is part of the contract, the ESCO is responsible to provide the client a set of agreed services (such as

heating, lighting, etc.), even taking responsibility of the installation's energy purchase in order to ensure the client an immediate save compared with the actual energetic cost. As this is not a P1 service, this report will only focus on the energy savings data coming from the monitoring system compared to the baseline energy demand and consumption from the building. That information is shown at the following table, which summarizes the main building's energy demand and consumption:

	Heating & Cooling		Electricity		
	Heating demand (kWh _{PCI})	Cooling demand (kWh _{PCI})	Natural Gas consumption (kWh _{PCI})	Chiller consumption (kWh _e)	Total electricity consumption (kWh _e)
January	16,870.00	948.00	16,066.67	400.00	7,052.00
February	11,021.00	592.50	10,469.19	250.00	6,493.00
March	7,876.00	1,896.00	7,500.95	800.00	6,258.00
April	2,108.00	2,133.00	2,007.62	900.00	5,741.00
May	0.00	4,740.00	0.00	2,000.00	5,479.00
June	0.00	5,925.00	0.00	2,500.00	5,141.00
July	0.00	7,110.00	0.00	3,000.00	7,415.00
August	0.00	5,451.00	0.00	2,300.00	6,184.00
September	0.00	4,503.00	0.00	1,900.00	6,369.00
October	1,599.00	2,844.00	1,522.86	1,200.00	5,196.00
November	10,345.00	90.06	9,852.38	38.00	5,256.00
December	16,682.00	2,038.20	15,887.62	860.00	5,410.00
TOTAL	66,501.00	38,270.76	63,334.29	16,148.00	71,994.00

Table 3 Energy demand and consumption of Lavola's headquarters (Source: Deliverable 3.7 and Deliverable 5.1)

The contents of Table 3 come from previous simulations being performed by other partners in the Consortium, which have been included in Deliverable 3.7: that information corresponds to both electrical and thermal energy demand from Lavola's headquarters (Ecobuilding) regarding weather and occupancy profiles from 2016. Later on will we find that overall natural gas consumption has increased, as showed by real invoices of the building's energy consumption over the years 2019 and 2020.

10.1.2.1. Electricity savings

As stated previously, and due to the COVID-19 pandemic situation we are currently suffering, the CHESSE SETUP's system performance is not reliable from March 2020 and so on, as Spain's population had experienced a confinement/isolation situation which was decreed by the Government. For that, BCN has performed a deep analysis on relevant data coming from the monitoring & control system deployed by WAT, which provided relevant information from September 2019 until February 2020: for so, the rest of the year's system performance has been forecasted taking into account the geographical demonstration site location, solar irradiation, energy bills and expected system performance under standard climatological conditions of each season.

As a result, a total amount of **11,058.36 kWh_e** as primary electricity energy savings has been estimated to come from PV panels' energy production. That being said, the overall electricity consumption is increased as the new ASHP installed consumes about 33,423.67 kWh_e, increasing overall electricity consumption to 84,917.20 kWh_e (the chiller is removed, so another approximately 16,148.00 kWh_e are already saved). Therefore, the new electricity consumption from the grid when deploying the CHESSE SETUP's system proposal at Lavola's headquarters is 73,561.95 kWh_e.

CHESSE SETUP's system electricity performance					
	PV Electricity gen. (kWh _e)	Actual El. Eq. Cons. (kWh _e)	Actual ASHP cons. (kWh _e)	Electricity consumption from GRID (kWh _e)	Total El. Cons. (kWh _e)
January	412.94	5,485.90	7,361.04	12,434.00	12,846.94
February	684.8	4,590.59	4,067.21	7,973.00	8,657.80
March	805.46	3,969.69	3,540.77	6,705.00	7,510.46
April	976.37	2,889.28	1,328.09	3,241.00	4,217.37
May	1,093.37	3,150.35	613.68	2,568.62	3,661.99
June	1,374.78	3,286.63	1,304.87	3,104.27	4,479.05
July	1,471.51	3,388.68	2,030.29	3,865.06	5,336.57
August	1,512.79	5,658.41	821.38	4,967.00	6,479.79
September	1193.7	5,105.70	1,012.00	4,924.00	6,117.70
October	767.5	4,347.67	1,014.83	4,595.00	5,362.50
November	432.82	5,147.68	4,407.14	9,122.00	9,554.82
December	332.32	4,472.96	5,922.36	10,063.00	10,395.32
TOTAL	11,058.36	51,493.53	33,423.67	73,561.95	84,917.20

Table 4 CHESSE SETUP's electrical energy generation and consumption at Lavola's headquarters
(Source: BCN Ecologia)

10.1.2.2. Thermal savings

The main feature of this reference case is the thermal savings that can be provided through the maximal exploitation of the ASHP while matching, as much as possible, its consumption curve with PV generation curve. The system provides a total amount of **87,113.99 kWh_{PCI}**.

Month	CHESS SETUP						Total Building		Lavola's Baseline						Total Building		
	Heating [kWh]	Cooling [kWh]	Total Thermal [kWh]	COP	Energy Cost [€]	CO ₂ [kg]	Energy Cost [€]	CO ₂ [kg]	Boiler savings [kWh _{PCI}]	Energy cost [€]	Chiller savings [kWh _e]	Energy cost [€]	Total Energy [kWh]	Energy Cost [€]	CO ₂ [kg]	Energy Cost [€]	CO ₂ [kg]
Aug.	0.00	3,961.65	3,961.65	4.82	116.83	96.65	839.32	694.29	0.00	0.00	1,672.99	282.70	1,672.99	282.70	233.85	1,238.85	1,024.79
Sept. 1-19	0.00	3,063.89	3,063.89	5.26	33.54	27.74	538.37	445.34	0.00	0.00	1,293.87	218.64	1,293.87	218.64	180.86	790.54	653.94
Sept. 20-30	0.00	1,317.70	1,317.70	3.07	2.83	2.34	293.69	242.94	0.00	0.00	556.46	94.03	556.46	94.03	77.78	384.88	318.38
Oct. 1-14	0.00	1,389.57	1,389.57	3.14	1.07	0.88	336.27	278.16	0.00	0.00	586.81	99.16	586.81	99.16	82.02	434.36	359.30
Oct. 15-31	3,322.41	0.00	3,322.41	5.80	40.72	33.69	440.19	364.13	3,927.20	250.84	0.00	0.00	3,927.20	250.84	1,033.30	650.31	1,363.74
Nov.	10,945.94	0.00	10,945.94	2.48	671.58	555.53	1,541.42	1,275.08	12,938.47	826.42	0.00	0.00	12,938.47	826.42	3,404.28	1,696.27	4,123.83
Dec.	12,096.67	0.00	12,096.67	2.04	944.60	781.38	1,700.43	1,406.61	14,298.66	913.30	0.00	0.00	14,298.66	913.30	3,762.17	1,669.14	4,387.40
Jan.	14,326.19	0.00	14,326.19	1.95	1,174.08	971.21	2,101.08	1,738.03	16,934.03	1,081.63	0.00	0.00	16,934.03	1,081.63	4,455.57	2,008.63	5,222.39
Feb.	9,579.46	0.00	9,579.46	2.36	571.56	472.79	1,347.27	1,114.47	11,323.24	723.25	0.00	0.00	11,323.24	723.25	2,979.29	1,498.96	3,620.97
Mar.	9,291.78	0.00	9,291.78	2.62	462.21	382.34	1,133.00	937.23	10,983.19	701.53	0.00	0.00	10,983.19	701.53	2,889.82	1,372.33	3,444.71
Apr.	5,695.77	0.00	5,695.77	4.29	59.43	49.16	547.66	453.03	6,732.59	430.03	0.00	0.00	6,732.59	430.03	1,771.43	918.26	2,175.30
May	1,884.00	0.00	1,884.00	3.07	81.06	67.05	434.04	359.04	2,226.96	142.24	0.00	0.00	2,226.96	142.24	585.94	657.34	1,012.04
Jun.	0.00	4,005.96	4,005.96	3.07	11.81	9.77	524.56	433.92	0.00	0.00	1,691.71	285.86	1,691.71	285.86	236.47	822.23	680.15
Jul.	0.00	6,233.00	6,233.00	3.07	94.42	78.11	653.11	540.26	0.00	0.00	2,632.18	444.78	2,632.18	444.78	367.93	1,003.47	830.08
TOTAL	67,142.23	19,971.76	87,113.99	2.61	3,779.26	3,126.23	12,430.41	10,282.52	79,364.34	5,069.25	8,434.02	1,425.17	87,798.36	6,494.42	22,060.71	15,145.57	29,217.00

Table 5 Comparative table between CHESS SETUP thermal energy generation and consumption and baseline consumption of Lavola's headquarters (Source: BCN Ecologia)

The red rows come from an estimation performed by BCN taking into account the most recent energy bills and monitoring & control system's data before all the current sanity emergency situation arose. As seen previously, either heating and cooling demand is now satisfied via new CHESSE SETUP's system deployment (PV alongside with ASHP), thus providing a total amount of 87,113.99 kWh_{PCI} as primary thermal energy savings. That being said, the fact is that it can't all be seen as savings from the initial scenario, as there was an existing chiller which took care of all cooling demand; therefore, we will only consider a total amount of **79,364.34 kWh_{PCI}** as primary thermal energy savings, as it is the amount of natural gas that has been estimated to be saved as thermal energy of Ecobuilding's heating demand (previously satisfied with natural gas combustion at the existing boiler).

10.1.3. Business plan simulation

After all variables have been defined, it is the time to perform a business plan simulation under many different perspectives, in order to analyse the feasibility and profitability of the CHESSE SETUP system deployment at Sant Cugat's Sports Centre. The main variables involved in the simulation are:

- **Total investment cost (previously referred as MEB):** 113,426.03 €;
- **Annual maintenance (P2) and full warranty (P3) costs:** 1,813.00€/year and between 701.00 €/year and 991.00 €/year (5-year to 10-year EPC).
- **Duration of the contract:** 5 years/ 8 years/ 10 years;
- **Amortisation:** the same as the duration of the contract;
- **Interest rate for the total investment cost:** 5%;
- **Annual CPI increase:** 1.45%
- **Profit margin of the ESCO on total investment cost:** 10% (therefore, the installation is sold to the client for 124,768.63 €);
- **Client's payment schedule:** up to 2 months' maximum;

As the contract's duration is not fixed and depends on the client's needs and the ESCO's perspective on the operation and maintenance works of the technical configuration of the system, a simulation of an 8-year contract and a 10-year contract has been also conducted as they are also common contract durations on these kind of projects.

Last but not least, those simulations have been performed under simulated and estimated data coming from different partners and other Deliverables of the CHESSE SETUP's project; therefore, VLC exposes that those business plan simulations may not correspond with the real system performance under a complete full operating cycle (at least one year), as the reporting period has not lasted a complete year.

*D6.1 Business models analysis
for the case studies*

Business plan simulation (5-year contract)		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Final sales (P2+P3+P4)		31,332	31,369	31,406	31,444	31,484	
Total costs (P2+P3+Structure cost)		4,274	4,311	4,349	4,387	4,427	
EBITDA		27,058	27,058	27,057	27,057	27,056	
	Amortisation	-22,685	-22,685	-22,685	-22,685	-22,685	
EBIT		27,058	27,058	27,057	27,057	27,056	
EBT (No financial costs considered)		4,373	4,373	4,372	4,372	4,371	
	Tax base	4,373	4,373	8,745	13,116	17,487	
Corporate income tax (25%)		1,093	1,093	1,093	1,093	1,093	
Net benefits		3,280	3,279	3,279	3,279	3,278	
Client payments		26,182	31,363	31,400	31,438	31,477	5,175
Supplier payments		3,923	4,308	4,345	4,384	4,424	364
ETE		22,259	27,055	27,054	27,054	27,053	4,811
Cash Flow		-92,260	25,962	25,961	25,961	25,960	4,811
Project TIR	6.59%						
Project NPV	3,566.15 €						

Table 6 Business plan simulation at Lavola's Ecobuilding for a 5-year EPC under abovementioned conditions

*D6.1 Business models analysis
for the case studies*

Business plan simulation (8-year contract)		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028
Final sales (P2+P3+P4)		22,004	22,043	22,083	22,124	22,166	22,206	22,250	22,294	
Total costs (P2+P3+Structure cost)		3,891	3,931	3,971	4,013	4,056	4,096	4,140	4,185	
EBITDA		18,113	18,112	18,112	18,111	18,111	18,110	18,110	18,109	
	Amortisation	-14,178	-14,178	-14,178	-14,178	-14,178	-14,178	-14,178	-14,178	
EBIT		3,934	3,934	3,934	3,933	3,932	3,932	3,931	3,931	
EBT (No financial costs considered)		3,934	3,934	3,934	3,933	3,932	3,932	3,931	3,931	
	Tax base	3,934	3,934	7,868	11,801	15,733	19,665	23,596	27,527	
Corporate income tax (25%)		984	984	983	983	983	983	983	983	
Net benefits		2,951	2,951	2,950	2,950	2,949	2,949	2,949	2,948	
Client payments		18,387	22,036	22,076	22,117	22,159	22,200	22,243	22,287	3,665
Supplier payments		3,571	3,927	3,968	4,009	4,052	4,093	4,137	4,181	344
ETE		14,815	18,109	18,109	18,108	18,107	18,107	18,106	18,106	3,321
Cash Flow		-99,594	17,126	17,125	17,125	17,124	17,124	17,123	17,123	3,321
Project TIR		5.47%								
Project NPV		5,613.38 €								

Table 7 Business plan simulation at Lavola's Ecobuilding for an 8-year EPC under abovementioned conditions

D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies

Business plan simulation (10-year contract)		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
Final sales (P2+P3+P4)		18,962	19,003	19,044	19,087	19,131	19,173	19,218	19,264	19,310	19,358	
Total costs (P2+P3+Structure cost)		3,808	3,849	3,891	3,935	3,979	4,021	4,067	4,113	4,161	4,209	
EBITDA		15,153	15,153	15,152	15,152	15,151	15,151	15,150	15,150	15,149	15,153	
	Amortisation	-11,343	-11,343	-11,343	-11,343	-11,343	-11,343	-11,343	-11,343	-11,343	-11,343	
EBIT		3,811	3,812	3,811	3,811	3,810	3,809	3,809	3,808	3,808	3,807	
EBT (No financial costs considered)		3,811	3,812	3,811	3,811	3,810	3,809	3,809	3,808	3,808	3,807	
	Tax base	3,811	3,812	7,623	11,433	15,243	19,053	22,862	26,670	30,478	34,285	
Corporate income tax (25%)		953	953	953	953	953	952	952	952	952	952	
Net benefits		2,858	2,859	2,858	2,858	2,858	2,857	2,857	2,856	2,856	2,855	
Client payments		15,845	18,996	19,037	19,080	19,124	19,166	19,210	19,256	19,303	19,350	3,182
Supplier payments		3,495	3,846	3,888	3,931	3,975	4,018	4,063	4,110	4,157	4,205	346
ETE		12,350	15,150	15,150	15,149	15,148	15,148	15,147	15,146	15,146	15,145	2,836
Cash Flow		-102,029	14,197	14,197	14,196	14,196	14,196	14,195	14,194	14,194	14,193	2,836
Project TIR		5.13%										
Project NPV		6,694.30 €										

Table 8 Business plan simulation at Lavola's Ecobuilding for a 10-year EPC under abovementioned conditions

ANUAL COMPARISON ECOBUILDING (LAVOLA'S HEADQUARTERS)

	Actual status (Baseline)	EPC Proposal 5 years		EPC Proposal 8 years		EPC Proposal 10 years	
		Year 6	Year 6	Year 9	Year 9	Year 11	Year 11
Total electricity consumed (kWhe)	59.927,6	84.620,3	84.620,3	84.620,3	84.620,3	84.620,3	84.620,3
Electricity from the grid (kWhe)	59.927,6	73.562,0	73.562,0	73.562,0	73.562,0	73.562,0	73.562,0
Self-consumed electricity (kWhe)	0,0	11.058,4	11.058,4	11.058,4	11.058,4	11.058,4	11.058,4
Total electricity cost (€)	10.126 €	12.430 €	12.430 €	12.430 €	12.430 €	12.430 €	12.430 €
Total natural gas consumed (kWh_{pcl})							
Natural gas from the grid (kWh _{pcl})	79.364,3	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
Total natural gas cost (€)	5.069 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
P1 TOTAL ENERGY COST	15.196 €	12.430 €	12.430 €	12.430 €	12.430 €	12.430 €	12.430 €
		-2.765 €	-2.765 €	-2.765 €	-2.765 €	-2.765 €	-2.765 €
P2 TOTAL MAINTENANCE COST	- €	1.813 €	- €	1.813 €	- €	1.813 €	- €
P3 TOTAL FULL WARRANTY COST	- €	701 €	- €	886 €	- €	991 €	- €
Total investment		113.426 €		113.426 €		113.426 €	
Interest tax		5,00%		5,00%		5,00%	
P4 TOTAL INSTALLATION FINANCING COST	- €	28.818 €	- €	19.304 €	- €	16.158 €	- €
Energy cost Eurofitness Sant Cugat		12.430 €	12.430 €	12.430 €	12.430 €	12.430 €	12.430 €
Energy Services Contract proposal cost (P2 - P3 - P4)		31.332 €	- €	22.004 €	- €	17.149 €	- €
ANUAL COST P1 - P2 - P3 - P4 (€/year)	15.196 €	43.763 €	12.430 €	34.434 €	12.430 €	31.393 €	12.430 €
		187,99%	-18,20%	126,60%	-18,20%	106,59%	-18,20%
		- 28.567 €	2.765 €	- 19.239 €	2.765 €	- 16.197 €	2.765 €
		Savings 94,67 tn CO2/year		Savings 151,48 tn CO2/year		Savings 189,34 tn CO2/year	

Figure 33 Annual comparison between actual energy costs and services breakdown and ESCO's proposals breakdown on 5-year/8-year/10-year EPC's for Lavola's Ecobuilding

D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies

All business plan simulations and the annual comparison between actual energy costs and services breakdown and future scenarios under a 5-year/8-year/10-year energy performance contracts (EPC's) represent the overall business plan simulation under which an ESCO conducts an assessment on the financial feasibility and profitability of these kind of contracts. Therefore, many reasoning factors must be underlined to define if the ESCO wants to run this contract under the variables and conditions mentioned before:

- In an Energy Performance Contract – Guaranteed Savings model (EPC GS), the ESCO guarantees a certain savings on the client's energy bill and assumes all technical risk. The client obtains a bank loan or uses its own resources to pay contractually determined fees to the ESCO and to the bank and keeps the difference.
- In an Energy Performance Contract – Shared Savings model (EPC SS), the ESCO can provide financing (therefore assuming both technical and credit risks for the client), as well as project development and implementation costs. That can be valuable for the client as it avoids the need for upfront capital costs, with ongoing payments to the ESCO based on savings obtained.

Figure 34 Energy Performance Contract – Guaranteed Savings model (EPC GS) (Source: [25])

Figure 35 Energy Performance Contract – Shared Savings model (EPC SS) (Source: [25])

- Therefore, depending on the client's financial capacity, the chosen EPC changes the financial status but either if it's a guaranteed savings model or a shared savings model, the client relies on the ESCO to assume all technical risks as it provides all project development and implementation costs. The client can rely on the ESCO to assume all financial risks via contractual arrangement (P₄), normally with an interest rate lower than the bank's but again assuming all technical risk.
- The Net Present Value (NPV) represents one of the best financial profitability indicators; it is a useful tool to determine whether a project or investment will

D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies

result in a net profit or a loss. Whenever the NPV is positive, the project is profitable; in all business plan simulations for the 3 reference cases, the NPV is positive, with its value increasing when the project's duration is longer (3,566.15 € for the 5-year contract, 5,613.38 € for the 8-year contract and 6,694.30 € for the 10-year contract). The simulations have been made considering a discount rate of 5% under the data published by the Spain's National Bank [26].

- The Internal Rate of Return (IRR) is another of the best financial profitability indicators; it is defined as the rate of return that sets the NPV of all cash flows for the investment equal to zero, meaning that it is the discount rate at which the NPV of the future cash flows is equal to the initial investment. Whenever the IRR is positive, the project is profitable; in all business plan simulations for the 3 reference cases, the IRR is positive, with its value decreasing when the project's duration is longer (6.59% for the 5-year contract, 5.47% for the 8-year contract and 5.13% for the 10-year contract).
- The IRR is a relative profitability indicator of the project, but not an absolute profitability indicator. When comparing different internal rates of return of two projects, the possible difference over their size is not considered (neither do other external factors as inflation, cost of capital or various financial risks). A project with a huge investment and a low IRR can have a bigger NPV than a lower investment project with a higher IRR; in conclusion, IRR cannot be considered as an alternative to NPV but as a complementary information while comparing different project's profitability. The reference case shows very low IRR's, in some cases even than the discount rate of the reference country (Spain), which might be an indicator of a remarkable financial risk.
- In this reference case, the total material execution budget is 113,426.03 €, a considerable amount of money that needs to be amortised through an efficient operation of the system and based on considerable energy (and cost) savings. In this reference case, approximately 2,765 €/year can be saved by applying the CHESS SETUP system, which can be translated to an initial payback analysis of 41.02 years (not considering replacements). Considering a 5-year contract, the client would have to assume an annual installation financing cost (P_4) of 28,818 €/year to finance the installation, which decreases to 19,304 €/year for an 8-year contract and to 16,158 €/year for a 10-year contract.
- That means that, in a 5-year contract, although from the beginning the client is already saving approximately 2,765 €/year, its overall energy services and energy consumption costs increase by 187.99% (5-year contract), by 126.60% (8-year contract) or, in the best scenario, by 106.59% (10-year contract). Assuming the fact that the return of initial investment is 41.02 years and considering that the lifespan of most of the essential equipment rounds between 20 – 30 years, that investment would not be profitable for the client

(but it is for the ESCO, as its implication will last no longer than 10 years and it will obtain economic profit from all work and services performed).

- That does not mean the system is not efficient: it indeed is, as the monitoring and control systems showed that, most of the time the CHESSE SETUP system has been working, it operated under expected performance parameters, thus providing a considerable amount of electrical (**11,058.36 kWh_e**) and thermal (**79,364.34 kWh_{PCI}**) energy savings, which translates to 2,765 €/year of cost savings for Lavola's Ecobuilding. Just as a reminder, though: the overall electricity consumption is increased as the new ASHP installed consumes about 33,423.67 kWh_e, increasing overall electricity consumption to 84,620.30 kWh_e (the chiller is removed, so another approximately 16,148.00 kWh_e are already saved). Therefore, the new electricity consumption from the grid when deploying the CHESSE SETUP's system proposal at Lavola's headquarters is 73,561.95 kWh_e.
- Following that path, it is essential to provide an annual maintenance (P2) and full warranty (P3) service, in order to ensure the correct operation, maintenance and equipment substitution whenever any problem arises. Those services include a monitoring and control service that also takes into account benchmarking with similar projects and real-time surveillance of the system's performance, enhancing installation's lifespan and energy efficiency.
- The main problem of this reference case is the high budget allocated to architecture works, PV installation, SCADA system implementation and the heat pump. Although PV panel cost has been already decreasing over the last decades, many suppliers do now offer integrated solutions adaptable either for new or existing buildings, therefore reducing architecture works (mainly PV panel structure and reinforcements) and improving overall system's cost. Both PV panels and their structure represent more than 65% of the overall PV budget line, therefore reducing those costs imply a significant overall budget decrease as the PV budget line represents a 28.80% of total MEB. The same goes for the SCADA system: in the reference case, that budget line represents a 28.72% of total MEB, therefore improving its key component costs would also lead to a MEB reduction. Regarding the heat pump, the only recommendation is to bear in mind different heat pump suppliers' solutions that could be easily implemented in an existing building, and match them with building's thermal demand and other variables involved (especially climatological ones) so that the heat pump's COP is maximized, its performance is done under correct operational parameters and its lifespan is stretched as much as possible.

For that reason, the next section will provide some recommendations and/or improvement proposals in order to reduce the CHESSE SETUP system's investment, thus lowering expected payback and increasing financial profitability indicators so that both the client and the ESCO can take profit of the CHESSE SETUP system deployment. Other proposals will be considered such as increasing profitability

margins of the services offered by the ESCO (P₂, P₃ and P₄) or modifying business plan simulation variables to find the most suitable financial scenario, taking into account economical perspective issues and other financial information given by the banks and other creditor entities.

10.1.4. Improvement proposals

As stated previously, the main issue detected for this demonstration scenario has been the high budget allocated to architecture works, PV installation, SCADA system implementation and the heat pump. In that case, different proposals have been considered to mitigate the effects of the actual low VPN and IRR (as well as the high payback):

- Increase heat pump performance

As it is widely known, a heat pump is a thermal machine that transfers heat from a cold source to a hot source with great efficiency. The main advantage with regard to traditional heating and cooling systems is that they grab energy from the environment (cold source), whether if it comes from air, water or ground, and transfer it to inner dependencies (hot source) with a relatively small amount of work (using either electrical or thermal energy). By using a refrigerant in a closed thermodynamic cycle, and considering both hot and cold sources, this fluid serves as a heat transport from the environment to a room, so that space can be acclimatized accordingly.

The heat pump must get the heat from the outdoor environment, therefore whenever the outdoor temperature is lower, the amount of energy absorbed from it would decrease. That means that, in order to satisfy the thermal demand from a room/building/volume, if the outdoor temperature is lower the electrical or thermal energy consumed by the compressor would be higher. As we must stick to weather conditions from each geographical area, and as stated in Deliverables 3.4 and 3.5 about the heat pump design, the performance of a heat pump depends on many different parameters such as the temperature of the heat source, the heat sink, the working medium, the arrangement, the thermodynamic cycle conditions, the characteristics of the components of the controlling system, etc.

For so, the refrigerant selection has a direct impact on the overall cost and lifecycle of the system and should be considered as an improvement proposal in the heat pump design; as new regulations impose strict limitations to hydrofluorocarbons (HFC), hydro-fluoro-olefins (HFOs) and other types of refrigerants should be the next path in the research and development about heat pump technology as an alternative low global warming potential (GWP) working fluid. Considering both condenser and evaporator refrigerant temperatures, the overall thermodynamic cycle's performance can be increased, therefore reducing the amount of work (either in form of electrical or thermal energy) required to compress the refrigerant.

Last but not least, and directly related to the CHESSE SETUP's project objectives, to assess the efficiency of a heat pump and evaluate the amount of renewable energy

D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies

that these technologies can supply, we must previously know the seasonal performance factor (SPF). The SPF is referred to net active seasonal average efficiency ($SCOP_{net}$) for electrically driven heat pumps, or to net seasonal primary power-active ratio ($SPER_{net}$) for heat-driven heat pumps. For heat pumps in which the desired output is the cooling effect, the seasonal energy efficiency factor (SEER) is defined.

Current guides and standardised procedures to measure SPF do also consider a weight factor depending on the heat pump technology: the supplier usually offers a COP referred to a condensation temperature that might not be the operation temperature of the equipment/system. The technical justification is that the COP decrease according to the condensation temperature's increase does not depend on the energy source (air, water or ground) but that temperature indeed has an impact on the heat pump performance: whenever the fluid's working temperature is lower, it will ease the refrigerant's condensation, therefore increasing COP and thermal power supplied by the heat pump. This weight factor is only applied to electrical-driven heat pumps.

Moving on, when talking to the specific case of Lavola's Ecobuilding, the curve between investment costs and energy cost savings should cross so that there is matched correlation allowing cost savings to be higher than investment costs. As this work might lead to another entire project demonstration case, the following section will provide some general solutions that might increase NPV and IRR, so that the solution is financially profitable but would need to be demonstrated via new pilot sites and a new deployment of the CHESS SETUP system, which has already been proved to be efficient.

The many ways to increase the IRR are:

- **Reduce investment costs:** although in the reference case it has not a significant impact on the IRR, its calculation mainly depends on the cash flow of each period which is totally linked to the P₄ financial investment quote to be paid by the client. Whenever this cash flow is lower and the project's duration is kept, the IRR will increase. Therefore, the investment will be more profitable, indicating that the return of the investment is sooner than before.

That is the best option for the client: whenever investment costs are reduced, annual P₄ quote will also decrease, therefore increasing financial profitability for the client as, at the same energy and cost savings provided by the new technology deployed, lower investment needs to be recovered. Therefore, the recovery time is significantly lower, which is also a positive factor for the ESCO as it will be easier to sell the P₄ annual quote to the client.

- **Increase profit margin over investment costs:** paradoxically, when increasing the profit margin over investment costs, the cash flow of each period is increased but the ESCO's P₄ cost remains the same. That means that if the ESCO is able to reduce material and mankind costs (thus improving profit margin over investment costs), the IRR will significantly increase; for example, in the business plan simulation on a 5-year contract, doubling the profit margin over investment costs results in a 10.28% IRR (for the initial 6.59%). That can be translated into the following: it may be worth to waste more time and resources into finding the most suitable material or mankind supplier (in terms of price and quality assurance) rather than finding the most efficient equipment or work crew, as the manpower and/or equipment costs may not be matching with the overall system to be deployed.

Following previous arguments on reducing investment costs, whenever the ESCO can increase its profit margin but in a lower proportion than the investment cost decrease, both ESCO and client could benefit from it. As obvious, when increasing profit margins over investment costs that implies increasing P₄ annual quote to the detriment of the client's interests. Therefore, the ESCO could increase profit margin over investment costs as long as it is able to reduce in the same or bigger proportion the investment costs. That being said, that proposal highly depends on the cost proportion over the rest of services: whenever the P₄ annual quote represents a high percentage of energy service package provided, increasing the margin profit will result in a significant increase of overall project's NPV and IRR but if P₄ annual quote represents a low percentage of all energy service package provided, the impact will be significantly lower. That depends on each and every project, as different variables do integrate the algorithm calculation of each energy services quote depending on the technology deployed, the contract's duration and other technical/economic indicators.

- **Increase profit margin over maintenance and warranty services:** the same as abovementioned. Depending on the annual quote of maintenance (P₂) and full

D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies

warranty (P₃) services compared to improvement works and renewal of installations (P₄), it might be better to increase profit margins over those services rather than looking for a P₄ reduction. That highly depends on the client: in our case, it is better to go for a P₄ reduction as it represents the main cost of the contract (since it offers the financing of a significant initial investment with small operation, maintenance and substitution costs when the contract is lower than the main equipment's' lifespan) rather than improving/increasing profit margins over P₂ and P₃.

The argumentation from previous sections still applies to P₂ and P₃ annual quotes: when increasing profit margins over maintenance and warranty services, the ESCO improve overall financial profitability to the detriment of the client's interests, as the new annual quote is increased. Therefore, and as stated before, that proposal highly depends on the cost proportion over the rest of services and has to be matched with the client's interests.

That being said, the results from the business plan simulations shows that, even the ESCO business model applied is financially and economically feasible and profitable, the client would not be able to take profit from the deployment of the CHESSE SETUP system under those specific conditions and/or technical requirements. The following Deliverable's section will explore different ways so that business models in the form of private partnerships between the client and either a bank (to finance the improvement works and deployment of new equipment) or a bank plus a contractor (one party to finance the installation and another party to assume the installation, commissioning and operation if requested) do offer better financial indicators, identifying the most suitable scenarios where the CHESSE SETUP system can be deployed.

10.2. Sant Cugat Sports Centre – Sant Cugat (Spain)

As a brief reminder, the Sant Cugat's pilot site has been designed as a CHESSE SETUP system proposal for a big scale end user such as the Sant Cugat Sports Centre, composed of 4 buildings next to the City Hall. Since 90% of the total energy consumption comes from the Eurofitness building, the CHESSE SETUP configuration will focus on reducing this building's energy consumption via deployment of a STES to optimize and enhance energy usage and performance of the Sports Centre.

10.2.1. Total cost of operation

As seen on Lavola's demonstration scenario, we first need to know the exact cost of deploying the CHESSE SETUP system at the pilot focus area. Further detail of the all budget items is described in Appendix III, which can be resumed as it follows:

Budget line	Cost
Architecture (including demolition works, civil works and waste management)	223,681.23 €
Installations (including heat generation and storage systems, energy distribution and control devices)	438.240.89 €
TOTAL MATERIAL EXECUTION BUDGET (MEB)	661,922.12 €
General costs (13% MEB)	86,049.88 €
Industrial profit (6% MEB)	39,715.33 €
TOTAL IMPLEMENTATION BUDGET (IB)	787,687.32 €
VALUE-ADDED TAX (21% IB)	165,414.34 €
TOTAL CHESSE SETUP IMPLEMENTATION BUDGET (VAT INCLUDED)	953,101.66 €

Table 9 Main budget items CHESSE SETUP's system deployment at Sant Cugat's Sport Centre (Source: CUG)

For the business plan simulation, this report will be working (as it's usual) with the material execution budget as it only involves the requested material to be installed and the pilot site that can be attributed to the CHESSE SETUP system deployment. In that case, a total MEB of **661,922.12€** is considered for Sant Cugat's pilot site.

The following steps include the calculation of both maintenance (P₂) and full warranty (P₃) costs, including all services detailed in sections 6.2 and 6.3 of the current report, as well as what has been detailed previously in section 10.

In order to calculate the P2 cost, the main variables affecting its calculation are:

- Personnel costs, including operational staff, operator/workman, etc.;
- Tools, clothing and other material costs including uniforms, protective and safety equipment, etc.;
- Vehicle and transportation costs;
- Communication and management systems (PDA, monitoring devices, etc.);
- Subcontracting costs for specific works;
- Additional specific contracting works not included before (such as legionella prevention tasks, sanitation, etc.).

Taking into account all personnel hours and concepts seen before, the total annual cost of maintaining the CHESS SETUP system at Sant Cugat's Sports Centre is approximately **3,818.00€/year (does not change with the contract's duration)**.

In order to calculate the P3 cost, the main variables affecting its calculation are:

- Personnel manpower cost;
- Reference year for amortisation;
- Algorithms of failure calculation of equipment involved;
- Range of equipment involved;
- Amount of equipment involved;
- Lifespan of equipment involved.

Taking into account all equipment and concepts seen before, the total annual cost of a full warranty service for the CHESS SETUP system at Sant Cugat's Sports Centre ranges between **1,560.00€/year and 2,206.00 €/year (5-year to 10-year EPC)**.

10.2.2. Energy savings

Once seen the total improvement works/installation renewal costs (P4), as well as maintenance (P2) and full warranty (P3) costs, it's time to check the main results of the CHESS SETUP system's energy retrofit. This time it will not be correct to strictly define it as an energy management (P1) service and associated cost, as this term refers to all energy management needed for the correct operation of the installation contract, such as the energy management supply (fuel and electricity), the quality, quantity, control operation and supply guarantees. Whenever this is part of the contract, the ESCO is responsible to provide the client a set of agreed services (such as heating, lighting, etc.), even taking responsibility of the installation's energy purchase in order to ensure the client an immediate save compared with the actual energetic cost. As this is not a P1 service, this report will only focus on the energy savings data coming from the monitoring system compared to the baseline energy demand and consumption from the building. That information is shown at the next page's table, which summarizes the main building's energy demand and consumption.

Heating & Cooling demand and Natural Gas consumption					Electricity demand
	3 Swimming-pool water heating (kWh _{PCI})	Swimming-pool Air Treatment (kWh _{PCI})	Domestic Hot Water (kWh _{PCI})	Natural Gas consumption (kWh _{PCI})	Electricity consumption (kWh _e)
January	51,165.00	109,837.00	59,714.00	220,716.00	88,130.00
February	45,302.00	98,637.00	46,744.00	190,683.00	81,190.00
March	48,138.00	87,747.00	47,771.00	183,656.00	78,951.00
April	44,633.00	73,117.00	42,378.00	160,128.00	88,987.00
May	45,112.00	50,564.00	38,768.00	134,444.00	86,647.00
June	26,174.00	30,529.00	27,289.00	83,992.00	96,235.00
July	26,038.00	14,842.00	15,162.00	56,042.00	101,210.00
August	27,047.00	27,844.00	10,616.00	65,507.00	98,271.00
September	27,151.00	46,353.00	27,396.00	100,900.00	89,634.00
October	46,121.00	65,538.00	39,809.00	151,468.00	92,683.00
November	46,586.00	82,469.00	46,230.00	175,285.00	78,501.00
December	51,165.00	97,358.00	59,714.00	208,237.00	65,467.00
TOTAL	484,632.00	784,835.00	461,591.00	1,731,058.00	1,045,906.00

Table 10 Energy demand and consumption of Sant Cugat's Sport Centre (Source: Deliverable 3.7)

The contents of Table 10 come from previous simulations being performed by other partners in the Consortium, which have been included in Deliverable 3.7: that information corresponds to both electrical and thermal energy demand from Sant Cugat's Sports Centre regarding weather and occupancy profiles from 2016. Later on we will find that overall natural gas consumption has increased, as showed by real invoices of the building's energy consumption over the years 2019 and 2020.

10.2.2.1. Electricity savings

As stated previously, and due to the COVID-19 pandemic situation we are currently suffering, the CHESSE SETUP's system performance is not reliable from March 2020 and so on, as Spain's population had experienced a confinement/isolation situation which was decreed by the Government. For that, BCN has performed a deep analysis on relevant data coming from the monitoring & control system deployed by WAT, which provided relevant information from September 2019 until February 2020: for so, the rest of the year's system performance has been forecasted taking into account the geographical demonstration site location, solar irradiation, energy bills and expected system performance under standard climatological conditions of each season.

Figure 36 Estimation of monthly solar irradiation at Sant Cugat's Sport Centre (Source: PV-GIS)

As a result, a total amount of **31,976.00 kWh_e** as primary electricity energy savings has been estimated to come from hybrid PV-T panels' energy production. In fact, the total amount of electricity energy production from PV-T panels is 41,604.00 kWh_e but 9,629.00 kWh_e must be deducted considering that the CHESSE SETUP system consumes electricity from the PV-T panels (the total CHESSE SETUP system electricity consumption is 25,944.00 kWh_e, where 16,316.00 kWh_e come from the grid and 9,629.00 kWh_e come from the PV-T panels). Therefore, the net electricity savings of the installation is 15,660 kWh_e. As stated before, it has been estimated that the CHESSE SETUP system is providing 31.976,00 kWh_e as primary electricity energy savings, which later on will be translated into cost savings depending on the current electricity energy costs [€/kWh_e].

10.2.2.2. Thermal savings

In the same path, a total amount of **224,045 kWh_{PCI}** as primary thermal energy savings has been estimated, combining thermal generation coming from hybrid PV-T panels and sensible heat storage (SHS) performed in the tank thermal energy storage (TTES) in the form of a 100 m³ water tank installed in Sant Cugat's Sport Centre.

Total Sports Centre Consumption													
CHESS SETUP SYSTEM											BASELINE		
	Elect. Prod.	Electricity consumption				Total energy consumption					Total		
	PV-T (kWh)	f_PV-T (kWh)	f_Grid (kWh)	Total (kWh)	Surplus (kWh)	Electric (kWh)	NG (kWh _{PCI})	Electric Cost (€)	Natural Gas Cost (€)	CO ₂ (kg)	Natural Gas (kWh _{PCI})	Cost (€)	CO ₂ (kg)
January	1,315	378	1,479	1,857	937	542	369,418	81.49 €	21,480.19 €	97,275	377,567	21,954.05 €	99,343
February	2,416	509	2,009	2,518	1,907	102	207,812	-47.52 €	12,264.92 €	54,692	221,116	13,050.09 €	58,178
March	2,972	474	1,619	2,093	2,498	-879	239,696	-95.29 €	14,123.96 €	62,944	250,801	14,778.34 €	65,989
April	3,871	893	2,852	3,745	2,978	-126	227,350	-29.45 €	13,405.60 €	59,801	249,666	14,721.48 €	65,690
May	4,238	978	2,280	3,258	3,260	-980	173,207	-109.08 €	8,561.06 €	45,436	199,401	9,855.76 €	52,465
June	5,222	1,205	310	1,515	4,017	-3,706	83,561	-362.42 €	4,176.47 €	21,468	108,863	5,441.06 €	28,643
July	5,691	1,313	16	1,330	4,377	-4,361	38,027	-424.36 €	2,303.22 €	9,396	64,065	3,880.27 €	16,856
August	5,792	1,337	32	1,368	4,456	-4,424	47,134	-430.55 €	2,832.92 €	11,783	74,181	4,458.54 €	19,518
September	4,737	1,093	97	1,190	3,644	-3,546	84,485	-345.58 €	5,022.43 €	21,733	111,636	6,636.49 €	29,373
October	1,578	640	1,811	2,451	938	873	204,031	61.03 €	12,006.38 €	53,805	218,545	12,860.44 €	57,502
November	2,148	395	2,073	2,468	1,753	320	167,894	21.72 €	9,899.53 €	44,220	180,374	10,635.37 €	47,459
December	1,626	413	1,737	2,150	1,213	524	304,582	57.93 €	17,845.31 €	80,213	315,027	18,457.28 €	82,888
TOTAL	41,604	9,629	16,316	25,944	31,976	-15,660	2,147,197	-1,622.07 €	123,922.00 €	562,767	2,371,242	136,729.18 €	623,905
SAVINGS [%]											9.45%	10.55%	9.8%
SAVINGS [kWh _{PCI} , €t and kgCO ₂]											224,045	14,429.25	61,138

Table 11 Comparative table between CHESS SETUP energy generation and consumption and baseline consumption of Sant Cugat's Sport Centre (Source: BCN Ecologia)

The red rows come from an estimation performed by BCN taking into account the most recent energy bills and monitoring & control system's data before all the current sanitary emergency situation arose. The methodology is based on:

- Evaluating the boilers' efficiency by dividing the swimming pool water energy demand (kWh_t) by the swimming pool water energy consumption (kWh_{PCI}). The annual efficiency average of the boilers has been estimated to be 86.82%.
- Knowing the main hybrid PV-T panels' characteristics (such as dimensions, opening area, efficiency, thermal losses coefficients, power, etc.), a monthly thermal contribution from the CHESSE SETUP configuration has been estimated for the months where its optimal performance could not be achieved. The annual useful thermal energy provided by the CHESSE SETUP system has been estimated to be 193,279 kWh_t , which is translated to 224,045 kWh_{PCI} primary thermal energy savings applying the boilers' efficiency.
- The little differences between the kWh_{PCI} conversions are also caused by the actual billing information from September 2019 to February 2020, which is slightly different from earlier billing information (or what has been theoretically considered/estimated in Deliverables 3.7 and 5.1).

In order to check the CHESSE SETUP system's performance, another methodology has been conducted to compare BCN's mathematical calculations with a scientific methodology approach followed by Carl Begeal and Terese Decker [27]. The heat loss through the isolation of cylindrical tanks is determined by the following equation:

$$Q = \frac{k \cdot 2 \cdot \pi \cdot L \cdot (T_s - T_a)}{\ln\left(\frac{R_2}{R_1}\right) + \left(\frac{k}{h_t \cdot R_2}\right)}$$

Where:

$Q \rightarrow$ Thermal loss [kW]

$k \rightarrow$ Thermal conductivity coefficient [W/m·K]

$L \rightarrow$ Length of the cylinder [m]

$T_s \rightarrow$ Surface temperature [K]

$T_a \rightarrow$ Environment temperature [K]

$R_1 \rightarrow$ Tank radius [m]

$R_2 \rightarrow$ Tank + insulation radius [m]

$h_t \rightarrow$ Convection coefficient [$\text{W}/\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{K}$]

The cylindrical tank installed in Sant Cugat's Sports Centre has a 1,20m radius (1,55m including a 0.35m mineral wool insulation layer). Considering a thermal conductivity coefficient of 0.035 W/m·K (as mineral wool stone with a density lower than 160 kg/m^3

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has an λ between 0.034 and 0.038 W/m·K), a cylinder length of 25m, a surface temperature of 45 °C and an average environment temperature of 20 °C, and a convection coefficient of 15 W/m²·K:

$$Q = \frac{0.035 \cdot 2 \cdot \pi \cdot 25 \cdot (45 - 20)}{\ln\left(\frac{1.55}{1.20}\right) + \left(\frac{0.035}{15 \cdot 1.55}\right)} = 0.5296 \text{ kW}$$

In order to be as maximum precise as possible, the simulation has considered that thermal losses from the tank happen at all time (24 hours a day, either the hybrid PV-T panels are producing thermal power or not as thermodynamically speaking, the energy flow is constant over time and does not stop) as well as considering a 5% thermal loss from the distribution and transportation pipelines. As a result:

	Solar irradiation (kWh/m ²)	Potential solar energy (kWh)	Produced thermal energy (kWh _t)	Thermal energy losses TES (kWh _t)	Thermal energy losses pipelines (kWh _t)	Usable thermal energy VLC (kWh _t)	Usable thermal energy BCN (kWh _t)
January	99.05	22,941.56	10,323.70	393.99	516.19	9,413.53	7,100.00
February	128.90	29,855.30	13,434.89	355.86	671.74	12,407.28	11,600.00
March	168.62	39,055.09	17,574.79	393.99	878.74	16,302.07	9,700.04
April	178.37	41,313.35	18,591.01	381.28	929.55	17,280.18	19,527.79
May	195.59	45,301.77	20,385.80	393.99	1,019.29	18,972.52	22,944.34
June	210.34	48,718.11	21,923.15	393.99	1,096.16	20,433.01	21,506.40
July	226.08	52,363.75	23,563.69	393.99	1,178.18	21,991.52	22,132.00
August	225.02	52,118.23	23,453.20	393.99	1,172.66	21,886.56	22,990.00
September	197.01	45,630.67	20,533.80	381.28	1,026.69	19,125.83	23,078.00
October	147.26	34,107.77	15,348.50	393.99	767.42	14,187.09	12,700.00
November	99.73	23,099.06	10,394.58	381.28	519.73	9,493.57	10,900.00
December	94.80	21,957.20	9,880.74	393.99	494.04	8,992.72	9,100.00
TOTAL	1,970.77	456,461.86	205,407.84	4,651.57	10,270.39	190,485.88	193,278.57

Table 12 Comparative table between Begeal&Decker methodology analysis and BCN's analysis of the CHES5 SETUP system thermal generation of Sant Cugat's Sport Centre (Source: BCN Ecologia)

The Begeal&Decker simulation has been performed under the solar irradiation data from PV-GIS as seen from Figure 36. The first simulation results by VLC show a total amount of 190,485.88 kWh_t usable thermal energy while BCN's simulation results offers a total amount of 193,278.57 kWh_t usable thermal energy. Those minor differences show that both simulations reached very similar amounts of thermal energy expected production by the CHES5 SETUP system deployment at Sant Cugat's Sports Centre over one-year time frame.

Therefore, considering this amount of usable thermal energy translated into primary energy coming from natural gas combustion, the system offers the abovementioned 224,045 kWh_{PCI} primary thermal energy savings from overall system performance.

10.2.3. Business plan simulation

After all variables have been defined, it is the time to perform a business plan simulation under many different perspectives, in order to analyse the feasibility and profitability of the CHESSE SETUP system deployment at Sant Cugat's Sports Centre. The main variables involved in the simulation are:

- **Total investment cost (previously referred as MEB):** 661,922.12 €;
- **Annual maintenance (P2) and full warranty (P3) costs:** 3,818.00 €/year and between 1,560.00€/year and 2,206.00 €/year (5-year to 10-year EPC).
- **Duration of the contract:** 5 years/ 8 years/ 10 years;
- **Amortisation:** the same as the duration of the contract;
- **Interest rate for the total investment cost:** 5%;
- **Annual CPI increase:** 1.45%
- **Profit margin of the ESCO on total investment cost:** 10% (therefore, the installation is sold to the client for 728,114.33 €);
- **Client's payment schedule:** up to 2 months' maximum;

As the contract's duration is not fixed and depends on the client's needs and the ESCO's perspective on the operation and maintenance works of the technical configuration of the system, a simulation of an 8-year contract and a 10-year contract has been also conducted as they are also common contract durations on these kind of projects. In those cases:

- **Annual maintenance (P2) and full warranty (P3) costs for an 8-year contract:** 3,818.00 €/year (no changes) and 1,973.00 €/year respectively;
- **Annual maintenance (P2) and full warranty (P3) costs for a 10-year contract:** 3,818.00 €/year (no changes) and 2,206.00 €/year respectively;
- **Duration of the contract:** 8 years and 10 years respectively;
- **Amortisation:** the same as the duration of the contract, 8 years and 10 years respectively;
- **The remaining variables involved in the business plan simulation are the same.**

Last but not least, those simulations have been performed under simulated and estimated data coming from different partners and other Deliverables of the CHESSE SETUP's project; therefore, VLC exposes that those business plan simulations may not correspond with the real system performance under a complete full operating cycle (at least one year), as the reporting period has not lasted a complete year.

*D6.1 Business models analysis
for the case studies*

Business plan simulation (5-year contract)		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Final sales (P2+P3+P4)		173,554	173,609	173,666	173,724	173,784	
Total costs (P2+P3 +Structure cost)		14,808	14,875	14,943	15,014	15,086	
EBITDA		158,746	158,735	158,723	158,710	158,698	
	Amortisation	-132,384	-132,384	-132,384	-132,384	-132,384	
EBIT		26,362	26,351	26,339	26,327	26,314	
EBT (No financial costs considered)		26,362	26,351	26,339	26,327	26,314	
	Tax base	26,362	26,351	26,339	26,327	26,314	
Corporate income tax (25%)		6,590	6,588	6,585	6,582	6,579	
Net benefits		19,771	19,763	19,754	19,745	19,736	
Client payments		145,025	173,600	173,657	173,715	173,774	28,567
Supplier payments		13,591	14,869	14,938	15,008	15,080	1,240
ETE		131,434	158,731	158,719	158,707	158,694	27,327
Cash Flow		-537,079	152,143	152,134	152,125	152,115	27,327
Project TIR	6.83%						
Project NPV	23,917.75€						

Table 13 Business plan simulation at Sant Cugat's Sports Centre for a 5-year EPC under abovementioned conditions

*D6.1 Business models analysis
for the case studies*

Business plan simulation (8-year contract)		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028
Final sales (P2+P3+P4)		118,447	118,502	118,558	118,617	118,676	118,733	118,795	118,857	
Total costs (P2+P3+Structure cost)		11,895	11,968	12,042	12,119	12,197	12,272	12,353	12,435	
EBITDA		106,551	106,534	106,516	106,498	106,479	106,461	106,442	106,422	
	Amortisation	-82,740	-82,740	-82,740	-82,740	-82,740	-82,740	-82,740	-82,740	
EBIT		26,362	23,811	23,795	23,777	23,759	23,740	23,722	23,703	
EBT (No financial costs considered)		23,811	23,795	23,777	23,759	23,740	23,722	23,703	23,683	
	Tax base	23,811	23,795	47,572	71,330	95,070	118,792	142,495	166,178	
Corporate income tax (25%)		5,953	5,949	5,944	5,940	5,935	5,931	5,926	5,921	
Net benefits		17,858	17,846	17,833	17,819	17,805	17,792	17,777	17,762	
Client payments		98,976	118,493	118,549	118,607	118,667	118,724	118,785	118,847	19,538
Supplier payments		10,917	11,962	12,036	12,112	12,191	12,266	12,346	12,428	1,022
ETE		88,058	106,531	106,513	106,495	106,476	106,458	106,439	106,419	18,516
Cash Flow		-579,816	100,582	100,569	100,555	100,541	100,528	100,513	100,498	18,516
Project TIR	5.69%									
Project NPV	26,143.12 €									

Table 14 Business plan simulation at Sant Cugat's Sports Centre for an 8-year EPC under abovementioned conditions

**D6.1 Business models analysis
for the case studies**

Business plan simulation (10-year contract)		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
Final sales (P2+P3+P4)		100,318	100,374	100,430	100,488	100,548	100,605	100,667	100,729	100,792	100,857	
Total costs (P2+P3+Structure cost)		11,029	11,105	11,183	11,263	11,345	11,422	11,507	11,593	11,680	11,768	
EBITDA		89,289	89,269	89,248	89,226	89,204	89,183	89,160	89,136	89,113	89,089	
	Amortisation	-66,192	-66,192	-66,192	-66,192	-66,192	-66,192	-66,192	-66,192	-66,192	-66,192	
EBIT		23,097	23,077	23,056	23,035	23,012	22,991	22,968	22,945	22,921	22,897	
EBT (No financial costs considered)		23,097	23,077	23,056	23,035	23,012	22,991	22,968	22,945	22,921	22,897	
	Tax base	23,097	23,077	46,134	69,168	92,181	22,991	45,960	68,905	91,826	22,897	
Corporate income tax (25%)		5,774	5,769	5,764	5,759	5,753	5,748	5,742	5,736	5,730	5,724	
Net benefits		17,323	17,308	17,292	17,276	17,259	17,243	17,226	17,209	17,191	17,173	
Client payments		83,828	100,365	100,421	100,479	100,538	100,596	100,656	100,719	100,782	100,846	16,579
Supplier payments		10,123	11,099	11,176	11,256	11,338	11,416	11,500	11,586	11,673	11,761	967
ETE		73,705	89,266	89,245	89,223	89,201	89,180	89,156	89,133	89,110	89,085	15,612
Cash Flow		-593,991	83,496	83,481	83,464	83,447	83,432	83,414	83,397	83,379	83,361	15,612
Project TIR	5.35%											
Project NPV	30,480.24 €											

Table 15 Business plan simulation at Sant Cugat's Sports Centre for a 10-year EPC under abovementioned conditions

D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies

ANUAL COMPARISON EUROFITNESS SANT CUGAT

	Actual status (Baseline)	EPC Proposal 5 years		EPC Proposal 8 years		EPC Proposal 10 years	
		Year 5	Year 6	Year 8	Year 9	Year 10	Year 11
Total electricity consumed (kWh_e)	1.045.906,0	1.062.221,7	1.062.221,7	1.062.221,7	1.062.221,7	1.062.221,7	1.062.221,7
Electricity from the grid (kWh _e)	1.045.906,0	1.030.246,1	1.030.246,1	1.030.246,1	1.030.246,1	1.030.246,1	1.030.246,1
Self-consumed electricity (kWh _e)	0,0	31.975,7	31.975,7	31.975,7	31.975,7	31.975,7	31.975,7
Total electricity cost (€/kWh _e)	94.132 €	92.722 €	92.722 €	92.722 €	92.722 €	92.722 €	92.722 €
Total natural gas consumed (kWh_{pci})							
Natural gas from the grid (kWh _{pci})	2.371.242,2	2.147.197,3	2.147.197,3	2.147.197,3	2.147.197,3	2.147.197,3	2.147.197,3
Total natural gas cost (€/kWh _{pci})	136.729 €	123.922 €	123.922 €	123.922 €	123.922 €	123.922 €	123.922 €
P1 TOTAL ENERGY COST	230.861 €	216.644 €	216.644 €	216.644 €	216.644 €	216.644 €	216.644 €
		-14.217 €	-14.217 €	-14.217 €	-14.217 €	-14.217 €	-14.217 €
P2 TOTAL MAINTENANCE COST	- €	3.818 €	- €	3.818 €	- €	3.636 €	- €
P3 TOTAL FULL WARRANTY COST	- €	1.560 €	- €	1.973 €	- €	2.206 €	- €
Total investment		661.922 €		661.922 €		661.922 €	
Interest tax		5,00%		5,00%		5,00%	
P4 TOTAL INSTALLATION FINANCING COST	- €	168.176 €	- €	112.655 €	- €	94.294 €	- €
Energy cost Eurofitness Sant Cugat		216.644 €	216.644 €	216.644 €	216.644 €	216.644 €	216.644 €
Energy Services Contract proposal cost (P2 - P3 - P4)		173.554 €	- €	118.447 €	- €	96.500 €	- €
ANUAL COST P1 - P2 - P3 - P4 (€/year)	230.861 €	390.198 €	216.644 €	335.091 €	216.644 €	316.781 €	216.644 €
		69,02%	-6,16%	45,15%	-6,16%	37,22%	-6,16%
		- 159.338 €	14.217 €	- 104.230 €	14.217 €	- 85.920 €	14.217 €
		Savings 305,69 tn CO2/year		Savings 489,10 tn CO2/year		Savings 611,38 tn CO2/year	

Figure 37 Annual comparison between actual energy costs and services breakdown and ESCO's proposals breakdown on 5-year/8-year/10-year EPC's for Sant Cugat's Sports Centre

D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies

All business plan simulations and the annual comparison between actual energy costs and services breakdown and future scenarios under a 5-year/8-year/10-year energy performance contracts (EPC's) represent the overall business plan simulation under which an ESCO conducts an assessment on the financial feasibility and profitability of these kind of contracts. Therefore, many reasoning factors must be underlined to define if the ESCO wants to run this contract under the variables and conditions mentioned before:

- In an Energy Performance Contract – Guaranteed Savings model (EPC GS), the ESCO guarantees a certain savings on the client's energy bill and assumes all technical risk. The client obtains a bank loan or uses its own resources to pay contractually determined fees to the ESCO (P₄) and to the bank and keeps the difference.
- In an Energy Performance Contract – Shared Savings model (EPC SS), the ESCO can provide financing (therefore assuming both technical and credit risks for the client), as well as project development and implementation costs. That can be valuable for the client as it avoids the need for upfront capital costs, with ongoing payments to the ESCO based on savings obtained.

Figure 38 Energy Performance Contract – Guaranteed Savings model (EPC GS) (Source: [25])

Figure 39 Energy Performance Contract – Shared Savings model (EPC SS) (Source: [25])

- Therefore, depending on the client's financial capacity, the chosen EPC changes the financial status but either if it's a guaranteed savings model or a shared savings model, the client relies on the ESCO to assume all technical risks as it provides all project development and implementation costs. The client can rely on the ESCO to assume all financial risks via contractual arrangement (P₄), normally with an interest rate lower than the bank's but again assuming all technical risk.
- The Net Present Value (NPV) represents one of the best financial profitability indicators; it is a useful tool to determine whether a project or investment will

result in a net profit or a loss. Whenever the NPV is positive, the project is profitable; in all business plan simulations for the 3 reference cases, the NPV is positive, with its value increasing when the project's duration is longer (23,917.75 € for the 5-year contract, 26,143.12 € for the 8-year contract and 30,480.24 € for the 10-year contract). The simulations have been made considering a discount rate of 5% under the data published by the Spain's National Bank [26].

- The Internal Rate of Return (IRR) is another of the best financial profitability indicators; it is defined as the rate of return that sets the NPV of all cash flows for the investment equal to zero, meaning that it is the discount rate at which the NPV of the future cash flows is equal to the initial investment. Whenever the IRR is positive, the project is profitable; in all business plan simulations for the 3 reference cases, the IRR is positive, with its value decreasing when the project's duration is longer (6.83% for the 5-year contract, 5.69% for the 8-year contract and 5.35% for the 10-year contract).
- The IRR is a relative profitability indicator of the project, but not an absolute profitability indicator. When comparing different internal rates of return of two projects, the possible difference over their size is not considered (neither do other external factors as inflation, cost of capital or various financial risks). A project with a huge investment and a low IRR can have a bigger NPV than a lower investment project with a higher IRR; in conclusion, IRR cannot be considered as an alternative to NPV but as a complementary information while comparing different project's profitability. The reference case shows very low IRR's, in some cases even than the discount rate of the reference country (Spain), which might be an indicator of a remarkable financial risk.
- In this reference case, the total material execution budget is 661,922.12 €, a considerable amount of money that needs to be amortised through an efficient operation of the system and based on considerable energy (and cost) savings. In this reference case, just a little more than 14,000 €/year can be saved by applying the CHESSE SETUP system, which can be translated to a payback of 46.55 years. Considering a 5-year contract, the client would have to assume an annual installation financing cost (P_4) of 168,176 €/year to finance the installation, which decreases to 112,655 €/year for an 8-year contract and to 94,294 €/year for a 10-year contract.
- That means that, in a 5-year contract, although from the beginning the client is already saving 14,217 €/year, its overall energy services and energy consumption costs increase by 69.02% (5-year contract), by 45.15% (8-year contract) or, in the best scenario, by 37.22% (10-year contract). Assuming the fact that the return of initial investment is 46.55 years and considering that the lifespan of most of the essential equipment rounds between 20 – 30 years, that investment would not be profitable for the client (but it is for the ESCO, as its implication will last no longer than 10 years).

D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies

- That does not mean the system is not efficient: it indeed is, as the monitoring and control systems showed that, most of the time the CHESSE SETUP system has been working, it operated under expected performance parameters, thus providing a considerable amount of electrical (**31,976 kWh_e**) and thermal (**224,045 kWh_{PCI}**) energy savings, which translated to 14,127 €/year of cost savings for Sant Cugat's Sports Centre.
- Following that path, it is essential to provide an annual maintenance (P₂) and full warranty (P₃) service, in order to ensure the correct operation, maintenance and equipment substitution whenever any problem arises. Those services include a monitoring and control service that also takes into account benchmarking with similar projects and real-time surveillance of the system's performance, enhancing installation's lifespan and energy efficiency.
- The main problem of this reference case is the high budget allocated to architecture works and TTES implementation. As stated in Deliverable 2.1, in order to provide efficient results while operating STES systems, water tanks should have storage volumes over 1,000 m³; many examples of existing SSHS around Europe use TTES with a maximum capacity between 2,750 – 10,000 m³, which significantly reduces investment costs (for water tank volumes under 500 m³, investment costs can range between 450 – 500 €/m³ while water tank volumes over 10,000 m³ reached investment costs of around 50 €/m³).
- Following the same path, hot water TTES offer a thermal storage capacity of 60 – 80 kWh/m³, with an efficiency between 50 – 90 %. Therefore, increasing the TTES capacity implies a considerable investment cost decrease while significantly increasing the thermal storage capacity, thus providing a considerable increase on thermal energy (and cost) savings.

For that reason, the next section will provide some recommendations and/or improvement proposals in order to reduce the CHESSE SETUP system's investment, thus lowering expected payback and increasing financial profitability indicators so that both the client and the ESCO can take profit of the CHESSE SETUP system deployment. Other proposals will be considered such as increasing profitability margins of the services offered by the ESCO (P₂, P₃ and P₄) or modifying business plan simulation variables to find the most suitable financial scenario, taking into account economical perspective issues and other financial information given by the banks and other creditor entities.

10.2.4. Improvement proposals

As stated previously, the main issue detected for this demonstration scenario has been the high budget allocated to architecture works and TTES implementation. In that case, different proposals have been considered to mitigate the effects of the actual low VPN and IRR (as well as the high payback):

- Increase PV-T and STES system performance

Following the previous statements on Deliverable 2.1 and Deliverable 2.2, when reaching water tank volumes of 4,000 – 5,000 m³, the average investment cost per m³ water equivalent is reduced to 150 – 200 €/m³. Adding some more hybrid PV-T panels accordingly:

- The PV-T panels budget line is increased;
- The STES budget line is significantly reduced;
- The electricity and thermal savings are significantly higher, thus imply a significant decrease on energy costs;

The key for a balanced thermal energy storage system is the match between costs of energy production and energy storage with the maximum energy and cost savings through an optimized solution integrating a controlled operation and maintenance action. A seasonal thermal energy storage should be sized in order to be able to store all energy excess during high irradiation seasons (mainly summer but in some Mediterranean climates it can include some spring and autumn months). When integrating hybrid PV-T panels, STES will have low output temperatures thus low storage temperatures. If a heat exchanger must be put in place between PV-T production and STES, lower temperatures of storage will be accomplished, so STES will have low energy density no matter how large the storage volume is.

When trying to improve the PV-T performance, inlet panels temperature has to be lowered as much as possible. For this reason, STES is recommended to be well stratified: the temperature stratification is carried out automatically as hot water is less dense and therefore rises over water at less temperature. To prevent any mixing of the layers, a stratification device can be installed for charging in accordance with its temperature; therefore, stratification enhances the overall system's performance. In any case, a well-insulated system (not only on the STES but also on the building's facilities, piping connections and PV-T production lines) will lower the thermal losses, so that's why those systems must be specifically designed to integrate effective insulation layers to reduce as much as possible those thermal losses.

Moving on, when talking to the specific case of Sant Cugat's Sports Centre, the curve between investment costs and energy cost savings should cross so that there is a matched correlation allowing cost savings to be higher than investment costs. As this work might lead to another entire project demonstration case, this section will provide the general solutions that might increase NPV and IRR, so that the solution is financially profitable but would need to be demonstrated via new pilot sites and a new

deployment of the CHESS SETUP system, which has already been proved to be efficient. The many ways to increase the IRR are:

- **Reduce investment costs:** although it has not a significant impact on the IRR, its calculation mainly depends on the cash flow of each period which is completely linked to the P₄ financial investment quote to be paid by the client. Whenever this cash flow is lower and the project's duration is kept, the IRR will increase. Therefore, the investment will be more profitable, indicating that the return of the investment is sooner than before.

That is the best option for the client: whenever investment costs are reduced, annual P₄ quote will also decrease, therefore increasing financial profitability for the client as, at the same energy and cost savings provided by the new technology deployed, lower investment needs to be recovered. Therefore, the recovery time is significantly lower, which is also a positive factor for the ESCO as it will be easier to sell the P₄ annual quote to the client.

- **Increase profit margin over investment costs:** paradoxically, when increasing the profit margin over investment costs, the cash flow of each period is increased but the ESCO's P₄ cost remains the same. That means that if the ESCO is able to reduce material and manpower costs (thus improving profit margin over investment costs), the IRR will significantly increase; for example, in the business plan simulation on a 5-year contract, doubling the profit margin over investment costs results in a 10,52% IRR (for the initial 6,82%). That can be translated into the following: it may be worth to waste more time and resources into finding the most suitable material or manpower supplier (in terms of price and quality assurance) rather than finding the most efficient equipment or work crew, as their price may not be matching with the overall system to be deployed.

Following previous arguments on reducing investment costs, whenever the ESCO can increase its profit margin but in a lower proportion than the investment cost decrease, both ESCO and client could benefit from it. As obvious, when increasing profit margins over investment costs that implies increasing P₄ annual quote to the detriment of the client's interests. Therefore, the ESCO could increase profit margin over investment costs as long as it is able to reduce in the same or bigger proportion the investment costs. That being said, that proposal highly depends on the cost proportion over the rest of services: whenever the P₄ annual quote represents a high percentage of energy service package provided, increasing the margin profit will result in a significant increase of overall project's NPV and IRR but if P₄ annual quote represents a low percentage of all energy service package provided, the impact will be significantly lower. That depends on each and every project, as different variables do integrate the algorithm calculation of each energy services quote depending on the technology deployed, the contract's duration and other technical/economic indicators.

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- **Increase profit margin over maintenance and warranty services:** the same as abovementioned. Depending on the annual quote of maintenance (P₂) and full warranty (P₃) services compared to improvement works and renewal of installations (P₄), it might be better to increase profit margins over those services rather than looking for a P₄ reduction. That highly depends on the client: in our case, it is better to go for a P₄ reduction as it represents the main cost of the contract (since it offers the financing of a significant initial investment with small operation, maintenance and substitution costs when the contract is lower than the main equipment's' lifespan) rather than improving/increasing profit margins over P₂ and P₃.

The argumentation from previous sections still applies to P₂ and P₃ annual quotes: when increasing profit margins over maintenance and warranty services, the ESCO improve overall financial profitability to the detriment of the client's interests, as the new annual quote is increased. Therefore, and as stated before, that proposal highly depends on the cost proportion over the rest of services and has to be matched with the client's interests.

10.3. Corby Eco-Homes – Corby (England)

As a brief reminder, the Corby pilot case is meant to be a leading edge demonstration of eco-homes across a variety of house types. It is aimed to address many issues of new-build houses by ensuring a high quality building construction, focusing on developing energy efficiency and low carbon eco-homes. This Deliverable's section will focus on the implementation of the 3-bedroom townhouses (houses type A&B) as referred in Deliverables 3.7 and 5.1, which have a gross internal area (GIA) of 167.1 m². The CHESSE SETUP system deployment for those houses includes a combination of both hybrid PV-T and PV-only panels, a ground source heat pump and the Earth Energy Bank (EEB), the solar energy storage to be built under the houses.

10.3.1. Total cost of operation

As seen on previous pilot demonstration scenarios, we first need to know the exact cost of deploying the CHESSE SETUP system at the pilot focus area. Further detail of the all budget items is described in Appendix IV, which can be resumed as it follows:

Budget line	Cost
Photovoltaic installation (both PV-T and PV-only, including piping, wiring, converters, controllers, etc.)	9,477.00 €
Ground-Sourced Heat Pump	6,958.58€
Battery system	748.67 €
Earth Energy Bank	2,741.61 €
Monitoring and control system	573.29 €
Legalisation project	1,581.70 €
TOTAL MATERIAL EXECUTION BUDGET (MEB)	22,050.85 €
General costs (13% MEB)	2,866.61 €
Industrial profit (6% MEB)	1,323.05 €
TOTAL IMPLEMENTATION BUDGET (IB)	26,240.51 €
VALUE-ADDED TAX (21% IB)	5,510.51 €
TOTAL CHESSE SETUP IMPLEMENTATION BUDGET (VAT INCLUDED)	31,751.02 €

Table 16 Main budget items CHESSE SETUP's system deployment at Corby's Eco-Home – 3-bedroom townhouse (Source: COR)

For the business plan simulation, this report will be working (as it's usual) with the material execution budget as it only involves the requested material to be installed and the pilot site that can be attributed to the CHESSE SETUP system deployment. In that case, a total MEB of **22,050.85 € (P4)** is considered for each 3-bedroom townhouse. Considering that there will be fourteen 3-bedroom townhouses at Corby

demonstration pilot site, a total MEB of **308,711.90 €** is considered for the whole houses type A&B.

The following steps include the calculation of both maintenance (P₂) and full warranty (P₃) costs, including all services detailed in sections 6.2 and 6.3 of the current report, as well as what has been detailed previously in section 10.

In order to calculate the P₂ cost, the main variables affecting its calculation are:

- Personnel costs, including operational staff, operator/workman, etc.;
- Tools, clothing and other material costs including uniforms, protective and safety equipment, etc.;
- Vehicle and transportation costs;
- Communication and management systems (PDA, monitoring devices, etc.);
- Subcontracting costs for specific works;
- Additional specific contracting works not included before (such as legionella prevention tasks, sanitation, etc.).

Taking into account all personnel hours and concepts seen before, the total annual cost of maintaining the CHESSE SETUP system at Corby's Eco-Homes on a 3-bedroom townhouse is approximately **765.00€/year (does not change with the contract's duration)**.

In order to calculate the P₃ cost, the main variables affecting its calculation are:

- Personnel manpower cost;
- Reference year for amortisation;
- Algorithms of failure calculation of equipment involved;
- Range of equipment involved;
- Amount of equipment involved;
- Lifespan of equipment involved.

Taking into account all equipment and concepts seen before, the total annual cost of a full warranty service for the CHESSE SETUP system at Corby's Eco-Homes on a 3-bedroom townhouse ranges between **184.00€/year and 260.00 €/year (5-year to 10-year EPC)**.

10.3.2. Energy savings

Once seen the total improvement works/installation renewal costs (P₄), as well as maintenance (P₂) and full warranty (P₃) costs, it's time to check the main results of the CHESSE SETUP system's energy retrofit. This time it will not be correct to strictly define it as an energy management (P₁) service and associated cost, as this term refers to all energy management needed for the correct operation of the installation contract, such as the energy management supply (fuel and electricity), the quality, quantity, control operation and supply guarantees. Whenever this is part of the contract, the ESCO is responsible to provide the client a set of agreed services (such as

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heating, lighting, etc.), even taking responsibility of the installation's energy purchase in order to ensure the client an immediate save compared with the actual energetic cost. As this is not a P1 service, this report will only focus on the energy savings data coming from the monitoring system compared to the baseline energy demand and consumption from the building. That information is shown at the following table, which summarizes the main building's energy consumption, costs and emissions.

BASELINE FOR HOUSE TYPES A&B (3-BEDROOM TOWNHOUSE)								
	Boiler (kWh)	Natural Gas Costs (€)	Emissions (kgCO ₂)	Power demand (kWh)	Energy Costs (€)	Emissions (kgCO ₂)	Total Costs (€)	Total Emissions (kgCO ₂)
January	852.05	45.48	156.78	284.33	59.61	72.68	105.09	229.45
February	822.61	43.91	151.36	284.33	59.61	72.68	103.51	224.03
March	674.10	35.98	124.03	284.33	59.61	72.68	95.59	196.71
April	645.97	34.48	118.86	284.33	59.61	72.68	94.09	191.53
May	515.33	27.51	94.82	284.33	59.61	72.68	87.11	167.50
June	387.45	20.68	71.29	284.33	59.61	72.68	80.29	143.97
July	289.08	15.43	53.19	284.33	59.61	72.68	75.04	125.87
August	336.51	17.96	61.92	284.33	59.61	72.68	77.57	134.59
September	395.69	21.12	72.81	284.33	59.61	72.68	80.73	145.48
October	547.76	29.24	100.79	284.33	59.61	72.68	88.84	173.46
November	668.26	35.67	122.96	284.33	59.61	72.68	95.28	195.64
December	786.11	41.96	144.64	284.33	59.61	72.68	101.57	217.32
TOTAL	6,920.92	369.42	1,273.45	3,412.00	715.27	872.11	1,084.69	2,145.56

Table 17 Energy consumption of a house the same type as Corby's Eco-Home – 3-bedroom townhouse
(Source: BCN and COR)

10.3.2.1. Electricity savings

As stated previously, and due to the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic situation, the CHESSE SETUP's system performance is not reliable from March 2020 and so on, with many other issues arising during the baseline and validation period of data collection. For that, BCN has performed a deep analysis on relevant data coming from the monitoring & control system deployed by WAT: for so, the rest of the year's system performance has been forecasted taking into account the geographical demonstration site location, solar irradiation, energy bills and expected system performance under standard climatological conditions of each season.

As a result, a total amount of **4,269.32 kWh_e** as primary electricity energy savings has been estimated to come from PV panels' energy production. That being said, the overall electricity consumption is increased as the new GSHP installed consumes about 2,045.38 kWh_e, increasing overall electricity consumption from 3,412.00 kWh_e to 5,457.38 kWh_e. Therefore, the new electricity consumption from the grid when deploying the CHESSE SETUP's system proposal at Corby's 3-bedroom townhouse is 1,188.06 kWh_e.

CHESSE SETUP SYSTEM PERFORMANCE FOR HOUSE TYPES A&B (3-BEDROOM TOWNHOUSE)				
	PV (kWh)	Power demand (kWh)	Others (kWh)	HP (kWh)
January	126.25	578.34	284.33	294.00
February	199.45	571.79	284.33	287.46
March	350.58	494.61	284.33	210.27
April	464.03	470.63	284.33	186.30
May	561.51	419.10	284.33	134.77
June	575.39	377.37	284.33	93.03
July	580.45	349.88	284.33	65.55
August	510.20	360.20	284.33	75.87
September	383.15	378.42	284.33	94.09
October	260.58	427.42	284.33	143.09
November	143.53	484.28	284.33	199.94
December	114.19	545.34	284.33	261.01
TOTAL	4,269.32	5,457.38	3,412.00	2,045.38

Table 18 CHESSE SETUP's electrical energy generation and consumption of a house the same type as Corby's Eco-Home – 3-bedroom townhouse (Source: BCN and COR)

10.3.2.2. Thermal savings

In the same path, a total amount of **4,228.75 kWh_{PCI}** as primary thermal energy savings has been estimated, combining thermal generation coming from hybrid PV-T panels and sensible heat storage (SHS) performed at the EEB in the form of a borehole matrix under the 3-bedroom townhouse. As stated mainly in Deliverable 2.2, Deliverable 3.7 and Deliverable 5.1, the surplus thermal energy coming from hybrid PV-T panels is also used to heat a heat transfer fluid that is used to store thermal energy. That fluid is pumped to underground pipes in the overall EEB system; the heat transferred to these pipes underneath within the footing of the building warm the surrounding earth. The stored heat is then withdrawn from the EEB to its end-use via the ground source heat pump, which raises the temperature to a level that suits for its use as space heating or DHW. The panels on the roof perform both the function of electrical and thermal energy generation; the thermal energy is mainly produced during the summer months but the main heat use is strongly focused on winter. To overcome this issue, thermal energy generated in the summer is meant to be transferred into the EEB located under the footings of the building and stored for its use whenever it is needed during the winter.

CHESSE SETUP SYSTEM PERFORMANCE FOR HOUSE TYPES A&B (3-BEDROOM TOWNHOUSE)				
	PV- Thermal (kWh)	HP (kWh)	Thermal Output (kWh)	COP
January	440.46	294.00	766.84	2.61
February	456.71	287.46	740.34	2.58
March	515.85	210.27	606.69	2.89
April	483.66	186.30	581.38	3.12
May	463.66	134.77	463.80	3.44
June	379.25	93.03	348.71	3.75
July	306.09	65.55	260.17	3.97
August	273.49	75.87	302.86	3.99
September	221.71	94.09	356.12	3.78
October	216.44	143.09	492.99	3.45
November	182.34	199.94	601.43	3.01
December	289.09	261.01	707.50	2.71
TOTAL	4,228.75	2,045.38	6,228.83	3.05 (Average)

Table 19 CHESSE SETUP's thermal energy generation, consumption and COP of a house the same type as Corby's Eco-Home – 3-bedroom townhouse (Source: Deliverable 3.7 and Deliverable 5.1)

Therefore, we move from a baseline situation with a total amount of 6,920.92 kWh_{PCI} as natural gas consumption in a regular boiler to a new situation where we rely on **4,228.75 kWh_{PCI}** as estimated primary thermal energy savings (combining thermal generation coming from hybrid PV-T panels and sensible heat storage (SHS) performed at the EEB in the form of a borehole matrix under the 3-bedroom townhouse); the rest comes from the GSHP performance, which as seen previously translates to an electricity consumption increase. Although initial simulations estimated an GSHP performance (COP) around 3.84, the real data from the monitoring and control systems show COPs around 3.00, a bit lower than expected. Anyways, and as stated on the Commission Decision of 1 March 2013, establishing the guidelines for Member States on calculating renewable energy from heat pumps from different heat pump technologies pursuant to Article 5 of Directive 2009/28/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council, electrically driven heat pumps can be considered as renewably sourced whenever their SPF (referred to net active seasonal average efficiency (SCOP_{net}) for electrically driven heat pumps) is higher than 2.50.

Therefore, although both simulations and real data coming from the last month's CHESSE SETUP system performance show a lower COP than was initially expected, it can still be considered as renewably sourced heat pumps as the average measured and simulated COP goes around 3.00 – 3.05.

10.3.3. Business plan simulation

After all variables have been defined, it is the time to perform a business plan simulation under many different perspectives, in order to analyse the feasibility and profitability of the CHESSE SETUP system deployment at Corby's 3-bedroom townhouses. The main variables involved in the simulation are:

- **Total investment cost (previously referred as MEB):** 22,050.85 €;
- **Annual maintenance (P2) and full warranty (P3) costs:** 765.00 €/year and between 184.00 €/year and 260.00 €/year (5-year to 10-year EPC).
- **Duration of the contract:** 5 years/ 8 years/ 10 years;
- **Amortisation:** the same as the duration of the contract;
- **Interest rate for the total investment cost:** 5%;
- **Annual CPI increase:** 1.45%
- **Profit margin of the ESCO on total investment cost:** 10% (therefore, the installation is sold to the client for 24,255.94 €);
- **Client's payment schedule:** up to 2 months' maximum;

As the contract's duration is not fixed and depends on the client's needs and the ESCO's perspective on the operation and maintenance works of the technical configuration of the system, a simulation of an 8-year contract and a 10-year contract has been also conducted as they are also common contract durations on these kind of projects. As it's known, EPCs typically last from 2 to 20 years depending on the contract's conditions or equipment involved, but mainly on the customer's preference and access to capital (therefore the capital and technical risks to secure the finance for the project and its optimal execution and further operation). In those cases:

- **Annual maintenance (P2) and full warranty (P3) costs for an 8-year contract:** 765.00 €/year (no changes) and 233.00 €/year respectively;
- **Annual maintenance (P2) and full warranty (P3) costs for a 10-year contract:** 3,818.00 €/year (no changes) and 260.00 €/year respectively;
- **Duration of the contract:** 8 years and 10 years respectively;
- **Amortisation:** the same as the duration of the contract, 8 years and 10 years respectively;
- **The remaining variables involved in the business plan simulation are the same.**

Last but not least, those simulations have been performed under simulated and estimated data coming from different partners and other Deliverables of the CHESSE SETUP's project; therefore, VLC exposes that those business plan simulations may not correspond with the real system performance under a complete full operating cycle (at least one year), as the reporting period has not lasted a complete year.

*D6.1 Business models analysis
for the case studies*

Business plan simulation (5-year contract)		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Final sales (P2+P3+P4)		6,552	7,342	7,367	7,393	7,420	
Total costs (P2+P3+Structure cost)		1,297	1,358	1,373	1,388	1,404	
EBITDA		5,255	5,984	5,995	6,006	6,017	
	Amortisation	-4,410	-4,410	-4,410	-4,410	-4,410	
EBIT		844	1,574	1,585	1,595	1,606	
EBT (No financial costs considered)		844	1,574	1,585	1,595	1,606	
	Tax base	844	1,574	1,585	1,595	1,606	
Corporate income tax (25%)		211	394	396	399	402	
Net benefits		633	1,181	1,188	1,197	1,205	
Client payments		5,475	7,212	7,363	7,389	7,416	1,220
Supplier payments		1,191	1,353	1,371	1,387	1,402	115
ETE		4,284	5,859	5,992	6,003	6,014	1,104
Cash Flow		-17,978	5,466	5,596	5,604	5,612	1,104
Project TIR		10.84%					
Project NPV		1,895.29 €					

Table 20 Business plan simulation at Corby's Eco-Home – 3-bedroom townhouse for a 5-year EPC under abovementioned conditions

*D6.1 Business models analysis
for the case studies*

Business plan simulation (8-year contract)		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028
Final sales (P2+P3+P4)		4,751	5,542	5,568	5,595	5,622	5,649	5,677	5,706	
Total costs (P2+P3+Structure cost)		1,236	1,297	1,312	1,328	1,345	1,361	1,378	1,395	
EBITDA		3,515	4,245	4,256	4,266	4,277	4,288	4,299	4,311	
	Amortisation	-2,756	-2,756	-2,756	-2,756	-2,756	-2,756	-2,756	-2,756	-2,756
EBIT		759	1,489	1,499	1,510	1,521	1,532	1,543	1,554	
EBT (No financial costs considered)		759	1,489	1,499	1,510	1,521	1,532	1,543	1,554	
	Tax base	759	1,489	1,499	1,510	1,521	1,532	1,543	1,554	
Corporate income tax (25%)		190	372	375	377	380	383	386	389	
Net benefits		569	1,117	1,124	1,132	1,141	1,149	1,157	1,166	
Client payments		3,970	5,412	5,564	5,590	5,618	5,644	5,672	5,701	938
Supplier payments		1,134	1,292	1,311	1,327	1,344	1,359	1,376	1,394	115
ETE		2,836	4,120	4,253	4,263	4,274	4,285	4,296	4,308	823
Cash Flow		-19,405	3,748	3,878	3,886	3,894	3,902	3,910	3,919	823
Project TIR		9.71%								
Project NPV		2,324.11 €								
Table 21 Business plan simulation at Corby's Eco-Home – 3-bedroom townhouse for an 8-year EPC under abovementioned conditions										

**D6.1 Business models analysis
for the case studies**

Business plan simulation (10-year contract)		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
Final sales (P2+P3+P4)		4,167	4,958	4,985	5,012	5,040	5,066	5,095	5,125	5,154	5,185	
Total costs (P2+P3+Structure cost)		1,227	1,288	1,304	1,321	1,338	1,354	1,371	1,389	1,407	1,425	
EBITDA												
	Amortisation	-2,205	-2,205	-2,205	-2,205	-2,205	-2,205	-2,205	-2,205	-2,205	-2,205	
EBIT		735	1,465	1,475	1,486	1,497	1,507	1,519	1,530	1,542	1,554	
EBT (No financial costs considered)		735	1,465	1,475	1,486	1,497	1,507	1,519	1,530	1,542	1,554	
	Tax base	735	1,465	1,475	1,486	1,497	1,507	1,519	1,530	1,542	1,554	
Corporate income tax (25%)		184	366	369	371	374	377	380	383	386	389	
Net benefits		551	1,098	1,106	1,114	1,123	1,131	1,139	1,148	1,157	1,166	
Client payments		3,482	4,828	4,980	5,007	5,035	5,062	5,091	5,120	5,150	5,180	852
Supplier payments		1,126	1,283	1,303	1,319	1,336	1,353	1,370	1,388	1,406	1,424	117
ETE		2,356	3,545	3,677	3,688	3,699	3,709	3,721	3,732	3,744	3,756	735
Cash Flow		-19,879	3,179	3,308	3,316	3,325	3,333	3,341	3,350	3,358	3,367	735
Project TIR		9.33%										
Project NPV		2,561,24 €										

Table 22 Business plan simulation at Corby's Eco-Home – 3-bedroom townhouse for a 10-year EPC under abovementioned conditions

ANUAL COMPARISON CORBY ECO-HOME (3-BEDROOM TOWNHOUSE)

	Actual status (Baseline)	EPC Proposal 5 years		EPC Proposal 8 years		EPC Proposal 10 years	
		Year 5	Year 6	Year 8	Year 9	Year 10	Year 11
Total electricity consumed (kWh_e)	3.412,0	5.457,4	5.457,4	5.457,4	5.457,4	5.457,4	5.457,4
Electricity from the grid (kWh _e)	3.412,0	1.188,1	1.188,1	1.188,1	1.188,1	1.188,1	1.188,1
Self-consumed electricity (kWh _e)	0,0	4.269,3	4.269,3	4.269,3	4.269,3	4.269,3	4.269,3
Total electricity cost (€/kWh_e)	715 €	249 €	249 €	249 €	249 €	249 €	249 €
Total natural gas consumed (kWh_{PCI})							
Natural gas from the grid (kWh _{PCI})	6.920,9	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
Total natural gas cost (€/kWh_{PCI})	369 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
P1 TOTAL ENERGY COST	1.085 €	249 €	249 €	249 €	249 €	249 €	249 €
		-836 €	-836 €	-836 €	-836 €	-836 €	-836 €
P2 TOTAL MAINTENANCE COST	- €	765 €	- €	765 €	- €	765 €	- €
P3 TOTAL FULL WARRANTY COST	- €	184 €	- €	233 €	- €	260 €	- €
Total investment		22.051 €		22.051 €		22.051 €	
Interest tax		5,00%		5,00%		5,00%	
P4 TOTAL INSTALLATION FINANCING COST	- €	5.603 €	- €	3.753 €	- €	3.141 €	- €
Energy cost Eco-Home (3-bedroom townhouse)		249 €	249 €	249 €	249 €	249 €	249 €
Energy Services Contract proposal cost (P2 - P3 - P4)		6.552 €	- €	4.751 €	- €	3.401 €	- €
ANUAL COST P1 - P2 - P3 - P4 (€/year)	1.085 €	6.801 €	249 €	5.000 €	249 €	4.416 €	249 €
		526,98%	-77,04%	360,96%	-77,04%	307,10%	-77,04%
		- 5.716 €	836 €	- 3.915 €	836 €	- 3.331 €	836 €
		Savings 9,21 tn CO2/year		Savings 14,74 tn CO2/year		Savings 18,42 tn CO2/year	

Figure 4o Annual comparison between actual energy costs and services breakdown and ESCO's proposals breakdown on 5-year/8-year/10-year EPC's for Corby's Eco-Home – 3-bedroom townhouse

D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies

All business plan simulations and the annual comparison between actual energy costs and services breakdown and future scenarios under a 5-year/8-year/10-year energy performance contracts (EPC's) represent the overall business plan simulation under which an ESCO conducts an assessment on the financial feasibility and profitability of these kind of contracts. Therefore, many reasoning factors must be underlined to define if the ESCO wants to run this contract under the variables and conditions mentioned before:

- In an Energy Performance Contract – Guaranteed Savings model (EPC GS), the ESCO guarantees a certain savings on the client's energy bill and assumes all technical risk. The client obtains a bank loan or uses its own resources to pay contractually determined fees to the ESCO (P₄) and to the bank and keeps the difference.
- In an Energy Performance Contract – Shared Savings model (EPC SS), the ESCO can provide financing (therefore assuming both technical and credit risks for the client), as well as project development and implementation costs. That can be valuable for the client as it avoids the need for upfront capital costs, with ongoing payments to the ESCO based on savings obtained.

Figure 4.1 Energy Performance Contract – Guaranteed Savings model (EPC GS) (Source: [25])

Figure 4.2 Energy Performance Contract – Shared Savings model (EPC SS) (Source: [25])

- Therefore, depending on the client's financial capacity, the chosen EPC changes the financial status but either if it's a guaranteed savings model or a shared savings model, the client relies on the ESCO to assume all technical risks as it provides all project development and implementation costs. The client can rely on the ESCO to assume all financial risks via contractual arrangement (P₄), normally with an interest rate lower than the bank's but again assuming all technical risk.
- The Net Present Value (NPV) represents one of the best financial profitability indicators; it is a useful tool to determine whether a project or investment will

result in a net profit or a loss. Whenever the NPV is positive, the project is profitable; in all business plan simulations for the 3 reference cases, the NPV is positive, with its value increasing when the project's duration is longer (21,164.77 € for the 5-year contract, 23,141.12 € for the 8-year contract and 23,898.47 € for the 10-year contract). The simulations have been made considering a discount rate of 6,5% under the data published by the Bank of England [28].

- The Internal Rate of Return (IRR) is another of the best financial profitability indicators; it is defined as the rate of return that sets the NPV of all cash flows for the investment equal to zero, meaning that it is the discount rate at which the NPV of the future cash flows is equal to the initial investment. Whenever the IRR is positive, the project is profitable; in all business plan simulations for the 3 reference cases, the IRR is positive, with its value decreasing when the project's duration is longer (10.84% for the 5-year contract, 9.71% for the 8-year contract and 9.33% for the 10-year contract).
- The IRR is a relative profitability indicator of the project, but not an absolute profitability indicator. When comparing different internal rates of return of two projects, the possible difference over their size is not considered (neither do other external factors as inflation, cost of capital or various financial risks). A project with a huge investment and a low IRR can have a bigger NPV than a lower investment project with a higher IRR; in conclusion, IRR cannot be considered as an alternative to NPV but as a complementary information while comparing different project's profitability. The reference case shows very low IRR's, in some cases even than the discount rate of the reference country (Spain), which might be an indicator of a remarkable financial risk.
- In this reference case, the total material execution budget is 22,050.85 € per Corby's Eco-Home – 3-bedroom townhouse, a relatively small investment that needs to be amortised through an efficient operation of the system and based on overall energy (and cost) savings. In this reference case, approximately 836.00 €/year can be saved by applying the CHESS SETUP system, which can be translated to a payback of 26.37 years. Considering a 5-year contract, the client would have to assume an annual installation financing cost (P₄) of 5,603 €/year to finance the installation, which decreases to 3,753 €/year for an 8-year contract and to 3,141 €/year for a 10-year contract.
- That means that, in a 5-year contract, although from the beginning the client is already saving nearly 836.00 €/year, its overall energy services and energy consumption costs increase by 526.98% (5-year contract), by 360.96% (8-year contract) or, in the best scenario, by 307.10% (10-year contract). Assuming the fact that the return of initial investment is 26.37 years and considering that the lifespan of most of the essential equipment rounds between 20 – 30 years, that investment would not be profitable for the client (but it is for the ESCO, as its implication will last no longer than 10 years and it will obtain economic profit from all work and services performed).

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- That does not mean the system is not efficient: it indeed is, as the monitoring and control systems showed that, most of the time the CHESSE SETUP system has been working, it operated under expected performance parameters, thus providing a considerable amount of electrical (**4,269.32 kWh_e**) and thermal (**4,228.75 kWh_{th}**) energy savings, which translates to 836 €/year of cost savings for each 3-bedroom townhouse at Corby.
- Following that path, it is essential to provide an annual maintenance (P2) and full warranty (P3) service, in order to ensure the correct operation, maintenance and equipment substitution whenever any problem arises. Those services include a monitoring and control service that also takes into account benchmarking with similar projects and real-time surveillance of the system's performance, enhancing installation's lifespan and energy efficiency.
- The main problem of this reference case is the high budget allocated to PV-T installation and the ground source heat pump. Right now PV-T panel cost is still very high, doubling or even triplicating regular PV panel cost. In Corby's demonstration pilot, PV-T and PV installation represents nearly 43% of total investment cost (also referred as MEB), therefore it represents the most important budget line and the one that needs to be reduced as much as possible. The EEB budget line represents only 12.43% of total investment cost, therefore the main problem here is the high thermal generation cost associated to PV-T panel installation; for so, improving its key component costs would also lead to a MEB reduction. Regarding the heat pump, the only recommendation is to bear in mind different heat pump suppliers' solutions that could be easily implemented in an existing building, and match them with building's thermal demand and other variables involved (especially climatological ones) so that the heat pump's COP is maximized, its performance is done under correct operational parameters and its lifespan is stretched as much as possible.

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- As its widely known, geothermal heat pumps (which is not the CHESSE SETUP system deployment at Corby but it is still quite similar regarding the heat pump performance) extract thermal energy from the ground on winter that is later on transferred inside the house, while in summer the heat is extracted from inside the house and transferred again to the ground. As seen on the following figure, which represents a heat pump performance in heat mode, the left graph shows the enthalpy increase of the refrigerant during the

compression phase, corresponding to the compressor work. If we are able to increase the evaporation temperature, thus the pressure (graph on the right), the compressor has to work less in order to achieve the same pressure (therefore, the same temperature) in the condenser; then the electrical work energy needed is lower, decreasing energy costs and increasing overall system's efficiency. In cooling mode, we can also achieve energy and cost savings by lowering the condenser's temperature.

Figure 43 Refrigeration cycle of a heat pump (Source: [29])

- As it was already stated in Lavola's Ecobuilding reference case, the work fluid's selection (in Corby's reference case, the fluid that is circulating through the buried heat exchanger in the form of boreholes) must be done under different criterion such as heat transfer characteristics (mainly thermal conductivity and viscosity), freezing point, pressure and pressure drop requirements due to friction, corrosiveness, toxicity and flammability, and obviously its cost.
- The same goes for the underground heat exchange configuration: depending on the installation or the working fluid path, different configurations might be chosen so that the heat transfer with the ground is minimised. Remember that our case is not a geothermal heat pump; the thermal energy generated from the PV-T panels is meant to be stored underground whenever there is an excess of it (especially during hot seasons) so that it can be used later on (mainly on cold seasons). In the reference case, and as stated in Deliverable 3.7 among others, considering Corby's climatology the CHESSE SETUP system deployment is meant to serve as it follows: during cold seasons, the heat pump

is meant to recover storage heat (which is typically between 8 – 14 °C) and use it to increase work fluid's temperature to each circuit's operational temperature (between 35 – 60 °C) for its end use.

For that reason, the next section will provide some recommendations and/or improvement proposals in order to reduce the CHESSETUP system's investment, thus lowering expected payback and increasing financial profitability indicators so that both the client and the ESCO can take profit of the CHESSETUP system deployment. Other proposals will be considered such as increasing profitability margins of the services offered by the ESCO (P₂, P₃ and P₄) or modifying business plan simulation variables to find the most suitable financial scenario, taking into account economical perspective issues and other financial information given by the banks and other creditor entities.

10.3.4. Improvement proposals

As stated previously, the main issue detected for this demonstration scenario has been the high budget allocated to PV-T installation and the ground source heat pump. In that case, different proposals have been considered to mitigate the effects of the actual low VPN and IRR (as well as the high payback):

- Increase heat pump performance

Following the previous statements, and knowing that the heat pump cost cannot be reduced as it's a fixed budget line given by the selected supplier, what can be done is improve the heat pump performance. As we must stick to weather conditions from each geographical area, and as stated in Deliverables 3.4 and 3.5 about the heat pump design, the performance of a heat pump depends on the temperature of the heat source, the heat sink, the working medium, the arrangement, the thermodynamic cycle conditions, the characteristics of the components of the controlling system, etc.

For so, the refrigerant selection has a direct impact on the overall cost and lifecycle of the system and should be considered as an improvement proposal in the heat pump design; as new regulations impose strict limitations to hydrofluorocarbons (HFC), hydro-fluoro-olefins (HFOs) and other types of refrigerants should be the next path in the research and development about heat pump technology as an alternative low global warming potential (GWP) working fluid. Considering both condenser and evaporator refrigerant temperatures, the overall thermodynamic cycle's performance can be increased, therefore reducing the amount of work (either in form of electrical or thermal energy) required to compress the refrigerant.

Current guides and standardised procedures to measure SPF do also consider a weight factor depending on the heat pump technology: the supplier usually offers a COP referred to a condensation temperature that might not be the operation temperature of the equipment/system. The technical justification is that the COP decrease according to the condensation temperature's increase does not depend on the energy

source (air, water or ground) but that temperature indeed has an impact on the heat pump performance: whenever the fluid's working temperature is lower, it will ease the refrigerant's condensation, therefore increasing COP and thermal power supplied by the heat pump. This weight factor is only applied to electrical-driven heat pumps.

zemA-voda	Low temperature 35°C				Medium temperature 55°C			
	performance**	SCOP	μs %	class	performance**	SCOP	μs %	class
AquaMaster Inverter								
AQ 22I	7 kW	4,61	177	A++(+)	6 kW	3,53	133	A++(+)
AQ 30I	11 kW	4,85	186	A++(+)	11 kW	3,78	143	A++(+)
AQ 45I	21 kW	4,80	184	A++(+)	19 kW	3,70	140	A++(+)
AQ 60I	33 kW	5,02	193	A++(+)	33 kW	3,97	151	A++(+)
AQ 90I	44 kW	4,87	187	A++(+)	43 kW	3,87	147	A++(+)

performance - at the design outdoor temperature of -10 °C. A ++ (+) - meets Class A +++ valid from r. 2019

Figure 44 MasterTherm heat pump efficiencies (Source: [30])

Moving on, when talking to the specific case of Corby's Eco-Home – 3-bedroom townhouse, the curve between investment costs and energy cost savings should cross so that there is matched correlation allowing cost savings to be higher than investment costs. As this work might lead to another entire project demonstration case, the following section will provide some general solutions that might increase NPV and IRR, so that the solution is financially profitable but would need to be demonstrated via new pilot sites and a new deployment of the CHESS SETUP system, which has already been proved to be efficient. The many ways to increase the IRR are:

- **Reduce investment costs:** although in the reference case it has not a significant impact on the IRR, its calculation mainly depends on the cash flow of each period which is totally linked to the P₄ financial investment quote to be paid by the client. Whenever this cash flow is lower and the project's duration is kept, the IRR will increase. Therefore, the investment will be more profitable, indicating that the return of the investment is sooner than before.

That is the best option for the client: whenever investment costs are reduced, annual P₄ quote will also decrease, therefore increasing financial profitability for the client as, at the same energy and cost savings provided by the new technology deployed, lower investment needs to be recovered. Therefore, the recovery time is significantly lower, which is also a positive factor for the ESCO as it will be easier to sell the P₄ annual quote to the client. In the reference case, if we achieve a total amount of 836 €/year of cost savings, we should be looking for investment costs lower than approximately 10,000 €, so that the payback is limited to 10 years' maximum. Therefore, the PV-T budget line must be decreased among with any other budget lines that allow any form of budget cut or adjustments.

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That being said, another possibility would be to slightly increase investment costs but, at the same time, highly increasing energy savings, covering all energy demand with the implementation of additional thermal energy generation. Considering the high price of PV-T systems, matching other thermal RES generation or thermal income (for example, geothermal energy) with a heat pump solution to increase energy savings would allow a slight increase on investment costs, as we might be able to cover all energy demand from each townhouse with RES. Therefore, we would be able to achieve a total amount of 1,085 €/year of cost savings (all energy costs). Therefore, the investment costs could be slightly increased so that the payback is limited to approximately 10 years' maximum.

- **Increase profit margin over investment costs:** paradoxically, when increasing the profit margin over investment costs, the cash flow of each period is increased but the ESCO's P₄ cost remains the same. That means that if the ESCO is able to reduce material and mankind costs (thus improving profit margin over investment costs), the IRR will significantly increase; for example, in the business plan simulation on a 5-year contract, doubling the profit margin over investment costs results in a 14.44% IRR (for the initial 10.84%). That can be translated into the following: it may be worth to waste more time and resources into finding the most suitable material or mankind supplier (in terms of price and quality assurance) rather than finding the most efficient equipment or work crew, as the manpower and/or equipment costs may not be matching with the overall system to be deployed.

Following previous arguments on reducing investment costs, whenever the ESCO can increase its profit margin but in a lower proportion than the investment cost decrease, both ESCO and client could benefit from it. As obvious, when increasing profit margins over investment costs that implies increasing P₄ annual quote to the detriment of the client's interests. Therefore, the ESCO could increase profit margin over investment costs as long as it is able to reduce in the same or bigger proportion the investment costs. That being said, that proposal highly depends on the cost proportion over the rest of services: whenever the P₄ annual quote represents a high percentage of energy service package provided, increasing the margin profit will result in a significant increase of overall project's NPV and IRR but if P₄ annual quote represents a low percentage of all energy service package provided, the impact will be significantly lower. That depends on each and every project, as different variables do integrate the algorithm calculation of each energy services quote depending on the technology deployed, the contract's duration and other technical/economic indicators.

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- **Increase profit margin over maintenance and warranty services:** the same as abovementioned. Depending on the annual quote of maintenance (P₂) and full warranty (P₃) services compared to improvement works and renewal of installations (P₄), it might be better to increase profit margins over those services rather than looking for a P₄ reduction. That highly depends on the client: in our case, it is better to go for a P₄ reduction as it represents the main cost of the contract (since it offers the financing of a significant initial investment with small operation, maintenance and substitution costs when the contract is lower than the main equipment's' lifespan) rather than improving/increasing profit margins over P₂ and P₃.

The argumentation from previous sections still applies to P₂ and P₃ annual quotes: when increasing profit margins over maintenance and warranty services, the ESCO improve overall financial profitability to the detriment of the client's interests, as the new annual quote is increased. Therefore, and as stated before, that proposal highly depends on the cost proportion over the rest of services and has to be matched with the client's interests.

11. Private partnership business model applied for the case studies

As seen from the previous section, and considering the different variables and parameters that affect the ESCO BM deployment, it becomes essential to deploy a different BM approach so that the client's investment, energy and O&M costs are financially profitable and in the shortest possible time. Right now, and considering a payback approach through the deployment of the proposed full ESCO BM (which already considers a PV production decay as well as the expected failure calculation of equipment involved knowing their lifespans):

- For Lavola's Ecobuilding, approximately 2,765 €/year as energy cost savings are acknowledged, while the reported payback for the CHESSE SETUP system deployment for this reference case is approximately 41.02 years.
- For Sant Cugat's Sports Centre, approximately 14,217 €/year as energy costs savings are acknowledged, while the reported payback for the CHESSE SETUP system deployment for this reference case is approximately 46.55 years.
- For a 3-bedroom Ecohome at Corby, approximately 836 €/year as energy cost savings, while the reported payback for the CHESSE SETUP system deployment for this reference case is approximately 26.37 years.

Some of the small equipment, accessories and/or components of the installations do have high lifespans such as valves (25 years), pipelines and traps (35 years), expansion vessels (25 years), electrical wiring and accessories (20 to 25 years), boilers and chillers (between 15 and 20 years), etc., while some other equipment lifespan is significantly lower (as it is the case of ESS and inverters, whose maximum lifespan is usually no more than 10 years). For that reason, the following section will provide a private partnership BM considering that the client relies on its own financial strength or a third-party financing to assume the initial investment costs. In the same path, the O&M will be undertaken either by an ESCO or another small maintenance operator. This section will also consider some other specific parameters, such as the inverter replacement under 5 – 6 years' lifespan conditions as the main low lifespan equipment. The baseline proposal on many of the buildings will be done under the estimation of actual technology providers' technical specifications of heating/cooling generation units (pressurized/atmospheric/electrical boilers, chillers, AHU/fan-coil/split units, etc.) considering that their lifespans stand between 10 and 20 years. In the same path, a lifespan of the overall PV installation is considered to be of 24 years, approximately the same lifespan in terms of overall STES systems (which in some cases can even last more as different literature and case studies have shown).

That being said, the following section will provide a private partnership BM approach so that the scope of the most feasible scenarios under the actual CHESSE SETUP

system deployment parameters is identified. In general terms, and as general remarks on the parameter definition of the simulations:

- VLC's experience concludes that investment costs can be curtailed up to 10 – 15 % through a public or private tender and procurement process for the selection of the contractor/tenderer that will be responsible for the installation. That's one of the main issues that the CHESSE SETUP project has faced during the deployment phase, mainly due to construction and/or civil works that were required in order to adapt the system to each pilot buildings' typologies;
- Also through VLC and other ESCOs'/technology suppliers'/research technology organisations' experience, the degradation of PV panels and therefore the reduction of the PV panels' electricity generation is about 0,5 – 1% per year; the upcoming simulations will consider an annual decay of the PV production of 0,8%;
- In order to maximize the financial viability/profitability of the CHESSE SETUP system deployment from the client's perspective, the following simulations will only consider normative O&M costs, that is, the P2 provision with the minimum cost to comply with local regulations in terms of O&M. No P3 and P4 provision will be considered for the private partnership BM;
- Several scenarios will be simulated under different conditions regarding the actual equipment that might be already deployed in the pilot sites and could be part of the CHESSE SETUP system deployment through adaptation/adjustment procedures. This will enhance the identification of the most suitable scenarios in which different costs might be avoided because the clients do already have some of that equipment already installed, such as tanks, heating/cooling generation units (boilers, heat pumps, chillers, etc.) and so on.

Many different scenarios will enhance the profitability of the CHESSE SETUP system, some of them as follows:

- First scenario: the client does already have a tank/storage facility that could be easily adapted as a STES (useable water tank formerly used for other purposes e.g. fire emergency, drinking water supply water systems, fuel storage, etc.) and also has a heating/cooling generation unit (boiler/HP/chiller, etc.) to satisfy the heating/cooling/DHW demand. Therefore, the client just needs to deploy the RES generation system;
- Second scenario: the client does not already have a tank/storage facility that could be easily adapted as a SHS but no need of extra construction/civil works is needed. In that case, the scenario is meant to consider the fact that there is room availability either inside the client's facilities (mainly modular/monolith tanks from different materials allocated in an accessible room) or outside (mainly modular/monolith tanks fully or partially buried in the ground such as TTES, ATES, BTES, GWTES or PTES) for the deployment of a STES. In this scenario it is also considered that the client has a heating/cooling generation unit (boiler/HP/chiller, etc.) and a heat exchange system to satisfy the

heating/cooling/DHW demand. Therefore, the client needs to deploy the RES generation system and the STES.

- **Third scenario:** the client does not already have a tank/storage facility that could be easily adapted as a SHS but no need of extra construction/civil works is needed. In that case, the scenario is meant to consider the fact that there is room availability either inside the client's facilities (mainly modular/monolith tanks from different materials allocated in an accessible room) or outside (mainly modular/monolith tanks fully or partially buried in the ground such as TTES, ATES, BTES, GWTES or PTES) for the deployment of a STES. This scenario will consider that the client needs to deploy the whole CHESS SETUP system – both RES generation, STES and heat exchange systems as well as a heating/cooling generation unit (boiler/HP/chiller, etc.).
- **Fourth scenario:** The client can rely upon different grants/subsidies in terms of energy efficiency, RES generation or increased performance funding opportunities either locally, at country level or even at a European level. Therefore, this scenario will consider that the client needs to deploy the whole CHESS SETUP system but it can rely on a 50% funding of all initial investment costs (further replacement costs are assumed by the client).

11.1. Lavola's headquarters – Manlleu (Spain)

As a brief reminder, the Ecobuilding (Lavola's headquarters) pilot site has been finally designed not to integrate any TES; its technical solution is based on integrating PV panels in combination with an air-source heat pump (ASHP). Given the reduced size of the TES that could be installed in previous CHESS SETUP system configuration's analysis, the final configuration is taking advantage of the thermal inertia of the building's slab upper layer of mortar where the radiant heating floor is already installed as a small form of thermal storage system.

In that case, different scenarios have been simulated:

- **Baseline scenario:** this scenario is meant to offer the initial status of the HVAC system, where the heating demand is met with a boiler (Aldingas R-505, 168kW nominal power and an approximate cost of 10,000€), the cooling demand is met with an air-cooled liquid chiller (Carrier Eurovent 30RA, 118kW nominal power and an approximate cost of 20,000€) and the DHW demand is met with the use of thermal solar panels, a double-chamber tank of 300L and a gas-condensing boiler (Viessman Vitopend 100 WHE, 24 kW nominal power and an approximate cost of 1,500€). In that case:
 - **Total investment cost (previously referred as MEB):** 31,500 €;
 - **Initial annual energy costs:** 15,196 €/year;
 - **Initial annual maintenance costs:** 1,100 €/year;
 - **Annual CPI increase:** 1.45%.

- Scenario 1 – PV-only: this scenario is meant to offer a comparison between the baseline scenario and another one where we only include the PV system. Therefore, the initial costs will only be the ones related to the PV system implementation (including the metal structure legalization project, the galvanized layer sheet and the electrical wiring). In that case:
 - **Total investment cost (previously referred as MEB)**: 47,355€ (not including the perimeter railing system plus concrete slab for the HP);
 - **Initial annual energy costs**: 13,462 €/year;
 - **Initial annual maintenance costs**: 1,400 €/year;
 - **Annual CPI increase**: 1.45%.
- Scenario 2 – PV + HP: this scenario is the actual one being deployed, where the initial chiller has been removed and we rely on the PV system (and also the existing solar thermal panels, which had to be redistributed in the building's deck) as well as the new water-to-water HP (Carrier 30RQS-060B, 58kW nominal cooling power and 61.2kW heating power and an approximate cost of 29,350 €). Note that this scenario also includes the perimeter railing system and concrete slab for the new HP (approximate cost of 4,140 €) and the monitoring & control system that will be deployed (an approximate cost of 32,580 €). In that case:
 - **Total investment cost (previously referred as MEB)**: 113,426 €;
 - **Initial annual energy costs**: 12,625 €/year;
 - **Initial annual maintenance costs**: 1,813 €/year;
 - **Annual CPI increase**: 1.45%.
- Scenario 3 – PV + HP with a 50% grant: this scenario is the actual one being deployed but considering a 50% grant either taking advantage of local, country or European level funding trends, as it is the case of the current CHESS SETUP project. In that case:
 - **Total investment cost (previously referred as MEB)**: 56,713 €;
 - **Initial annual energy costs**: 12,625 €/year;
 - **Initial annual maintenance costs**: 1,813€/year;
 - **Annual CPI increase**: 1.45%.

The main difference between the ESCO BM is that, in this case, the client directly relies on its own financial strength to assume the initial investment (or either through a bank load with pre-fixed payment conditions). In the same path, the maintenance costs can be performed either by an ESCO or just a small maintenance operator, therefore reducing initial P2 service costs. Note also that those simulations now do have to include a PV degradation parameter aside, as the initial ESCO P3 service was the one that included a fixed fee related to any sudden failure/need of replacing some of the equipment involved in the overall CHESS SETUP system as well as equipment/material degradation. As seen before, and considering it as a multiplying factor that we will simplify and make it lineal on time, the annual PV production decrease has been considered to be of 0,8%. Note also that this only affects the

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amount of energy produced by the PV system but that the CPI increase affects all annual energy cost.

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Year	Initial Invest.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	
BASELINE SCENARIO																	
Equipment (€)	31.500 €																31.500 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)		10.126 €	10.273 €	10.423 €	10.577 €	10.736 €	10.886 €	11.050 €	11.215 €	11.384 €	11.554 €	11.728 €	11.904 €	12.082 €	12.263 €	12.447 €	
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)		5.069 €	5.142 €	5.218 €	5.295 €	5.374 €	5.450 €	5.531 €	5.614 €	5.699 €	5.784 €	5.871 €	5.959 €	6.048 €	6.139 €	6.231 €	
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)		1.100 €	1.116 €	1.132 €	1.149 €	1.166 €	1.183 €	1.200 €	1.218 €	1.237 €	1.255 €	1.274 €	1.293 €	1.312 €	1.332 €	1.352 €	
TOTAL	31.500 €	47.796 €	64.327 €	81.100 €	98.121 €	115.398 €	132.917 €	150.698 €	168.746 €	187.065 €	205.659 €	224.532 €	243.687 €	263.130 €	282.865 €	334.396 €	

Year	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	
BASELINE SCENARIO																
Equipment (€)																31.500 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)	12.634 €	12.824 €	13.016 €	13.211 €	13.409 €	13.611 €	13.815 €	14.022 €	14.232 €	14.446 €	14.662 €	14.882 €	15.106 €	15.332 €	15.562 €	
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)	6.325 €	6.419 €	6.516 €	6.613 €	6.713 €	6.813 €	6.916 €	7.019 €	7.125 €	7.231 €	7.340 €	7.450 €	7.562 €	7.675 €	7.790 €	
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)	1.372 €	1.393 €	1.414 €	1.435 €	1.457 €	1.478 €	1.501 €	1.523 €	1.546 €	1.569 €	1.593 €	1.617 €	1.641 €	1.665 €	1.690 €	
TOTAL	354.727 €	375.363 €	396.308 €	417.568 €	439.147 €	461.049 €	483.280 €	505.845 €	528.748 €	551.994 €	575.589 €	599.538 €	623.846 €	648.519 €	705.062 €	

Table 23 Financial feasibility baseline scenario within 30 years for Lavola pilot

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PV degradation	0,00%	0,80%	1,60%	2,40%	3,20%	4,00%	4,80%	5,60%	6,40%	7,20%	8,00%	8,80%	9,60%	10,40%	11,20%	12,00%
Year	Initial Invest.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
SCENARIO 1: PV ONLY																
Equipment (€)	47.355 €					2.232 €					2.232 €					2.232 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)		8.392 €	8.409 €	8.426 €	8.442 €	8.449 €	8.473 €	8.488 €	8.503 €	8.518 €	8.533 €	8.549 €	8.564 €	8.579 €	8.594 €	8.609 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)		5.069 €	5.142 €	5.218 €	5.295 €	5.374 €	5.450 €	5.531 €	5.614 €	5.699 €	5.784 €	5.871 €	5.959 €	6.048 €	6.139 €	6.231 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)		1.400 €	1.420 €	1.441 €	1.462 €	1.484 €	1.505 €	1.528 €	1.551 €	1.574 €	1.597 €	1.621 €	1.646 €	1.670 €	1.695 €	1.721 €
TOTAL	47.355 €	62.217 €	77.189 €	92.273 €	107.473 €	125.012 €	140.440 €	155.987 €	171.655 €	187.446 €	205.592 €	221.633 €	237.802 €	254.099 €	270.528 €	289.321 €
Year		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
SAVINGS		-14.421 €	-12.862 €	-11.173 €	-9.352 €	-9.614 €	-7.523 €	-5.289 €	-2.909 €	-380 €	67 €	2.898 €	5.886 €	9.031 €	12.337 €	45.075 €

PV degradation	12,80%	13,60%	14,40%	15,20%	16,00%	16,80%	17,60%	18,40%	0,00%	0,80%	1,60%	2,40%	3,20%	4,00%	4,80%
Year	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
SCENARIO 1: PV ONLY															
Equipment (€)					2.232 €				32.666 €						2.232 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)	8.624 €	8.640 €	8.655 €	8.670 €	8.685 €	8.700 €	8.716 €	8.731 €	8.382 €	8.397 €	8.412 €	8.427 €	8.442 €	8.458 €	8.473 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)	6.325 €	6.419 €	6.516 €	6.613 €	6.713 €	6.813 €	6.916 €	7.019 €	7.125 €	7.231 €	7.340 €	7.450 €	7.562 €	7.675 €	7.790 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)	1.747 €	1.773 €	1.799 €	1.826 €	1.854 €	1.882 €	1.910 €	1.939 €	1.968 €	1.997 €	2.027 €	2.058 €	2.088 €	2.120 €	2.151 €
TOTAL	306.016 €	322.848 €	339.819 €	356.928 €	376.412 €	393.807 €	411.348 €	429.037 €	479.176 €	496.802 €	514.581 €	532.516 €	550.608 €	571.092 €	589.507 €
Year	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
SAVINGS	48.710 €	52.514 €	56.490 €	60.640 €	62.735 €	67.242 €	71.932 €	76.808 €	49.571 €	55.192 €	61.008 €	67.022 €	73.238 €	77.427 €	115.555 €

Table 24 Financial feasibility scenario 1 (PV-only) within 30 years for Lavola pilot

D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies

PV degradation	0,00%	0,80%	1,60%	2,40%	3,20%	4,00%	4,80%	5,60%	6,40%	7,20%	8,00%	8,80%	9,60%	10,40%	11,20%	12,00%
Year	Initial Invest.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
SCENARIO 2: PV + HP																
Equipment (€)	113.426 €					2.232 €					2.232 €					2.232 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)		12.625 €	12.643 €	12.660 €	12.678 €	12.680 €	12.708 €	12.723 €	12.738 €	12.753 €	12.769 €	12.784 €	12.799 €	12.814 €	12.829 €	12.844 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)		0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)		1.813 €	1.839 €	1.866 €	1.894 €	1.922 €	1.949 €	1.978 €	2.008 €	2.038 €	2.069 €	2.100 €	2.131 €	2.163 €	2.196 €	2.229 €
TOTAL	113.426 €	127.864 €	142.346 €	156.872 €	171.443 €	188.277 €	202.934 €	217.636 €	232.382 €	247.173 €	264.242 €	279.126 €	294.056 €	309.033 €	324.058 €	341.363 €
Year		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
SAVINGS		-80.068 €	-78.019 €	-75.772 €	-73.322 €	-72.879 €	-70.018 €	-66.937 €	-63.635 €	-60.108 €	-58.583 €	-54.594 €	-50.369 €	-45.903 €	-41.193 €	-6.967 €

PV degradation	12,80%	13,60%	14,40%	15,20%	16,00%	16,80%	17,60%	18,40%	0,00%	0,80%	1,60%	2,40%	3,20%	4,00%	4,80%
Year	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
SCENARIO 2: PV + HP															
Equipment (€)					2.232 €				113.426 €						2.232 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)	12.860 €	12.875 €	12.890 €	12.905 €	12.920 €	12.936 €	12.951 €	12.966 €	12.617 €	12.632 €	12.647 €	12.662 €	12.678 €	12.693 €	12.708 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)	2.262 €	2.296 €	2.330 €	2.365 €	2.401 €	2.437 €	2.473 €	2.510 €	2.548 €	2.586 €	2.625 €	2.664 €	2.704 €	2.745 €	2.786 €
TOTAL	356.484 €	371.655 €	386.875 €	402.146 €	419.698 €	435.071 €	450.495 €	465.971 €	594.562 €	609.780 €	625.052 €	640.379 €	655.761 €	673.431 €	688.925 €
Year	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
SAVINGS	-1.757 €	3.708 €	9.433 €	15.423 €	19.449 €	25.979 €	32.786 €	39.874 €	-65.814 €	-57.786 €	-49.463 €	-40.841 €	-31.915 €	-24.911 €	16.138 €

Table 25 Financial feasibility scenario 2 (PV + HP) within 30 years for Lavola pilot

D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies

PV degradation	0,00%	0,80%	1,60%	2,40%	3,20%	4,00%	4,80%	5,60%	6,40%	7,20%	8,00%	8,80%	9,60%	10,40%	11,20%	12,00%
Year	Initial Invest.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
SCENARIO 3: PV + HP (50% GRANT)																
Equipment (€)	56.713 €					2.539 €					2.539 €					2.539 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)		12.625 €	12.643 €	12.660 €	12.678 €	12.680 €	12.708 €	12.723 €	12.738 €	12.753 €	12.769 €	12.784 €	12.799 €	12.814 €	12.829 €	12.844 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)		0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)		1.813 €	1.839 €	1.866 €	1.894 €	1.922 €	1.949 €	1.978 €	2.008 €	2.038 €	2.069 €	2.100 €	2.131 €	2.163 €	2.196 €	2.229 €
TOTAL										190.768						
	56.713 €	71.151 €	85.633 €	100.159 €	114.730 €	131.872 €	146.529 €	161.230 €	175.976 €	€	208.144 €	223.027 €	237.957 €	252.935 €	267.959 €	285.571 €
Year		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
SAVINGS		-23.355 €	-21.306 €	-19.059 €	-16.609 €	-16.473 €	-13.612 €	-10.532 €	-7.230 €	-3.702 €	-2.485 €	1.504 €	5.730 €	10.196 €	14.905 €	48.824 €

PV degradation	12,80%	13,60%	14,40%	15,20%	16,00%	16,80%	17,60%	18,40%	0,00%	0,80%	1,60%	2,40%	3,20%	4,00%	4,80%
Year	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
SCENARIO 3: PV + HP (50% GRANT)															
Equipment (€)					2.539 €				56.713 €						2.539 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)	12.860 €	12.875 €	12.890 €	12.905 €	12.920 €	12.936 €	12.951 €	12.966 €	12.617 €	12.632 €	12.647 €	12.662 €	12.678 €	12.693 €	12.708 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)	2.262 €	2.296 €	2.330 €	2.365 €	2.401 €	2.437 €	2.473 €	2.510 €	2.548 €	2.586 €	2.625 €	2.664 €	2.704 €	2.745 €	2.786 €
TOTAL	300.693 €	315.864 €	331.084 €	346.354 €	364.214 €	379.586 €	395.010 €	410.487 €	482.365 €	497.583 €	512.855 €	528.182 €	543.564 €	561.541 €	577.035 €
Year	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
SAVINGS	54.034 €	59.499 €	65.225 €	71.214 €	74.933 €	81.463 €	88.270 €	95.358 €	46.383 €	54.411 €	62.734 €	71.356 €	80.282 €	86.979 €	128.027 €

Table 26 Financial feasibility scenario 3 (PV + HP with a 50% grant on initial investment costs) within 30 years for Lavola pilot

Figure 45 Financial feasibility scenarios within 30 years for Lavola pilot

D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies

Notice that the new business plan simulations within the private partnership BM also include the investment costs, energy costs (both electrical and thermal) and O&M costs as in the ESCO BM. In that case, and as stated in the beginning, the only considered normative O&M costs, that is, the P2 provision with the minimum cost to comply with local regulations in terms of O&M. No P3 and P4 provision has been considered for the private partnership BM.

That being said, many conclusions and recommendations can be taken from the private partnership BM through the comparative financial feasibility analysis within 30 years:

- The first scenario (PV-only) is amortized by the client in 9 to 10 years, which offers an accumulated economic save of 71,932€ at year 23 (just the year before the replacement of the main PV system components is needed) and of 115,555€ in 30 years in relation to the baseline scenario. These indicators match with the actual scenarios where PV is deployed either in residential clients or small offices/commercial/industrial clients (payback returns between 8 and 12 years) and therefore show that the first scenario is feasible and profitable for the client;
- The second scenario (PV + HP) is amortized by the client in 16 to 17 years, which offers an accumulated economic save of 39,874€ at year 23 (just the year before the replacement of the main PV and HP system components is needed) and of 16,138€ in 30 years in relation to the baseline scenario. That's caused by the fact that the required investment at year 24 needs to be again amortized, but as the accumulated cost savings at year 23 is 39,874€, the second payback return is lowered to less than 7 years in comparison with the baseline scenario costs. Anyways, and as seen earlier, the second scenario is also feasible and profitable for the client but with a significant decrease compared to the first scenario;
- The third scenario (PV + HP with a 50% grant on initial investment costs) is amortized by the client in 10 to 11 years, which offers an accumulated economic save of 95,358€ at year 23 (just the year before the replacement of the main PV system components is needed) and of 128,027€ in 30 years in relation to the baseline scenario. Therefore, the third scenario is also feasible and profitable for the client and shows a similar payback and accumulated economic savings as in the first scenario (PV-only), meaning that lowering investment costs while keeping the expected energy savings and O&M costs results in a relevant payback decrease and a significant increase in accumulated economic savings of the deployed CHESSE SETUP system.

This third scenario's financial feasibility analysis has many other outcomes to be discussed (as the Lavola pilot site did not perform a formal STES system) but it sure offers a clear picture on the actual challenges and threats while deploying RES

D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies

equipment and installations. While PV systems have low paybacks and can be amortized in most cases in less than 10 years, heating/cooling generation or energy conversion systems such as HPs, chillers, etc. do still offer higher paybacks while comparing it with the baseline scenario. As seen from the second scenario (PV + HP), all costs are amortized by the client in 16 to 17 years when coupling a PV installation with a HP system.

As stated in IRENA's Renewable Power Generation Costs report from 2019, when referring to solar photovoltaics: *"The rapid decline in total installed costs, increasing capacity factors and falling O&M costs, have contributed to the remarkable reduction in the cost of electricity from solar PV and the improvement of its economic competitiveness"* [31].

Figure 46 Global weighted average total installed costs, capacity factors and LCOE for PV, 2010–2019 (Source: [31])

The same report highlights some relevant aspects on how those systems keep decreasing their costs: *"The global weighted-average LCOE of utility-scale PV plants declined by 82% between 2010 and 2019, from around USD 0.378/kWh to USD 0.068/kWh in 2019, with a 13% reduction year-on-year in 2019. (...) The cost of crystalline solar PV modules sold in Europe declined by around 90% between December 2009 and December 2019. (...) The total installed costs in the residential rooftop PV market are higher than utility-scale due to their small size, but decreased by between 47% and 80% between 2010 and 2019 depending on the market"* [31].

11.2. Sant Cugat Sports Centre – Sant Cugat (Spain)

After studying different possibilities for the location of the thermal storage tank and its operability with the solar-hybrid panels and heat pump, and with the aim of optimizing the system, the CHESSE SETUP system deployed at Sant Cugat's Sports Centre pilot site is designed to cover the swimming-pool water heat demand and the swimming pool air treatment demand during the summer period.

In that case, different scenarios have been simulated:

- **Baseline scenario:** this scenario is meant to offer the initial status of the HVAC system, where heating, pool heating and DHW demands are covered by two low temperature boilers (2 x Ygnis LR-550, 550 kW nominal power and an approximate cost of 15,000€ each) and the cooling demand is met with a water-sourced liquid heat pump (Climaventa WRAT 1002/LN, 200.4kW nominal power and an approximate cost of 20,000€). In that case:
 - **Total investment cost (previously referred as MEB):** 50,000 €;
 - **Initial annual energy costs:** 230,861 €/year;
 - **Initial annual maintenance costs:** 1,500 €/year;
 - **Annual CPI increase:** 1.45%.
- **Scenario 1 – PV-T-only:** this scenario is meant to offer a comparison between the baseline scenario and another one where we only include the PV-T system. Therefore, the initial costs will only be the ones related to the PV-T system implementation (108.262,11 €). In that case:
 - **Total investment cost (previously referred as MEB):** 108,262 € (including all related pipework and accessories such as valves, thermometers, insulating material for the hot water pipes, etc.);
 - **Initial annual energy costs:** 229,324 €/year;
 - **Initial annual maintenance costs:** 2,500 €/year;
 - **Annual CPI increase:** 1.45%.
- **Scenario 2 – PV-T + STES:** this scenario is meant to offer a comparison between the baseline scenario and another one where we include both the PV-T system and the STES, therefore considering that the client does already have a heating/cooling generation unit that can provide either heating or both heating and cooling taking advantage of the new RES generation, STES and heat exchanger deployed systems. In that case:
 - **Total investment cost (previously referred as MEB):** 459,343 € (excluding all civil works and other modification works, therefore considering that the client does not require further adaptation works);
 - **Initial annual energy costs:** 216,517 €/year;
 - **Initial annual maintenance costs:** 2,900 €/year;
 - **Annual CPI increase:** 1.45%.
- **Scenario 3: PV-T + STES + HP:** this scenario is the actual one being deployed, which compares the baseline scenario with the full CHESSE SETUP system

D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies

deployment (PV-T generation, STES and HP as well as all related pipework, wiring, SCADA, etc.). A new water-sourced liquid HP is deployed (Carrier 61WG-060A, 97.5kW nominal power and an approximate cost of 18,000€). In that case:

- **Total investment cost (previously referred as MEB):** 566.305 €;
 - **Initial annual energy costs:** 216,517 €/year;
 - **Initial annual maintenance costs:** 3,800 €/year;
 - **Annual CPI increase:** 1.45%.
- **Scenario 4 – PV-T + HP with a 50% grant:** this scenario is the actual one being deployed but considering a 50% grant either taking advantage of local, country or European level funding trends, as it is the case of the current CHESSE SETUP project. In that case:
 - **Total investment cost (previously referred as MEB):** 283,152 €;
 - **Initial annual energy costs:** 216,517 €/year;
 - **Initial annual maintenance costs:** 3,800 €/year;
 - **Annual CPI increase:** 1.45%.

As stated before, the main difference between the ESCO BM is that, in this case, the client directly relies on its own financial strength to assume the initial investment (or either through a bank load with pre-fixed payment conditions). In the same path, the maintenance costs can be performed either by an ESCO or just a small maintenance operator, therefore reducing initial P2 service costs. Note also that those simulations now do have to include a PV degradation parameter aside, as the initial ESCO P3 service was the one that included a fixed fee related to any sudden failure/need of replacing some of the equipment involved in the overall CHESSE SETUP system as well as equipment/material degradation. As seen before, and considering it as a multiplying factor that we will simplify and make it lineal on time, the annual PV production decrease has been considered to be of 0,8%. Note also that this only affects the amount of energy produced by the PV system but that the CPI increase affects all annual energy cost.

D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies

Year	Initial Invest.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
BASELINE SCENARIO											
Equipment (€)	50.000,00 €										
Energy cost (electricity) (€)		94.131,54 €	95.491,27 €	96.888,31 €	98.323,71 €	99.798,56 €	101.195,74 €	102.713,68 €	104.254,38 €	105.818,20 €	107.405,47 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)		136.729,18 €	138.704,23 €	140.733,48 €	142.818,44 €	144.960,72 €	146.990,17 €	149.195,02 €	151.432,95 €	153.704,44 €	156.010,01 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)		1.500,00 €	1.521,67 €	1.543,93 €	1.566,80 €	1.590,30 €	1.612,57 €	1.636,76 €	1.661,31 €	1.686,23 €	1.711,52 €
TOTAL	50.000,00 €	282.360,72 €	518.077,89 €	757.243,61 €	999.952,56 €	1.246.302,15 €	1.496.100,64 €	1.749.646,10 €	2.006.994,74 €	2.268.203,61 €	2.533.330,62 €

Year	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
BASELINE SCENARIO										
Equipment (€)					50.000,00 €					
Energy cost (electricity) (€)	109.016,56 €	110.651,80 €	112.311,58 €	113.996,25 €	115.706,20 €	117.441,79 €	119.203,42 €	120.991,47 €	122.806,34 €	124.648,44 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)	158.350,16 €	160.725,41 €	163.136,29 €	165.583,34 €	168.067,09 €	170.588,09 €	173.146,92 €	175.744,12 €	178.380,28 €	181.055,99 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)	1.737,19 €	1.763,25 €	1.789,70 €	1.816,55 €	1.843,80 €	1.871,45 €	1.899,52 €	1.928,02 €	1.956,94 €	1.986,29 €
TOTAL	2.802.434,53 €	3.075.575,00 €	3.352.812,57 €	3.634.208,71 €	3.969.825,79 €	4.259.727,13 €	4.553.976,99 €	4.852.640,59 €	5.155.784,15 €	5.463.474,87 €

Year	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
BASELINE SCENARIO										
Equipment (€)										50.000,00 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)	126.518,16 €	128.415,94 €	130.342,17 €	132.297,31 €	134.281,77 €	134.281,77 €	134.281,77 €	134.281,77 €	134.281,77 €	134.281,77 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)	183.771,83 €	186.528,40 €	189.326,33 €	192.166,22 €	195.048,72 €	195.048,72 €	195.048,72 €	195.048,72 €	195.048,72 €	195.048,72 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)	2.016,09 €	2.046,33 €	2.077,02 €	2.108,18 €	2.139,80 €	2.139,80 €	2.139,80 €	2.139,80 €	2.139,80 €	2.139,80 €
TOTAL	5.775.780,94 €	6.092.771,61 €	6.414.517,13 €	6.741.088,84 €	7.072.559,12 €	7.404.029,41 €	7.735.499,69 €	8.066.969,97 €	8.398.440,26 €	8.779.910,54 €

Table 27 Financial feasibility baseline scenario within 30 years for Sant Cugat pilot

D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies

PV degradation	0,00%	0,80%	1,60%	2,40%	3,20%	4,00%	4,80%	5,60%	6,40%	7,20%	8,00%
Year	Initial Invest.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
SCENARIO 1: PV-T ONLY											
Equipment (€)	108.262,11 €					18.059,54 €					18.059,54 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)		92.595,25 €	92.635,49 €	92.675,75 €	92.716,01 €	92.648,01 €	92.762,74 €	92.786,11 €	92.809,48 €	92.832,85 €	92.856,22 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)		136.729,18 €	138.704,23 €	140.733,48 €	142.818,44 €	144.960,72 €	146.990,17 €	149.195,02 €	151.432,95 €	153.704,44 €	156.010,01 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)		2.500,00 €	2.536,11 €	2.573,22 €	2.611,34 €	2.650,51 €	2.687,62 €	2.727,93 €	2.768,85 €	2.810,38 €	2.852,54 €
TOTAL	108.262,11 €	340.086,54 €	573.962,38 €	809.944,82 €	1.048.090,61 €	1.306.409,39 €	1.548.849,92 €	1.793.558,98 €	2.040.570,26 €	2.289.917,93 €	2.559.696,23 €
Year		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
SAVINGS		-57.725,82 €	-55.884,48 €	-52.701,21 €	-48.138,05 €	-60.107,23 €	-52.749,28 €	-43.912,88 €	-33.575,52 €	-21.714,32 €	-26.365,62 €

PV degradation	8,80%	9,60%	10,40%	11,20%	12,00%	12,80%	13,60%	14,40%	15,20%	16,00%
Year	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
SCENARIO 1: PV-T ONLY										
Equipment (€)					18.059,54 €					18.059,54 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)	92.879,58 €	92.902,95 €	92.926,32 €	92.949,69 €	92.973,05 €	92.996,42 €	93.019,79 €	93.043,16 €	93.066,53 €	93.089,89 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)	158.350,16 €	160.725,41 €	163.136,29 €	165.583,34 €	168.067,09 €	170.588,09 €	173.146,92 €	175.744,12 €	178.380,28 €	181.055,99 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)	2.895,32 €	2.938,75 €	2.982,84 €	3.027,58 €	3.072,99 €	3.119,09 €	3.165,87 €	3.213,36 €	3.261,56 €	3.310,49 €
TOTAL	2.813.821,30 €	3.070.388,42 €	3.329.433,87 €	3.590.994,47 €	3.873.167,15 €	4.139.870,75 €	4.409.203,33 €	4.681.203,97 €	4.955.912,34 €	5.251.428,24 €
Year	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
SAVINGS	-11.386,77 €	5.186,58 €	23.378,70 €	43.214,24 €	96.658,65 €	119.856,38 €	144.773,66 €	171.436,63 €	199.871,82 €	212.046,63 €

PV degradation	16,80%	17,60%	18,40%	0,00%	0,80%	1,60%	2,40%	3,20%	4,00%	4,80%
Year	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
SCENARIO 1: PV-T ONLY										
Equipment (€)				108.262,11 €						18.059,54 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)	93.113,26 €	93.136,63 €	93.160,00 €	92.622,54 €	91.276,75 €	91.299,78 €	91.322,80 €	91.345,82 €	91.368,84 €	91.391,87 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)	183.771,83 €	186.528,40 €	189.326,33 €	192.166,22 €	195.048,72 €	195.048,72 €	195.048,72 €	195.048,72 €	195.048,72 €	195.048,72 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)	3.360,14 €	3.410,54 €	3.461,70 €	3.513,63 €	3.566,33 €	3.566,33 €	3.566,33 €	3.566,33 €	3.566,33 €	3.566,33 €
TOTAL	5.531.673,47 €	5.814.749,05 €	6.100.697,08 €	6.497.261,58 €	6.787.153,38 €	7.077.068,21 €	7.367.006,06 €	7.656.966,93 €	7.965.010,36 €	8.255.017,28 €
Year	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
SAVINGS	244.107,47 €	278.022,56 €	313.820,06 €	243.827,26 €	285.405,74 €	326.961,20 €	368.493,64 €	410.003,05 €	433.429,90 €	524.893,26 €

Table 28 Financial feasibility scenario 1 (PV-T-only) within 30 years for Sant Cugat pilot

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D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies

PV degradation	0,00%	0,80%	1,60%	2,40%	3,20%	4,00%	4,80%	5,60%	6,40%	7,20%	8,00%
Year	Initial Invest.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
SCENARIO 2: PV-T + STES											
Equipment (€)	459.342,75 €					18.059,54 €					18.059,54 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)		92.595,25 €	92.635,49 €	92.675,75 €	92.716,01 €	92.648,01 €	92.762,74 €	92.786,11 €	92.809,48 €	92.832,85 €	92.856,22 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)		123.922,00 €	125.712,05 €	127.551,22 €	129.440,89 €	131.382,50 €	133.221,86 €	135.220,19 €	137.248,49 €	139.307,22 €	141.396,83 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)		2.900,00 €	2.941,89 €	2.984,93 €	3.029,15 €	3.074,59 €	3.117,63 €	3.164,40 €	3.211,86 €	3.260,04 €	3.308,94 €
TOTAL	459.342,75 €	678.760,00 €	900.049,43 €	1.123.261,33 €	1.348.447,38 €	1.593.612,02 €	1.822.714,26 €	2.053.884,95 €	2.287.154,79 €	2.522.554,89 €	2.778.176,42 €
		216.517									
Year		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
SAVINGS		-396.399,27 €	-381.971,54 €	-366.017,72 €	-348.494,81 €	-347.309,87 €	-326.613,62 €	-304.238,86 €	-280.160,05 €	-254.351,28 €	-244.845,80 €

PV degradation	8,80%	9,60%	10,40%	11,20%	12,00%	12,80%	13,60%	14,40%	15,20%	16,00%
Year	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
SCENARIO 2: PV-T + STES										
Equipment (€)					18.059,54 €					18.059,54 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)	92.879,58 €	92.902,95 €	92.926,32 €	92.949,69 €	92.973,05 €	92.996,42 €	93.019,79 €	93.043,16 €	93.066,53 €	93.089,89 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)	143.517,78 €	145.670,54 €	147.855,60 €	150.073,44 €	152.324,54 €	154.609,41 €	156.928,55 €	159.282,48 €	161.671,71 €	164.096,79 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)	3.358,58 €	3.408,96 €	3.460,09 €	3.511,99 €	3.564,67 €	3.618,14 €	3.672,41 €	3.727,50 €	3.783,41 €	3.840,16 €
TOTAL	3.017.932,36 €	3.259.914,81 €	3.504.156,82 €	3.750.691,93 €	4.017.613,74 €	4.268.837,71 €	4.522.458,46 €	4.778.511,59 €	5.037.033,24 €	5.316.119,63 €
Year	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
SAVINGS	-215.497,83 €	-184.339,81 €	-151.344,25 €	-116.483,22 €	-47.787,94 €	-9.110,58 €	31.518,53 €	74.129,00 €	118.750,91 €	147.355,24 €

PV degradation	16,80%	17,60%	18,40%	0,00%	0,80%	1,60%	2,40%	3,20%	4,00%	4,80%
Year	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
SCENARIO 2: PV-T + STES										
Equipment (€)				459.342,75 €						18.059,54 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)	93.113,26 €	93.136,63 €	93.160,00 €	92.622,54 €	91.276,75 €	91.299,78 €	91.322,80 €	91.345,82 €	91.368,84 €	91.391,87 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)	166.558,24 €	169.056,61 €	171.592,46 €	174.166,35 €	176.778,85 €	176.778,85 €	176.778,85 €	176.778,85 €	176.778,85 €	176.778,85 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)	3.897,77 €	3.956,23 €	4.015,58 €	4.075,81 €	4.136,95 €	4.136,95 €	4.136,95 €	4.136,95 €	4.136,95 €	4.136,95 €
TOTAL	5.579.688,89 €	5.845.838,37 €	6.114.606,40 €	6.844.813,85 €	7.117.006,40 €	7.389.221,96 €	7.661.460,55 €	7.933.722,17 €	8.224.066,34 €	8.496.374,00 €
Year	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
SAVINGS	196.092,05 €	246.933,24 €	299.910,73 €	-103.725,01 €	-44.447,27 €	14.807,44 €	74.039,14 €	133.247,81 €	174.373,92 €	283.536,54 €

Table 29 Financial feasibility scenario 2 (PV-T + STES) within 30 years for Sant Cugat pilot

D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies

PV degradation	0,00%	0,80%	1,60%	2,40%	3,20%	4,00%	4,80%	5,60%	6,40%	7,20%	8,00%
Year	Initial Invest.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
SCENARIO 3: PV-T + STES + HP											
Equipment (€)	566.304,92 €					18.059,54 €					18.059,54 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)		92.595,25 €	92.635,49 €	92.675,75 €	92.716,01 €	92.648,01 €	92.762,74 €	92.786,11 €	92.809,48 €	92.832,85 €	92.856,22 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)		123.922,00 €	125.712,05 €	127.551,22 €	129.440,89 €	131.382,50 €	133.221,86 €	135.220,19 €	137.248,49 €	139.307,22 €	141.396,83 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)		3.800,00 €	3.854,89 €	3.911,29 €	3.969,23 €	4.028,77 €	4.085,18 €	4.146,45 €	4.208,65 €	4.271,78 €	4.335,86 €
TOTAL	566.304,92 €	786.622,16 €	1.008.824,60 €	1.232.962,85 €	1.459.088,98 €	1.705.207,81 €	1.935.277,59 €	2.167.430,34 €	2.401.696,96 €	2.638.108,80 €	2.894.757,24 €
Year		216.517	218.348	220.227							
SAVINGS		-504.261,44 €	-490.746,70 €	-475.719,24 €	-459.136,42 €	-458.905,65 €	-439.176,95 €	-417.784,24 €	-394.702,22 €	-369.905,19 €	-361.426,62 €

PV degradation	8,80%	9,60%	10,40%	11,20%	12,00%	12,80%	13,60%	14,40%	15,20%	16,00%
Year	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
SCENARIO 3: PV-T + STES + HP										
Equipment (€)					18.059,54 €					18.059,54 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)	92.879,58 €	92.902,95 €	92.926,32 €	92.949,69 €	92.973,05 €	92.996,42 €	93.019,79 €	93.043,16 €	93.066,53 €	93.089,89 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)	143.517,78 €	145.670,54 €	147.855,60 €	150.073,44 €	152.324,54 €	154.609,41 €	156.928,55 €	159.282,48 €	161.671,71 €	164.096,79 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)	4.400,89 €	4.466,91 €	4.533,91 €	4.601,92 €	4.670,95 €	4.741,01 €	4.812,13 €	4.884,31 €	4.957,57 €	5.031,94 €
TOTAL	3.135.555,49 €	3.378.595,89 €	3.623.911,73 €	3.871.536,77 €	4.139.564,85 €	4.391.911,69 €	4.646.672,16 €	4.903.882,10 €	5.163.577,91 €	5.443.856,07 €
Year	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
SAVINGS	-333.120,97 €	-303.020,90 €	-271.099,16 €	-237.328,06 €	-169.739,06 €	-132.184,56 €	-92.695,17 €	-51.241,51 €	-7.793,76 €	19.618,79 €

PV degradation	16,80%	17,60%	18,40%	0,00%	0,80%	1,60%	2,40%	3,20%	4,00%	4,80%
Year	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
SCENARIO 3: PV-T + STES + HP										
Equipment (€)				566.304,92 €						18.059,54 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)	93.113,26 €	93.136,63 €	93.160,00 €	92.622,54 €	91.276,75 €	91.299,78 €	91.322,80 €	91.345,82 €	91.368,84 €	91.391,87 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)	166.558,24 €	169.056,61 €	171.592,46 €	174.166,35 €	176.778,85 €	176.778,85 €	176.778,85 €	176.778,85 €	176.778,85 €	176.778,85 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)	5.107,42 €	5.184,03 €	5.261,79 €	5.340,72 €	5.420,83 €	5.420,83 €	5.420,83 €	5.420,83 €	5.420,83 €	5.420,83 €
TOTAL	5.708.634,99 €	5.976.012,26 €	6.246.026,51 €	7.084.461,03 €	7.357.937,46 €	7.631.436,90 €	7.904.959,37 €	8.178.504,87 €	8.470.132,92 €	8.743.724,46 €
Year	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
SAVINGS	67.145,95 €	116.759,34 €	168.490,62 €	-343.372,19 €	-285.378,33 €	-227.407,50 €	-169.459,68 €	-111.534,89 €	-71.692,66 €	36.186,08 €

Table 30 Financial feasibility scenario 3 (PV-T + STES + HP) within 30 years for Sant Cugat pilot

D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies

PV degradation	0,00%	0,80%	1,60%	2,40%	3,20%	4,00%	4,80%	5,60%	6,40%	7,20%	8,00%
Year	Initial Invest.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
SCENARIO 4: PV-T + STES + HP (50% GRANT)											
Equipment (€)	283.152,46 €					18.059,54 €					18.059,54 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)		92.595,25 €	92.635,49 €	92.675,75 €	92.716,01 €	92.648,01 €	92.762,74 €	92.786,11 €	92.809,48 €	92.832,85 €	92.856,22 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)		123.922,00 €	125.712,05 €	127.551,22 €	129.440,89 €	131.382,50 €	133.221,86 €	135.220,19 €	137.248,49 €	139.307,22 €	141.396,83 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)		3.800,00 €	3.854,89 €	3.911,29 €	3.969,23 €	4.028,77 €	4.085,18 €	4.146,45 €	4.208,65 €	4.271,78 €	4.335,86 €
TOTAL	283.152,46 €	503.469,70 €	725.672,14 €	949.810,39 €	1.175.936,53 €	1.422.055,35 €	1.652.125,13 €	1.884.277,88 €	2.118.544,50 €	2.354.956,34 €	2.611.604,78 €
Year		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
SAVINGS		-221.108,98 €	-207.594,24 €	-192.566,78 €	-175.983,96 €	-175.753,20 €	-156.024,49 €	-134.631,78 €	-111.549,76 €	-86.752,73 €	-78.274,16 €

PV degradation	8,80%	9,60%	10,40%	11,20%	12,00%	12,80%	13,60%	14,40%	15,20%	16,00%
Year	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
SCENARIO 4: PV-T + STES + HP (50% GRANT)										
Equipment (€)					18.059,54 €					18.059,54 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)	92.879,58 €	92.902,95 €	92.926,32 €	92.949,69 €	92.973,05 €	92.996,42 €	93.019,79 €	93.043,16 €	93.066,53 €	93.089,89 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)	143.517,78 €	145.670,54 €	147.855,60 €	150.073,44 €	152.324,54 €	154.609,41 €	156.928,55 €	159.282,48 €	161.671,71 €	164.096,79 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)	4.400,89 €	4.466,91 €	4.533,91 €	4.601,92 €	4.670,95 €	4.741,01 €	4.812,13 €	4.884,31 €	4.957,57 €	5.031,94 €
TOTAL	2.852.403,03 €	3.095.443,44 €	3.340.759,27 €	3.588.384,31 €	3.856.412,39 €	4.108.759,23 €	4.363.519,70 €	4.620.729,64 €	4.880.425,46 €	5.160.703,62 €
Year	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
SAVINGS	-49.968,51 €	-19.868,44 €	12.053,30 €	45.824,40 €	113.413,40 €	150.967,90 €	190.457,29 €	231.910,95 €	275.358,70 €	302.771,25 €

PV degradation	16,80%	17,60%	18,40%	0,00%	0,80%	1,60%	2,40%	3,20%	4,00%	4,80%
Year	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
SCENARIO 4: PV-T + STES + HP (50% GRANT)										
Equipment (€)				283.152,46 €						18.059,54 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)	93.113,26 €	93.136,63 €	93.160,00 €	92.622,54 €	91.276,75 €	91.299,78 €	91.322,80 €	91.345,82 €	91.368,84 €	91.391,87 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)	166.558,24 €	169.056,61 €	171.592,46 €	174.166,35 €	176.778,85 €	176.778,85 €	176.778,85 €	176.778,85 €	176.778,85 €	176.778,85 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)	5.107,42 €	5.184,03 €	5.261,79 €	5.340,72 €	5.420,83 €	5.420,83 €	5.420,83 €	5.420,83 €	5.420,83 €	5.420,83 €
TOTAL	5.425.482,53 €	5.692.859,81 €	5.962.874,05 €	6.518.156,11 €	6.791.632,54 €	7.065.131,99 €	7.338.654,46 €	7.612.199,95 €	7.903.828,01 €	8.177.419,54 €
Year	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
SAVINGS	350.298,41 €	399.911,80 €	451.643,08 €	222.932,72 €	280.926,58 €	338.897,42 €	396.845,23 €	454.770,02 €	494.612,25 €	602.491,00 €

Table 31 Financial feasibility scenario 4 (PV-T + STES + HP with a 50% grant on initial investment costs) within 30 years for Sant Cugat pilot

Figure 47 Financial feasibility scenarios within 30 years for Sant Cugat pilot

D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies

Notice that the new business plan simulations within the private partnership BM also include the investment costs, energy costs (both electrical and thermal) and O&M costs as in the ESCO BM. In that case, and as stated in the beginning, the only considered normative O&M costs, that is, the P2 provision with the minimum cost to comply with local regulations in terms of O&M. No P3 and P4 provision has been considered for the private partnership BM.

That being said, many conclusions and recommendations can be taken from the private partnership BM through the comparative financial feasibility analysis within 30 years:

- The first scenario (PV-only) is amortized by the client in 11 to 12 years, which offers an accumulated economic save of 313,820€ at year 23 (just the year before the replacement of the main PV system components is needed) and of 524,893€ in 30 years in relation to the baseline scenario. These indicators match with the actual scenarios where PV is deployed either in residential clients or small offices/commercial/industrial clients (payback returns between 8 and 12 years) and therefore show that the first scenario is feasible and profitable for the client;
- The second scenario (PV + STES) is amortized by the client in 16 to 17 years, which offers an accumulated economic save of 299,911€ at year 23 (just the year before the replacement of the main PV and HP system components is needed) and of 283,537€ in 30 years in relation to the baseline scenario. That's caused by the fact that the required investment at year 24 needs to be again amortized, but as the accumulated cost savings at year 23 is 299,911€, the second payback return is lowered to less than 3 years in comparison with the baseline scenario costs. Anyways, and as seen earlier, the second scenario is also feasible and profitable for the client but with a significant decrease compared to the first scenario;
- The third scenario (PV + STES + HP) is amortized by the client in 19 to 20 years, which offers an accumulated economic save of 168.491€ at year 23 (just the year before the replacement of the main PV system components is needed) and of 36.186€ in 30 years in relation to the baseline scenario. Therefore, the third scenario is also feasible and profitable for the client but shows that the actual CHESSE SETUP system deployment as it has been done in Sant Cugat's pilot offers relatively small incomes and benefits in terms of cost savings. The positive environmental impact is noticeable but the accumulated energy and cost savings are relatively small when compared to such an important initial investment cost. That being said, the third scenario is also feasible and profitable for the client but with a significant decrease compared to the first and second scenarios;
- The fourth scenario (PV + STES + HP with a 50% grant on initial investment costs) is amortized by the client in 12 to 13 years, which offers an accumulated economic save of 451,643€ at year 23 (just the year before the replacement of

D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies

the main PV system components is needed) and of 602,491€ in 30 years in relation to the baseline scenario. Therefore, the fourth scenario is also feasible and profitable for the client and shows a similar payback and accumulated economic savings as in the first scenario (PV-only), meaning that lowering investment costs while keeping the expected energy savings and O&M costs results in a relevant payback decrease and a significant increase in accumulated economic savings of the deployed CHESSETUP system.

As Sant Cugat's pilot site private partnership BM shows, it looks like under the conditions in which the CHESSETUP system has been deployed in this pilot, the most suitable client in which we could replicate and/or escalate the overall PV-T + STES + HP system would be the one who already has a tank/storage facility that could be easily adapted as a STES (useable water tank formerly used for other purposes e.g. fire emergency, drinking water supply water systems, fuel storage, etc.) and also has a heating/cooling generation unit (boiler/HP/chiller, etc.) to satisfy the heating/cooling/DHW demand. In case the client does not already have a tank/storage facility that could be easily adapted as a SHS but no need of extra construction/civil works is needed (therefore, the client needs to deploy the RES generation system and the STES), the payback increases up to 16 – 17 years but still offers a great profitability and accumulated energy and cost savings.

On the other hand, when the client needs to deploy the whole CHESSETUP system – both RES generation, STES and heat exchange systems as well as a heating/cooling generation unit (boiler/HP/chiller, etc.), the financial viability of the project is tightened, offering paybacks of 19 – 20 years and small accumulated energy and cost savings within 30 years. That's why a scenario where the client relies upon different grants/subsidies in terms of energy efficiency, RES generation or increased performance funding opportunities either locally, at country level or even at a European level is comparable to the first scenario. That can be seen from the perspective that the STES and HP sectors might need to increase their performance and/or reduce associated investment + O&M costs so that these kind of coupled solutions do offer financial profitability, cost and energy savings and a reduced environmental impact at a minimum risk and in small time windows (about 10 years at maximum).

As stated in EHPA's White Paper: Heat Pumps - Integrating Technologies to Decarbonise Heating and Cooling (2018), *"The economics of a heat pump are mainly influenced by the investments and the cost of operations. The final decision in favour or against a heat pump system is not only influenced by the absolute cost of the system but even more by the relative cost differences between different heating solutions and to a certain degree also by the attractiveness/image of the technology in general and the personal preference of the investor in particular"* [32].

"An overarching universal statement on the economic cost of heat pump systems is therefore not possible. It is however worthwhile to dissect the different cost components to gain a better understanding how they will be influenced by general market

D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies

development and the related economies of scale as well as by the (disruptive) innovation and creation of new business models resulting from digitalisation, sector connection and the introduction of new services for heating/cooling” [32].

“In the ideal world, an end-user would compare cost of all available heating technologies over the lifetime of the product and select the one with the lowest total cost of ownership” [32].

“The following cost components can be distinguished:

- A. Investment cost (CAPEX)
 - A1. cost of system design (often hidden)
 - A2. administration cost: permits, application procedures, etc.
 - A3. cost of the product or system including the tank
 - A4. installation cost
 - A5. financial advantages based on the investment cost: loans, grants, tax reductions, consulting services etc.
- B. Cost of operating the system (OPEX)
 - B1. fuel
 - B2. maintenance, insurance
 - B3. competitive advantages and disadvantages affecting B1 and B2: subsidies for the energy used, taxation of the energy carriers preferred electricity tariff compensation for demand side flexibility
- C. cost of refurbishment, exchange or dismantling

These cost factors depend a lot on the respective market framework and differ widely from country to country. This holds true in particular for the cost of equipment and the cost of fuel (often mainly influence by taxation levels). When referring to financial incentives and administration cost, these can differ from region to region and even from city to city. In general, items A5 and B3 will reduce the immediate and total cost of ownership of a heat pump system and increase its competitiveness” [32].

Figure 48 Heat pump sales development by technology (Source: [32])

For that reason, accelerating the heat pump market development through support schemes of institutional or financial nature can accelerate the deployment of HPs all over the world. The following figure shows a generic typology of approaches aimed at supporting HP deployment:

Figure 49 Types of incentive schemes for heat pumps (Source: [32])

11.3. Corby Eco-Homes – Corby (England)

As a brief reminder, the Corby pilot case is meant to be a leading edge demonstration of eco-homes across a variety of house types. It is aimed to address many issues of new-build houses by ensuring a high quality building construction, focusing on developing energy efficiency and low carbon eco-homes. This Deliverable's section will focus on the implementation of the 3-bedroom townhouses (houses type A&B) as referred in Deliverables 3.7 and 5.1, which have a gross internal area (GIA) of 167.1 m². The CHESSETUP system deployment for those houses includes a combination of both hybrid PV-T and PV-only panels, a ground source heat pump and the Earth Energy Bank (EEB), the solar energy storage to be built under the houses.

In that case, different scenarios have been simulated:

- **Baseline scenario:** this scenario is meant to offer the initial status of the HVAC system. In that case, and due to the fact that those are new built houses, the baseline scenario considered a wall-hung condensing boiler to satisfy both the heating and the DHW demand. For example, a BAXI Platinum Plus/Max Plus/Duo Plus/Combi Plus brand would fit, considering a 3-bedroom townhouse FIA of 167.1 m². In that case, the nominal heating power rounds above 24 and 34 kW with an approximate cost between 2,800 and 4,500 €; we will consider a 4,000 € overall installation cost. In that case:
 - **Total investment cost (previously referred as MEB):** 4,000 €;
 - **Initial annual energy costs:** 1,086 €/year;
 - **Initial annual maintenance costs:** 50 €/year;
 - **Annual CPI increase:** 1.45%.
- **Scenario 1 – PV/PV-T-only:** this scenario is meant to offer a comparison between the baseline scenario and another one where we only include the PV/PV-T + ESS equipment. Therefore, the initial costs will be the ones from the PV/PVT + ESS system (9,477 € and 749 € as seen in section 10.3.1). In that case:
 - **Total investment cost (previously referred as MEB):** 10,769 €
 - **Initial annual energy costs:** 715 €/year;
 - **Initial annual maintenance costs:** 150 €/year;
 - **Annual CPI increase:** 1.45%.
- **Scenario 2 – PV/PV-T + EEB:** this scenario considers that the client is assuming the cost of both the PV/PV-T system and underground energy storage (EEB) with an approximate cost of 2,742 €. Therefore, we're considering that the client does already have a heating/cooling generation unit that can cover both heating and DHW demand taking advantage of the new RES generation, STES and heat exchanger deployed systems. In that case:
 - **Total investment cost (previously referred as MEB):** 13,511 €;
 - **Initial annual energy costs:** 260 €/year;
 - **Initial annual maintenance costs:** 200 €/year;
 - **Annual CPI increase:** 1.45%.

- Scenario 3 – PV/PV-T + EEB + HP: this scenario is the actual one being deployed which considers that the client has to assume the cost of both PV/PV-T + ESS. EEB + HP (Mastertherm Ground-Sourced HP, 8kW of nominal power and an approximate cost of 6,960 €). In that case:
 - **Total investment cost (previously referred as MEB):** 21,478 €;
 - **Initial annual energy costs:** 260 €/year;
 - **Initial annual maintenance costs:** 250 €/year;
 - **Annual CPI increase:** 1.45%.
- Scenario 4 – PV + HP with a 50% grant: this scenario is the actual one being deployed but considering a 50% grant either taking advantage of local, country or European level funding trends, as it is the case of the current CHESSE SETUP project. In that case:
 - **Total investment cost (previously referred as MEB):** 10,739 €;
 - **Initial annual energy costs:** 260 €/year;
 - **Initial annual maintenance costs:** 250 €/year;
 - **Annual CPI increase:** 1.45%.

Again notice that main difference between the ESCO BM is that, in this case, the client directly relies on its own financial strength to assume the initial investment (or either through a bank load with pre-fixed payment conditions). In the same path, the maintenance costs can be performed either by an ESCO or just a small maintenance operator, therefore reducing initial P2 service costs. Note also that those simulations now do have to include a PV degradation parameter aside, as the initial ESCO P3 service was the one that included a fixed fee related to any sudden failure/need of replacing some of the equipment involved in the overall CHESSE SETUP system as well as equipment/material degradation. As seen before, and considering it as a multiplying factor that we will simplify and make it lineal on time, the annual PV production decrease has been considered to be of 0,8%. Note also that this only affects the amount of energy produced by the PV system but that the CPI increase affects all annual energy cost.

D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies

Year	Initial Invest.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
BASELINE SCENARIO											
Equipment (€)	4.000 €										
Energy cost (electricity) (€)		715 €	726 €	736 €	747 €	758 €	769 €	780 €	792 €	804 €	816 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)		369 €	375 €	380 €	386 €	392 €	397 €	403 €	409 €	415 €	422 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)		50 €	51 €	51 €	52 €	53 €	54 €	55 €	55 €	56 €	57 €
TOTAL	4.000 €	5.135 €	6.286 €	7.454 €	8.639 €	9.842 €	11.062 €	12.300 €	13.557 €	14.832 €	16.127 €

Year	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
BASELINE SCENARIO										
Equipment (€)						4.000 €				
Energy cost (electricity) (€)	828 €	841 €	853 €	866 €	879 €	892 €	906 €	919 €	933 €	947 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)	428 €	434 €	441 €	447 €	454 €	461 €	468 €	475 €	482 €	489 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)	58 €	59 €	60 €	61 €	61 €	62 €	63 €	64 €	65 €	66 €
TOTAL	17.441 €	18.775 €	20.129 €	21.503 €	26.898 €	28.313 €	29.750 €	31.209 €	32.689 €	34.192 €

Year	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
BASELINE SCENARIO										
Equipment (€)										4.000 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)	961 €	976 €	990 €	1.005 €	1.020 €	1.020 €	1.020 €	1.020 €	1.020 €	1.020 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)	497 €	504 €	512 €	519 €	527 €	527 €	527 €	527 €	527 €	527 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)	67 €	68 €	69 €	70 €	71 €	71 €	71 €	71 €	71 €	71 €
TOTAL	35.717 €	37.265 €	38.836 €	40.431 €	42.049 €	43.668 €	45.287 €	46.905 €	48.524 €	54.143 €

Table 32 Financial feasibility baseline scenario within 30 years for Corby pilot

D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies

PV degradation	0,00%	0,80%	1,60%	2,40%	3,20%	4,00%	4,80%	5,60%	6,40%	7,20%	8,00%
Year	Initial Invest.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
SCENARIO 1: PV/PV-T ONLY											
Equipment (€)	10.769 €					997 €					997 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)		0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)		369 €	375 €	380 €	386 €	392 €	397 €	403 €	409 €	415 €	422 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)		150 €	152 €	154 €	157 €	159 €	161 €	164 €	166 €	169 €	171 €
TOTAL	10.769 €	11.288 €	11.815 €	12.350 €	12.893 €	14.440 €	14.998 €	15.565 €	16.141 €	16.724 €	18.314 €
Year		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
SAVINGS		-6.154 €	-5.530 €	-4.896 €	-4.254 €	-4.598 €	-3.937 €	-3.265 €	-2.584 €	-1.892 €	-2.187 €

PV degradation	8,80%	9,60%	10,40%	11,20%	12,00%	12,80%	13,60%	14,40%	15,20%	16,00%
Year	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
SCENARIO 1: PV/PV-T ONLY										
Equipment (€)					997 €					997 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)	428 €	434 €	441 €	447 €	454 €	461 €	468 €	475 €	482 €	489 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)	174 €	176 €	179 €	182 €	184 €	187 €	190 €	193 €	196 €	199 €
TOTAL	18.916 €	19.526 €	20.146 €	20.775 €	22.410 €	23.058 €	23.716 €	24.384 €	25.061 €	26.746 €
Year	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
SAVINGS	-1.475 €	-751 €	-17 €	728 €	4.487 €	5.255 €	6.034 €	6.825 €	7.628 €	7.446 €

PV degradation	16,80%	17,60%	18,40%	0,00%	0,80%	1,60%	2,40%	3,20%	4,00%	4,80%
Year	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
SCENARIO 1: PV/PV-T ONLY										
Equipment (€)				10.769 €					997 €	
Energy cost (electricity) (€)	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)	497 €	504 €	512 €	519 €	527 €	527 €	527 €	527 €	527 €	527 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)	202 €	205 €	208 €	211 €	214 €	214 €	214 €	214 €	214 €	214 €
TOTAL	27.444 €	28.153 €	28.872 €	40.371 €	41.112 €	41.853 €	42.594 €	43.335 €	45.073 €	45.814 €
Year	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
SAVINGS	8.272 €	9.112 €	9.964 €	60 €	937 €	1.815 €	2.693 €	3.570 €	3.451 €	8.329 €

Table 33 Financial feasibility scenario 1 (PV/PV-T-only) within 30 years for Corby pilot

D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies

PV degradation	0,00%	0,80%	1,60%	2,40%	3,20%	4,00%	4,80%	5,60%	6,40%	7,20%	8,00%
Year	Initial Invest.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
SCENARIO 2: PV/PV-T + EEB											
Equipment (€)	13.511 €					997 €					997 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)		260 €	267 €	275 €	282 €	289 €	296 €	304 €	311 €	318 €	325 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)		0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)		200 €	203 €	206 €	209 €	212 €	215 €	218 €	222 €	225 €	228 €
TOTAL	13.511 €	13.970 €	14.441 €	14.921 €	15.412 €	16.910 €	17.421 €	17.943 €	18.475 €	19.018 €	20.569 €
Year		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
SAVINGS		-8.836 €	-8.155 €	-7.467 €	-6.773 €	-7.068 €	-6.359 €	-5.643 €	-4.919 €	-4.186 €	-4.442 €

PV degradation	8,80%	9,60%	10,40%	11,20%	12,00%	12,80%	13,60%	14,40%	15,20%	16,00%
Year	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
SCENARIO 2: PV/PV-T + EEB										
Equipment (€)					997 €					997 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)	333 €	340 €	347 €	355 €	362 €	369 €	376 €	384 €	391 €	398 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)	232 €	235 €	239 €	242 €	246 €	250 €	253 €	257 €	261 €	265 €
TOTAL	21.133 €	21.708 €	22.294 €	22.891 €	24.495 €	25.114 €	25.744 €	26.384 €	27.036 €	28.696 €
Year	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
SAVINGS	-3.692 €	-2.933 €	-2.165 €	-1.388 €	2.402 €	3.199 €	4.007 €	4.824 €	5.653 €	5.496 €

PV degradation	16,80%	17,60%	18,40%	0,00%	0,80%	1,60%	2,40%	3,20%	4,00%	4,80%
Year	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
SCENARIO 2: PV/PV-T + EEB										
Equipment (€)				13.511 €					997 €	
Energy cost (electricity) (€)	405 €	413 €	420 €	253 €	256 €	263 €	271 €	278 €	285 €	292 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)	269 €	273 €	277 €	281 €	285 €	285 €	285 €	285 €	285 €	285 €
TOTAL	29.370 €	30.056 €	30.753 €	44.797 €	45.339 €	45.887 €	46.443 €	47.006 €	48.573 €	49.150 €
Year	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
SAVINGS	6.346 €	7.209 €	8.083 €	-4.366 €	-3.289 €	-2.219 €	-1.156 €	-101 €	-49 €	4.992 €

Table 34 Financial feasibility scenario 2 (PV/PV-T + EEB) within 30 years for Corby pilot

D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies

PV degradation	0,00%	0,80%	1,60%	2,40%	3,20%	4,00%	4,80%	5,60%	6,40%	7,20%	8,00%
Year	Initial Invest.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
SCENARIO 3: PV/PV-T + EEB + HP											
Equipment (€)	21.478 €					997 €					997 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)		260 €	267 €	275 €	282 €	289 €	296 €	304 €	311 €	318 €	325 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)		0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)		250 €	254 €	257 €	261 €	265 €	269 €	273 €	277 €	281 €	285 €
TOTAL	21.478 €	21.987 €	22.508 €	23.040 €	23.583 €	25.134 €	25.699 €	26.276 €	26.863 €	27.463 €	29.070 €
Year	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
SAVINGS		-16.853 €	-16.223 €	-15.586 €	-14.944 €	-15.292 €	-14.637 €	-13.976 €	-13.307 €	-12.630 €	-12.943 €

PV degradation	8,80%	9,60%	10,40%	11,20%	12,00%	12,80%	13,60%	14,40%	15,20%	16,00%
Year	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
SCENARIO 3: PV/PV-T + EEB + HP										
Equipment (€)					997 €					997 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)	333 €	340 €	347 €	355 €	362 €	369 €	376 €	384 €	391 €	398 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)	290 €	294 €	298 €	303 €	307 €	312 €	317 €	321 €	326 €	331 €
TOTAL	29.692 €	30.326 €	30.972 €	31.629 €	33.295 €	33.976 €	34.669 €	35.374 €	36.091 €	37.817 €
Year	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
SAVINGS	-12.251 €	-11.551 €	-10.843 €	-10.126 €	-6.398 €	-5.663 €	-4.919 €	-4.165 €	-3.402 €	-3.625 €

PV degradation	16,80%	17,60%	18,40%	0,00%	0,80%	1,60%	2,40%	3,20%	4,00%	4,80%
Year	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
SCENARIO 3: PV/PV-T + EEB + HP										
Equipment (€)				21.478 €					997 €	
Energy cost (electricity) (€)	405 €	413 €	420 €	253 €	256 €	263 €	271 €	278 €	285 €	292 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)	336 €	341 €	346 €	351 €	357 €	357 €	357 €	357 €	357 €	357 €
TOTAL	38.558 €	39.312 €	40.078 €	62.160 €	62.773 €	63.393 €	64.020 €	64.654 €	66.293 €	66.941 €
Year	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
SAVINGS	-2.842 €	-2.048 €	-1.243 €	-21.729 €	-20.724 €	-19.725 €	-18.733 €	-17.749 €	-17.769 €	-12.799 €

Table 35 Financial feasibility scenario 3 (PV/PV-T + EEB + HP) within 30 years for Corby pilot

D6.1 Business models analysis for the case studies

PV degradation	0,00%	0,80%	1,60%	2,40%	3,20%	4,00%	4,80%	5,60%	6,40%	7,20%	8,00%
Year	Initial Invest.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
SCENARIO 4: PV/PV-T + EEB + HP (50% GRANT)											
Equipment (€)	10.739 €					997 €					997 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)		260 €	267 €	275 €	282 €	289 €	296 €	304 €	311 €	318 €	325 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)		0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)		250 €	250 €	250 €	250 €	250 €	250 €	250 €	250 €	250 €	250 €
TOTAL	10.739 €	11.249 €	11.766 €	12.290 €	12.822 €	14.358 €	14.904 €	15.458 €	16.019 €	16.587 €	18.160 €
Year		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
SAVINGS		-6.114 €	-5.480 €	-4.837 €	-4.183 €	-4.516 €	-3.843 €	-3.158 €	-2.462 €	-1.755 €	-2.033 €

PV degradation	8,80%	9,60%	10,40%	11,20%	12,00%	12,80%	13,60%	14,40%	15,20%	16,00%
Year	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
SCENARIO 4: PV/PV-T + EEB + HP (50% GRANT)										
Equipment (€)					997 €					997 €
Energy cost (electricity) (€)	333 €	340 €	347 €	355 €	362 €	369 €	376 €	384 €	391 €	398 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)	250 €	250 €	250 €	250 €	250 €	250 €	250 €	250 €	250 €	250 €
TOTAL	18.742 €	19.332 €	19.930 €	20.534 €	22.143 €	22.762 €	23.388 €	24.022 €	24.663 €	26.308 €
Year	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
SAVINGS	-1.301 €	-557 €	199 €	969 €	4.755 €	5.551 €	6.362 €	7.187 €	8.026 €	7.884 €

PV degradation	16,80%	17,60%	18,40%	0,00%	0,80%	1,60%	2,40%	3,20%	4,00%	4,80%
Year	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
SCENARIO 4: PV/PV-T + EEB + HP (50% GRANT)										
Equipment (€)				10.739 €					997 €	
Energy cost (electricity) (€)	405 €	413 €	420 €	253 €	256 €	263 €	271 €	278 €	285 €	292 €
Energy cost (natural gas) (€)	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
Operation & Maintenance cost (€)	250 €	250 €	250 €	250 €	250 €	250 €	250 €	250 €	250 €	250 €
TOTAL	26.963 €	27.626 €	28.296 €	39.537 €	40.043 €	40.557 €	41.077 €	41.605 €	43.137 €	43.679 €
Year	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
SAVINGS	8.754 €	9.639 €	10.540 €	893 €	2.006 €	3.111 €	4.209 €	5.300 €	5.387 €	10.464 €

Table 36 Financial feasibility scenario 4 (PV/PV-T + EEB + HP with a 50% grant on initial investment costs) within 30 years for Corby pilot

Figure 50 Financial feasibility scenarios within 30 years for Corby pilot

Notice that the new business plan simulations within the private partnership BM also include the investment costs, energy costs (both electrical and thermal) and O&M costs as in the ESCO BM. In that case, and as stated in the beginning, the only considered normative O&M costs, that is, the P₂ provision with the minimum cost to comply with local regulations in terms of O&M. No P₃ and P₄ provision has been considered for the private partnership BM.

That being said, many conclusions and recommendations can be taken from the private partnership BM through the comparative financial feasibility analysis within 30 years:

- The first scenario (PV/PV-T-only) is amortized by the client in 13 to 14 years, which offers an accumulated economic save of 9.964€ at year 23 (just the year before the replacement of the main PV system components is needed) and of 8.329€ in 30 years in relation to the baseline scenario. These indicators are not as good as the actual scenarios where PV is deployed either in residential clients or small offices/commercial/industrial clients (payback returns between 8 and 12 years) but they still show that the first scenario is feasible and profitable for the client;
- The second scenario (PV/PV-T + EEB) is amortized by the client in 14 to 15 years, which offers an accumulated economic save of 8.083€ at year 23 (just the year before the replacement of the main PV and HP system components is needed) and of 4.992€ in 30 years in relation to the baseline scenario. That's caused by the fact that the required investment at year 24 needs to be again amortized, but as the accumulated cost savings at year 23 is 8.083€, the second payback return is lowered to less than 7 years in comparison with the baseline scenario costs. Anyways, and as seen earlier, the second scenario is also feasible and profitable for the client but with a significant decrease compared to the first scenario;
- The third scenario (PV/PV-T + EEB + HP) is not profitable. Compared with the baseline scenario, the accumulated economic savings by year 23 are -1,243€ and by the year 30 it increases up to -12,799€. That's mainly due to the fact that such a relevant initial investment cost could not be amortized considering the lifespan of all related equipment and the energy and cost savings provided. Therefore, and under the actual pilot's deployed conditions, this scenario would not be profitable for the client;
- The fourth scenario (PV/PV-T + EEB + HP with a 50% grant on initial investment costs) is amortized by the client in 12 to 13 years, which offers an accumulated economic save of 10,540€ at year 23 (just the year before the replacement of the main PV system components is needed) and of 10,464€ in 30 years in relation to the baseline scenario. Therefore, the fourth scenario is also feasible and profitable for the client and shows a similar payback and accumulated economic savings as in the first scenario (PV/PV-T-only), meaning that lowering investment costs while keeping the expected energy savings and O&M costs results in a relevant payback decrease and a significant

increase in accumulated economic savings of the deployed CHESSE SETUP system.

As Corby's pilot site private partnership BM shows, it looks like under the conditions in which the CHESSE SETUP system has been deployed in this pilot, the overall PV-T + EEB + HP system's investment costs make it unprofitable for the client. That can be seen from the perspective that the residential applications of both STES and HP systems might need to be improved or that a different approach should be considered while deploying STES systems in residential environments. As stated through Sant Cugat's pilot experience, the overall system should offer an increased performance and/or reduced investment + O&M costs in comparison to the baseline scenario, so that these kind of coupled solutions do offer financial profitability, cost and energy savings and a reduced environmental impact at a minimum risk and in small time windows (about 10 years at maximum).

12. Conclusions and recommendations

This Deliverable offers an overall approach to business model (BM) comprehension and its application to the energy services market. First of all, an overview of European Union's energy services market was provided, realizing that almost 50% of ESCO revenues in Europe come from Energy Performance Contracts – Guaranteed Savings models (EPC – GS), about a 15% comes from Energy Performance Contracts – Shared Savings models (EPC _ SS) and 25% comes from Energy Supply Contracts (ESC). But the first question arouses: what is a BM? Different and varied expert authors have similar definitions and approaches but Osterwalder *et al.* do offer a respected and concise approach, stating that *“a business model is a conceptual tool containing a set of objects, concepts and their relationship with the objective to express the business logic of a specific firm. Therefore, we must consider which concepts and relationships allow a simplified description and representation of what value is provided to customers, how this is done and with which financial consequences”*. The main difference between a BM and a business strategy is that first one deals with the definition, classification and modelling of the business (how to fit the pieces together) and the second one explains how you will do better than your rivals. Strategy usually contemplates the execution and implementation while BM is more about how a business works as a system.

That being said, this report offered a deep review on the main methodologies to create and assess BM. The e³ – value ontology is meant to represent a networked business model, including its actors, links and the way the economic value is translated from one to another. The basic cornerstone of it is *“the notion of economic value, and how actors create, exchange and consume objects of economic value”* [11]. In the other hand, SWOT ontology is meant to offer a deep analysis of internal strengths and weaknesses, as well as external opportunities and threats in an organization's environment. Following what Sammut-Bonicci *et al.* stated in one of their papers, *“The internal analysis is used to identify resources, capabilities, core competencies, and competitive advantages inherent to the organization. The external analysis identifies market opportunities and threats by looking at competitors' resources, the industry environment, and the general environment. The objective of a SWOT analysis is to use the knowledge an organization has about its internal and external environments and to formulate its strategy accordingly”* [12]. Finally, one of the best (and worldly recognized) options while creating and assessing a BM is the Canvas ontology: this business model ontology is a tool for describing, analysing and designing business models developed by Alexander Osterwalder and Yves Pigneur. Based on many experiences from people all over the world, the *Business model generation* book points out how should it be used in order to *“translate their business plans into the business processes that they (will) need to operate their business and that they are focused properly on being customer-centred in a way that makes the business as highly profitable as can be”* (Bob Dunn, U.S.) [9].

Applying these BM creation and assessment methodology, the energy services market found its own way of defining different partnerships and revenue streams,

such as private, public or public – private partnerships (as well as other joint ventures) that increase overall's BM performance. Many value-added services (VAS) have risen out over the last years, whether if they're provided by utilities, third-party providers or even public entities acting as super ESCOs and so on. Many authors have already analysed tens of BMs applied to distributed energy resources (DERs) as Burger & Luke, which have stated that there already are BMs focused on energy storage for end-user customers or event energy storage and PV generation optimization (and co-optimization) for end-user customers, clearly defining a match between both technologies to work together to increase overall services' profitability.

After all that theoretical approach, the next sections focused on providing a proposal of an ESCO BM for the CHESSE SETUP project, which is a translation of the Energy Savings and Maintenance Contracting model (a mix between ESC and EPC) which was introduced by the *Instituto para la Diversificación y el Ahorro de la Energía (IDAE)*. This model is composed by the following terms:

- P1: Energy Management
- P2: Maintenance
- P3: Full Warranty
- P4: Improvement works and renewal of installations

The most attractive point of this model is the externalization of the energy services. From an energy saving engagement, the ESCO "takes control" of the client's installation and ensures an improvement on the energy consumption after its exploitation and some investments, which costs will be amortized at the end of the contract. After that, when the contract runs out, the client has a more efficient installation with a lower energy consumption.

The key point during the ESCO's exploitation of the installation remains in the control and motorization increase in order to reduce the operational costs. One of the main goals of this type of contract is that it offers different types of contracting depending on the client's needs. This combination of services allows the ESCO to generate its business plan depending on the different needs that the client may have and determinate how to make its offer more attractive and profitable.

Moving on, the following sections offer the main barriers and success factors of the proposed ESCO BM as well as the Measure and Verification Plan (M&V). In order to calculate energy savings of the different thermal solutions, a Measure and Verification Plan must be developed, establishing the baseline energy consumption of the buildings involved as demonstration pilot sites depending on the environmental conditions and internal use of each building. Based on the International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol (IPMVP), developed by the Efficiency Valuation Organization (EVO) which is a non-profit private association [23] [24], this report offers an application of the IPMVP for the CHESSE SETUP project. The main purpose of the M&V in the context of EPC contracts in buildings is to present the

economic performance of an improvement project on them. The M&V Plan becomes part of the contractual terms of the EPC contract, defining the measures and calculations to be performed in order to determine the payments between the ESCO and the client, or to demonstrate the achievement of a guaranteed level of efficiency.

After all the main concepts involved are clear and their implementation for the CHESS SETUP project is understood, the last section offers a deep, concise and vast application of the ESCO BM proposal for each demonstration pilot site. As seen previously, each of the three reference cases/demonstration pilot sites has its own singularities or peculiarities that are being summarized in the following points (following last section's structure):

- Depending on the client's financial capacity, the chosen EPC changes the financial status but either if it's a guaranteed savings model or a shared savings model, the client relies on the ESCO to assume all technical risks as it provides all project development and implementation costs. The client can rely on the ESCO to assume all financial risks via contractual arrangement (P₄), normally with an interest rate lower than the bank's but again assuming all technical risk.
- The Net Present Value (NPV) represents one of the best financial profitability indicators; it is a useful tool to determine whether a project or investment will result in a net profit or a loss. Whenever the NPV is positive, the project is profitable; in all business plan simulations for the 3 reference cases, the NPV is positive, with its value increasing when the project's duration is longer:
 - For Lavola's Ecobuilding, the NPV is 3,566.15 € for the 5-year contract, 5,613.38 € for the 8-year contract and 6,694.30 € for the 10-year contract;
 - For Sant Cugat's Sports Centre, the NPV is 23,917.75 € for the 5-year contract, 26,143.12 € for the 8-year contract and 30,480.24 € for the 10-year contract;
 - For a 3-bedroom townhouse Ecohome at Corby (which can be translated to all townhouses built with the same characteristics and under the same contract services), the NPV is 1,895.29 € for the 5-year contract, 2,324.11 € for the 8-year contract and 2,561.24 € for the 10-year contract.
- The Internal Rate of Return (IRR) is another of the best financial profitability indicators; it is defined as the rate of return that sets the NPV of all cash flows for the investment equal to zero, meaning that it is the discount rate at which the NPV of the future cash flows is equal to the initial investment. The IRR is a relative profitability indicator of the project, but not an absolute profitability indicator. When comparing different internal rates of return of two projects, the possible difference over their size is not considered (neither do other external factors as inflation, cost of capital or various financial risks). A project with a huge investment and a low IRR can have a bigger NPV than a lower investment project with a higher IRR; in conclusion, IRR cannot be considered as an alternative to NPV but as a complementary information while comparing

different project's profitability. Whenever the IRR is positive, the project is profitable; in all business plan simulations for the three reference cases, the IRR is positive, with its value decreasing when the project's duration is longer:

- For Lavola's Ecobuilding, the IRR is 6.59% for the 5-year contract, 5.47% for the 8-year contract and 5.13% for the 10-year contract;
 - For Sant Cugat's Sports Centre, the IRR is 6.83% for the 5-year contract, 5.69% for the 8-year contract and 5.35% for the 10-year contract;
 - For a 3-bedroom townhouse Ecohome at Corby (which can be translated to all townhouses built with the same characteristics and under the same contract services), the IRR is 10.84% for the 5-year contract, 9.71% for the 8-year contract and 9.33% for the 10-year contract.
- Each of the Energy Savings and Maintenance Contracting terms (P₁ – Energy Management; P₂ – Maintenance; P₃ – Full Warranty and P₄ – Improvement works and renewal of installations) for each of the three demonstration pilot sites is:
 - For Lavola's Ecobuilding, the initial investment is 113,426.03 €. Considering a 5-year contract, the client would have to assume an annual installation financing cost (P₄) of 28,818 €/year to finance the installation, which decreases to 19,304 €/year for an 8-year contract and to 16,158 €/year for a 10-year contract. The annual maintenance service cost (P₂) is approximately 1,813.00€/year and the annual full warranty service cost (P₃) ranges between 701.00€/year and 991.00€/year (5-year to 10-year EPC).
 - For Sant Cugat's Sports Centre, the initial investment is 661,922.12 €. Considering a 5-year contract, the client would have to assume an annual installation financing cost (P₄) of 168,176 €/year to finance the installation, which decreases to 112,655 €/year for an 8-year contract and to 94,294 €/year for a 10-year contract. The annual maintenance service cost (P₂) is approximately 3,818.00€/year and the annual full warranty service cost (P₃) ranges between 1,560.00€/year and 2,206.00€/year (5-year to 10-year EPC).
 - For a 3-bedroom townhouse Ecohome at Corby, the initial investment is 22,050.85 €. Considering a 5-year contract, the client would have to assume an annual installation financing cost (P₄) of 5,603 €/year to finance the installation, which decreases to 3,753 €/year for an 8-year contract and to 3,141 €/year for a 10-year contract. The annual maintenance service cost (P₂) is approximately 765.00€/year and the annual full warranty service cost (P₃) ranges between 184.00€/year and 260.00€/year (5-year to 10-year EPC).
 - Regarding the energy savings and GHG emission prevention that has been either simulated and/or extracted from data collected by the monitoring &

control system from each of the three demonstration pilot sites during the reporting period:

- For Lavola's Ecobuilding, a total amount of 11,058.36 kWh_e as primary electricity energy savings has been estimated to come from PV panels' energy production. That being said, the overall electricity consumption is increased as the new ASHP installed consumes about 33,423.67 kWh_e, therefore a total amount of a total amount of 79,364.34 kWh_{PCI} as primary thermal energy savings has been estimated to come from ASHP thermal energy production. This translates to an annual energy cost savings of approximately 2,765 €/year, while the reported payback for the CHESSE SETUP system deployment for this reference case is approximately 41.02 years. That also means a total amount of 18,934.48 kg of CO₂ saved as GHG emissions each year
- For Sant Cugat's Sports Centre, a total amount of 31,976 kWh_e as primary electricity energy savings has been estimated to come from hybrid PV-T panels' energy production. In the same path, a total amount of 224,045 kWh_{PCI} as primary thermal energy savings has been estimated, combining thermal generation coming from hybrid PV-T panels and sensible heat storage (SHS) performed in the tank thermal energy storage (TTES) in the form of a 100 m³ water tank installed in Sant Cugat's Sport Centre. This translates to an annual energy cost savings of approximately 14,217 €/year, while the reported payback for the CHESSE SETUP system deployment for this reference case is approximately 46.55 years. That also means a total amount of 61,138.11 kg of CO₂ saved as GHG emissions each year
- For a 3-bedroom townhouse Ecohome at Corby, a total amount of 4,269.32 kWh_e as primary electricity energy savings has been estimated to come from PV panels' energy production. That being said, the overall electricity consumption is increased as the new GSHP installed consumes about 2,045.38 kWh_e, increasing overall electricity consumption from 3,412.00 kWh_e to 5,457.38 kWh_e. In the same path, a total amount of 4,228.75 kWh_{PCI} as primary thermal energy savings has been estimated, combining thermal generation coming from hybrid PV-T panels and sensible heat storage (SHS) performed at the EEB in the form of a borehole matrix under the 3-bedroom townhouse. This translates to an annual energy cost savings of approximately 836 €/year, while the reported payback for the CHESSE SETUP system deployment for this reference case is approximately 26.37 years. That also means a total amount of 1,841.89 kg of CO₂ saved as GHG emissions each year

After reviewing the CHESSE SETUP system deployment results at each of the three reference cases, some common concluding thoughts must be highlighted and many improvement proposals have been pointed out to increase the CHESSE SETUP project's profitability:

- A common problem of all reference cases is the high budget allocated to architecture works, to both PV-T and/or PV-only panels installation or to the heat pump solution. Although PV panel cost has been already decreasing over the last decades, many suppliers do now offer integrated solutions adaptable either for new or existing buildings, therefore reducing architecture works (mainly PV panel structure and reinforcements) and improving overall system's cost. Solar PVT panels are more expensive than the price of traditional solar PV panels. Having said that, Solar PV-T systems can be installed at almost the same cost as the equivalent capacity of separate PV and Solar thermal and so can be a sensible investment where roof space is tight; anyways, the PV-T panel is roughly 10% more expensive than the cost of an individual PV panel and solar thermal panel installation, which needs to be improved and correctly matched with some form of heat storage, leveraging thermal and electrical production with building's energy demand through an optimal RES integrated energy infrastructure.
- Another problem detected is the high budget allocated to TTES implementation. As stated in Deliverable 2.1, in order to provide efficient results while operating STES systems, water tanks should have storage volumes over 1,000 m³; many examples of existing SSHS around Europe use TTES with a maximum capacity between 2,750 – 10,000 m³, which significantly reduces investment costs (for water tank volumes under 500 m³, investment costs can range between 450 – 500 €/m³ while water tank volumes over 10,000 m³ reached investment costs of around 50 €/m³). Following the same path, hot water TTES offer a thermal storage capacity of 60 – 80 kWh/m³, with an efficiency between 50 – 90 %. Therefore, increasing the TTES capacity implies a considerable investment cost decrease while significantly increasing the thermal storage capacity, thus providing a considerable increase on thermal energy (and cost) savings.
- Further thoughts regarding the heat pump must be mentioned: as the heat pump must get the heat from the outdoor environment, therefore whenever the outdoor temperature is lower, the amount of energy absorbed from it would decrease. That means that, in order to satisfy the thermal demand from a room/building, if the outdoor temperature is lower the electrical or thermal energy consumed by the compressor would be higher. As we must stick to weather conditions from each geographical area, and as stated in Deliverables 3.4 and 3.5 about the heat pump design, the performance of a heat pump depends on the temperature of the heat source, the heat sink, the working medium, the arrangement, the thermodynamic cycle conditions, the characteristics of the components of the controlling system, etc. Current guides and standardised procedures to measure seasonal performance factor (SPF) do also consider a weight factor depending on the heat pump technology: the supplier usually offers a COP referred to a condensation temperature that might not be the operation temperature of the equipment/system. The technical justification is that the COP decrease

according to the condensation temperature's increase does not depend on the energy source (air, water or ground) but that temperature indeed has an impact on the heat pump performance: whenever the fluid's working temperature is lower, it will ease the refrigerant's condensation, therefore increasing COP and thermal power supplied by the heat pump. This weight factor is only applied to electrical-driven heat pumps.

Once the main issues about the CHESS SETUP system deployment have been detected, this report offers many recommendations/improvement proposals so that further deployments of the CHESS SETUP solution could be more effective, efficient and profitable:

- **Increase PV-T and STES performance:** TES systems are key components in a system with thermal/PVT panels and heat pumps that require an active storage system. Before choosing the most suitable storage, it is required to identify some important parameters of the projected system: production temperatures, heating temperatures, storage capacity, thermal power, storage duration, space availability and energy costs. In thermal/PVT panels and heat pump installations, two types of thermal storage are being projected: buffer/daily storage and a Seasonal Thermal Energy Storage (STES). Thermal/PVT panels will be installed upstream of STES storage, while heat pumps will be connected downstream of STES storage and upstream of buffer/daily storage. STES should be dimensioned to be able to store all the excess energy of the summer period; in the specific case of PVT panels STES will have low output temperatures, thus temperature storage will be low. Temperatures of storage will even be lower if a heat exchanger has to be installed between PVT and STES. In both cases STES will have low energy density and a large volume. The best adapted technology for STES are SHS systems. PTES and TTES have the advantage of permitting a good stratification, have a high efficiency (if well-isolated) and low temperature hysteresis between charging and discharging. Volume occupation is the biggest disadvantage. Adding Gravel in PTES or TTES decreases the performance of the system, reducing energy density and stratification. The temperature of storage of buffer/daily storage should be in accordance with the installation and required temperatures of the existing heating and DHW demand. In the particular case of PCM/TCM storage a heat exchanger has to be installed, thus its temperature difference between primary/secondary materials implies a higher temperature energy storage. As in STES storage, for buffer/daily storage, the most used storage is water tanks, due mainly to cost, stratification properties and low temperature hysteresis between charging and discharging. Water tanks' most notable disadvantages are the lowest temperature stability and the low energy density.
- **Increase HP performance:** following the previous statements, and knowing that the heat pump cost cannot be reduced as it's a fixed budget line given by

the selected supplier, what can be done is improve the heat pump performance. As we must stick to weather conditions from each geographical area, and as stated in Deliverables 3.4 and 3.5 about the heat pump design, the performance of a heat pump depends on the temperature of the heat source, the heat sink, the working medium, the arrangement, the thermodynamic cycle conditions, the characteristics of the components of the controlling system, etc.

For so, the refrigerant selection has a direct impact on the overall cost and lifecycle of the system and should be considered as an improvement proposal in the heat pump design; as new regulations impose strict limitations to hydrofluorocarbons (HFC), hydro-fluoro-olefins (HFOs) and other types of refrigerants should be the next path in the research and development about heat pump technology as an alternative low global warming potential (GWP) working fluid. Considering both condenser and evaporator refrigerant temperatures, the overall thermodynamic cycle's performance can be increased, therefore reducing the amount of work (either in form of electrical or thermal energy) required to compress the refrigerant. In order to have an adequate performance, heat pumps need to have a stable input temperature and flow from STES storage (evaporator side) and a stable input temperature and flow from buffer/daily storage (condenser side).

- **Reduce investment costs:** although in the reference case it has not a significant impact on the IRR, its calculation mainly depends on the cash flow of each period which is totally linked to the P₄ financial investment quote to be paid by the client. Whenever this cash flow is lower and the project's duration is kept, the IRR will increase. Therefore, the investment will be more profitable, indicating that the return of the investment is sooner than before.

That is the best option for the client: whenever investment costs are reduced, annual P₄ quote will also decrease, therefore increasing financial profitability for the client as, at the same energy and cost savings provided by the new technology deployed, lower investment needs to be recovered. Therefore, the recovery time is significantly lower, which is also a positive factor for the ESCO as it will be easier to sell the P₄ annual quote to the client.

- **Increase profit margin over investment costs:** paradoxically, when increasing the profit margin over investment costs, the cash flow of each period is increased but the ESCO's P₄ cost remains the same. That means that if the ESCO is able to reduce material and mankind costs (thus improving profit margin over investment costs), the IRR will significantly increase.

Following previous arguments on reducing investment costs, whenever the ESCO can increase its profit margin but in a lower proportion than the investment cost decrease, both ESCO and client could benefit from it. As obvious, when increasing profit margins over investment costs that implies increasing P₄ annual quote to the detriment of the client's interests. Therefore,

the ESCO could increase profit margin over investment costs as long as it is able to reduce in the same or bigger proportion the investment costs. That being said, that proposal highly depends on the cost proportion over the rest of services: whenever the P₄ annual quote represents a high percentage of energy service package provided, increasing the margin profit will result in a significant increase of overall project's NPV and IRR but if P₄ annual quote represents a low percentage of all energy service package provided, the impact will be significantly lower. That depends on each and every project, as different variables do integrate the algorithm calculation of each energy services quote depending on the technology deployed, the contract's duration and other technical/economic indicators.

- **Increase profit margin over maintenance and warranty services:** the same as abovementioned. Depending on the annual quote of maintenance (P₂) and full warranty (P₃) services compared to improvement works and renewal of installations (P₄), it might be better to increase profit margins over those services rather than looking for a P₄ reduction. That highly depends on the client: in our case, it is better to go for a P₄ reduction as it represents the main cost of the contract (since it offers the financing of a significant initial investment with small operation, maintenance and substitution costs when the contract is lower than the main equipment's' lifespan) rather than improving/increasing profit margins over P₂ and P₃.

The argumentation from previous sections still applies to P₂ and P₃ annual quotes: when increasing profit margins over maintenance and warranty services, the ESCO improve overall financial profitability to the detriment of the client's interests, as the new annual quote is increased. Therefore, and as stated before, that proposal highly depends on the cost proportion over the rest of services and has to be matched with the client's interests.

After having seen the results of the private partnership BM simulations, it looks clear that different scenarios are feasible and profitable for the client. In those terms:

- If the client does already have a tank/storage facility that could be easily adapted as a STES (useable water tank formerly used for other purposes e.g. fire emergency, drinking water supply water systems, fuel storage, etc.) and also has a heating/cooling generation unit (boiler/HP/chiller, etc.) to satisfy the heating/cooling/DHW demand, it would just be needed to deploy a RES generation system. When referring to PV/PV-T systems' deployment, those have been proven to be technically viable and economically profitable, with reported paybacks between 10 and 14 years within the CHESSETUP project's experience;
- If the client does not already have a tank/storage facility that could be easily adapted as a SHS but no need of extra construction/civil works is needed, the most suitable client would be the one who has room availability either inside its facilities (mainly modular/monolith tanks from different materials allocated

in an accessible room) or outside (mainly modular/monolith tanks fully or partially buried in the ground such as TTES, ATES, BTES, GWTES or PTES) for the deployment of a STES. If the client did already have a heating/cooling generation unit (boiler/HP/chiller, etc.) and a heat exchange system to satisfy the heating/cooling/DHW demand, it would only need to deploy the RES generation system and the STES;

- If the client needs to deploy the whole CHESS SETUP system – both RES generation, STES and heat exchange systems as well as a heating/cooling generation unit (boiler/HP/chiller, etc.) to satisfy the heating/cooling/DHW demand – the project offers relatively small incomes and benefits in terms of cost savings. The positive environmental impact is noticeable but the accumulated energy and cost savings are relatively small when compared to such an important initial investment cost.

In the same path, and as it is also stated in EHPA's White Paper: Heat Pumps - Integrating Technologies to Decarbonise Heating and Cooling (2018), innovative business model proposals such as the ESCO or the private partnership ones proposed could improve the deployment of the CHESS SETUP and other related systems:

"Today's dominant business model in the heating industry is based on manufacturing a boiler and selling it to the end customer via wholesalers or installers. Value is created by manufacturing, installing and maintaining the product as well as by providing the energy to operate it. The end-user pays for both, the product and the energy needed to operate it and banks act as intermediaries to provide financing. Planners and architects are responsible for the design of the buildings, also influencing the technical specification of the required system and thus the purchase decision. Innovative institutional and financial support (in particular if it honours environmental benefits) can shape the selection of the product and the total cost of ownership.

The value proposition is a working heating system, owned by the end-user. It is designed by experts and delivered by skilled craftsmen who install and – in case of malfunction – maintain the system. Even though end-users buy branded products, the relation between manufacturer and user is indirect. When it comes to cooling, the same applies: the user has a demand for cooling, addresses an expert who designs the system which is then installed and later maintained by an installer company.

As heating and cooling services are often perceived to be disconnected, they will also be offered by different parties, making integrated solutions a challenge and the inherent cost reduction potential of providing two services with one application difficult to unleash.

When it comes to larger capacity heat pumps that are deployed in multifamily and commercial buildings, multi-building complexes and district heating systems, use a different business model already today. Based on a service model, the end-user pays for the delivery of heating/cooling.

This approach is becoming now feasible for aggregated numbers of individual heat pumps or even individual units. The increased availability of sensors and computing power as well as access to high speed data grids, the option to aggregate and to control larger numbers of products allows a new perspective on the product.

With a redefined value proposition, the offering is no longer a physical product but a more or less comprehensive package consisting of hardware, software and support in terms of planning, financing, insurance, maintenance etc.

Heat/cooling becomes a service that the user enjoys and pays for, while the service provider/operator takes ownership and is also responsible for system design and operations. Optimising design, monitoring operations and the provision of timely maintenance leads to reduced operating cost and thus optimised profits" [32].

	STANDARD BUSINESS MODEL	SERVICE BASED BUSINESS MODEL	DEMAND SIDE FLEXIBILITY BASED SERVICE MODEL
VALUE	Product and energy source as two different products offered to the user	Heating/cooling as service offered to the user	Indoor comfort in return for system services and access to data
KEY PARTNERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Manufacturers of heat pumps ▶ Utilities 	Energy service company or energy performance company	Grid operator
SALES CHANNEL PER CUSTOMER SEGMENT	From manufacturer via end user via a number of support parties (planner, installer)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Commercial: direct from service to end-consumer with a variety of service approaches ▶ Industrial: direct from developer to end-consumer 	Direct from integrator to prosumer

Figure 51 Business models for heat pumps (Source: [32])

References

- [1] B. B. P. Boza - Kiss and M. Economidou, "Energy Service Companies in the EU - Status review and recommendations for further market development with a focus on Energy Performance Contracting," Publications Office of the European Union, 2017, Luxembourg, 2017.
- [2] The Economist, "Energy and Technology. Let there be light," *The Economist*, pp. 1-10, 17 January 2015.
- [3] International Energy Agency, "Energy Efficiency 2018. Analysis and outlooks to 2040," 2018.
- [4] International Energy Agency, "Energy Service Companies (ESCOs). At the heart of innovative financing models for efficiency," 26 November 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iea.org/data-and-statistics/charts/esco-revenues-by-contract-type>. [Accessed 30 December 2019].
- [5] J. Magretta, "Why Business Models Matter," *Harvard Business Review*, pp. 86-92, 2002.
- [6] A. Ovans, "What Is a Business Model?," *Harvard Business Review*, 2015.
- [7] A. Osterwalder, Y. Pigneur and C. L. Tucci, "Clarifying Business Models: Origins, Present, and Future of the Concept," *Communications of the Association for Information Systems*, vol. XV, no. 1, pp. 1-25, 2005.
- [8] A. Osterwalder and Y. Pigneur, "An ontology for e-Business models," in *Value creation from e-Business models*, Burlington, Boston (USA), Elsevier Butterworth-Heinemann, 2004, pp. 65-97.
- [9] A. Osterwalder and Y. Pigneur, *Business Model Generation: A handbook for visionaries, game changers and challengers*, New York: John Wiley & Sons Inc, 2010.
- [10] A. Osterwalder y Y. Pigneur, «An e-Business Model Ontology for Modeling e-Business,» de *15th Bled Electronic Commerce Conference– eReality: Constructing the eEconomy*, Bled (Slovenia), June 17-19, 2002.
- [11] J. Gordijn, "e-Business value modelling using the e3-value ontology," in *Value creation from e-Business Models*, Burlington, Boston (USA), Elsevier Butterworth-Heinemann, 2004, pp. 98-127.
- [12] T. Sammut-Bonnici y D. Galea, «SWOT Analysis,» de *Wiley Encyclopedia of Management*, John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, 2015.
- [13] CITYInvest Consortium, "CITYInvest | A clever investment in your city!," [Online]. Available: <http://www.cityinvest.eu/content/sunshine-3>. [Accessed January 2020].
- [14] X. Garcia Casals, M. Santmartí and J. Salom, "Smart Energy Communities: Insights into its structure and latent business models," Barcelona, 2019.
- [15] D. Vansintjan and D. Creupelandt, "REScoop – Municipality Approach," 2018.

- [16] D. Vansintjan y D. Creupelandt, «REScoop - Energy Transition to Energy Democracy,» Antwerp (Belgium), 2015.
- [17] A. d. U. d. Barcelona, “BCNecologia,” 2012. [Online]. Available: <http://www.bcnecologia.net/en>. [Accessed 28 January 2019].
- [18] International Energy Agency, “Joint Public-Private Approaches for Energy Efficiency Finance,” Paris, 2011.
- [19] M. Hamelink y R. Opdenakker, «How business model innovation affects firm performance in the energy storage market,» *Renewable Energy*, vol. 131, pp. 120-127, 2019.
- [20] S. P. Burger and M. Luke, “Business Models for Distributed Energy Resources: A Review and Empirical Analysis,” Cambridge (Boston), 2016.
- [21] G. Fong, R. Moreira and G. Strbac, “Economic Analysis of Energy Storage Business Models,” in *2017 IEEE Manchester PowerTech*, Manchester (United Kingdom), 2017.
- [22] I. p. I. D. y. A. d. I. E. (IDAE), “Propuesta de modelo de Contrato de Servicios Energéticos y Mantenimiento en Edificios de las Administraciones Públicas,” Madrid, 2007.
- [23] Efficiency Valuation Organization (EVO), “EVO | Efficiency Valuation Organization,” December 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://evo-world.org/en/products-services-mainmenu-en/protocols/ipmvp>.
- [24] Efficiency Valuation Organization (EVO), «International Performance, Measurement and Verification Protocol of Energy Performance. Concepts and options to determine energy and water savings. Volume I,» 2012.
- [25] International Energy Agency (IEA), «Energy Service Companies (ESCOs). At the heart of innovative financing models for efficiency,» ESCO contracts, December 2018. [En línea]. Available: <https://www.iea.org/reports/energy-service-companies-escos-2/esco-contracts>. [Último acceso: July 2020].
- [26] Banco de España, “Tipos de interés aplicados por las entidades de crédito,” January 2020. [Online]. Available: https://clientebancario.bde.es/pcb/es/menu-horizontal/productosservici/relacionados/tiposinteres/guia-textual/tiposinteresprac/Tabla_de_tipos__a0b053c69a40f51.html. [Accessed July 2020].
- [27] C. Begeal and T. Decker, “Solar Thermal Energy Storage,” in *Large Energy Storage Systems Handbook*, 2011, pp. 182-200.
- [28] Bank of England, “Monthly average rate of discount, 3 month Treasury bills, Sterling,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.bankofengland.co.uk/boeapps/database/fromshowcolumns.asp?Travel=NlxAZxSUx&FromSeries=1&ToSeries=50&DAT=RNG&FD=1&FM=Jan&FY=2010&TD=11&TM=May&TY=2025&FNY=Y&CSVF=TT&html.x=66&html.y=26&SeriesCodes=IUMAAJNB&UsingCodes=Y&Filter=N&title=IUMAAJNB&VPD>. [Accessed August 2020].
- [29] Instituto para la Diversificación y Ahorro de la Energía, «Diseño de sistemas de intercambio

geotérmico de circuito cerrado,» Madrid, 2012.

- [30] MasterTherm Heat Pumps, “Energy Related Products (ErP) Directive – Heat Pump Efficiency,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.mastertherm.co.uk/heat-pump-efficiency>. [Accessed August 2020].
- [31] International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), “Renewable Power Generation Costs in 2019,” IRENA Publications, Abu Dhabi, 2020.
- [32] European Copper Institute, “White Paper: Heat Pumps - Integrating Technologies to Decarbonise Heating and Cooling,” EHPA Publications, 2018.
- [33] S. M. Shafer, H. J. Smith and J. C. Linder, “The power of business models,” *Business Horizons*, vol. 48, no. 3, pp. 199-207, 2005.

Appendix I – CHESS SETUP system maintenance plans

STES Maintenance

	W	BW	M	BM	Q	SM	A
VERIFICATIONS AND OPERATIONS OF MAINTENANCE							
Verify the anomalies of the security elements			X				
Review of the automatic associated control system					X		
Verify the water tightness of the system (tank, valves, joints, etc.)	X						
Verify the effective functioning of the level sensors system			X				
Check the state of the joints and valves of the tank					X		
Check the connections of the tank to the piping system					X		
Check the absence of obstructions in the emptying taps of the tank					X		
Check the functioning of the entrance and exit meter					X		
Verify the water tightness of the interception valves						X	
Review the state of the thermal insulation material							X
Verify the water treatment system (water input)			X				

W:Weekly, BW:Biweekly, M:Monthly, BM:Bimonthly, Q:Quarterly, SM:Six-monthly, A:Annual

Heat Pump Maintenance

	W	BW	M	BM	Q	SM	A
VERIFICATIONS AND OPERATIONS OF MAINTENANCE							
Verify leaks of refrigerant	X	X	X		X	X	X
Check the refrigerant gas loads (bubbles in the viewer)			X				
Verify the lack of humidity in the refrigerant (humidity in the viewer)					X		
Verify the overheating of the thermal expansion valve	X	X	X				
Check the oil condition. Replace if necessary.	X	X	X				
Review the oil load in all the compressors. Add if necessary.			X				
Review the functioning of the crankcase resistance					X		
Verify earthing					X		
Verify the control of the compressors capacity					X		
Readjust the electrical connections of each compressor	X	X			X		
Change compressors sequence					X		
Check strange noises of the compressors	X	X	X				
Check contactors: movement and contacts	X	X	X				
Check circuit breakers (readjust connections)	X	X	X				
Check and adjust the flow valve	X	X			X		
Water control thermostat regulation	X	X			X		
Write down the oil pressure switch cut-off value	X	X			X		
Bearing greasing	X	X					X

Pressure switch and thermostat contrast and adjustment	X	X	X				
Review and clean of the water filter	X	X					X
Write down the anomalies codes	X	X	X				
Check corrosion	X	X					X
CLEANING	X						
Condenser mechanics cleaning							X
MEASUREMENT	X						
Water circuit manometer lecture	X	X	X				
Evaporator's thermal jump	X	X	X				
Condenser's thermal jump	X	X	X				
High and low pressure of the refrigerating circuits	X	X	X				
Compressor's suction and discharge pressure	X	X	X				
Liquid's line temperature	X	X	X				
Refrigerating circuit suction aspiration temperature	X	X	X				
Refrigerating circuit overheating level	X	X	X				
Refrigerating circuit sub cooling level	X	X	X				
Oil temperature	X	X	X				
Compressor and crankcase's resistances consumption	X	X	X				

W:Weekly, BW:Biweekly, M:Monthly, BM:Bimonthly, Q:Quarterly, SM:Six-monthly, A:Annual

Buffer Maintenance

	W	BW	M	BM	Q	SM	A
VERIFICATIONS AND OPERATIONS OF MAINTENANCE							
Visual inspection of leaks	X	X	X				
Visual check of the piping system. Look for leaks.			X				
Review of the galvanic anode and change if necessary						X	
CLEANING							
General clean of the water filters			X				
Heating elements and tank cleaning							X
General review of the tank isolation							X
Verify the security devices							X
MEASUREMENT							
Hot water temperature distribution	X	X	X				
Hot water consumption			X				

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Solar Installation Maintenance

	W	BW	M	BM	Q	SM	A
VERIFICATIONS AND OPERATIONS OF MAINTENANCE							
Verify the circuit's temperature	X	X	X		X	X	X
Review the level of glycol			X				
Verify the leakproofness of the circuit			X				
Verify the absence of condensation during the central hours of the day	X	X		X	X	X	X
Verify cracks, deformations corrosions or joint leaks	X	X		X	X	X	
Verify the lack of degradation and corrosion in the absorption tube	X	X		X	X	X	
Manual purge of the primary circuit	X	X		X	X	X	
Verify the state of the piping system and isolation of the circuit	X	X		X		X	
CLEANING							
Cleaning of the panel glasses with water and suitable product	X	X	X				

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Other Equipment

PUMPS

	W	BW	M	BM	Q	SM	A
VERIFICATIONS AND OPERATIONS OF MAINTENANCE							
Test the backup pump, in the case of double pumps	X	X	X				
Inspection of operation: noise and vibrations			X				
Check the wear of the bearings			X				
Verify the lubrication and greasing of the bearings	X	X	X				
Verify the lack of leaks in the joints	X	X	X				
Verify the drain of refrigeration and absence of leaks (check obstructions)		X	X	X			
Verify the impulse pressure	X	X	X				
Verify the non-return valves	X	X	X				
Verify the cut-off valves	X	X				X	X
Check the electric connection terminals	X						X
Check anti-vibration sleeves	X						X
Leaktightness and pipe connections inspection	X						X
Verification of the circuit breaker	X						X
Vibrations and fixations check	X						X
Verification and adjustment alignment of the group	X						X
Verification and adjustment of the earthing	X						X
Manometers and thermometers contrast	X						X
CLEANING							
	X						

Aspiration filters	X	X	X				
MEASUREMENT	X						
Work pressure	X	X	X	X			

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PLATE EXCHANGER

	W	BW	M	BM	Q	SM	A
VERIFICATIONS AND OPERATIONS OF MAINTENANCE							
Verify the absence of leaks			X		X	X	X
Check joints							X
Thermal insulation review							X
Verify the lack of corrosion							X
Check the heat exchange (clean when necessary)							X
CLEANING							
Primary and secondary circuit							X
MEASUREMENT							
Primary circuit entrance and exit temperatures			X				
Secondary circuit entrance and exit circuit temperatures			X				

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PROBES

	W	BW	M	BM	Q	SM	A
VERIFICATIONS AND OPERATIONS OF MAINTENANCE							
Operational control					X		
Verify the signalling alarm					X		

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PIPE SYSTEM

	W	BW	M	BM	Q	SM	A
VERIFICATIONS AND OPERATIONS OF MAINTENANCE							
Position and state of the pipe supports							X
Review of the thermal insulation							X
Verify the lack of corrosion							X
Verify the lack of expansion							X

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VALVES

	W	BW	M	BM	Q	SM	A
VERIFICATIONS AND OPERATIONS OF MAINTENANCE							
Verify and adjust the closing devices							X
Verify the leaks in the stuffing box							X

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ELECTRIC PANEL

	W	BW	M	BM	Q	SM	A
VERIFICATIONS AND OPERATIONS OF MAINTENANCE							
Verify the state of the fuses			X				
Check the regulation of the circuit breakers			X				
Verify circuit breakers and differentials			X				
Check overheated cables			X				
Verify and readjust electrical connections			X				
Verify switches and circuit breaker function			X				
Contrast and adjustment of measuring devices			X				
Review the protection devices function			X				
Verify the earthing			X				
Verify the electrical insulation			X				
CLEANING							
Electric panel			X				
MEASUREMENT							
Operating hours			X				
Electrical consumption of the refrigerant system			X				

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